

Quantum-Computation and Quantum-Communication

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Abstract

In this research notebook on quantum computation and quantum communication protocol for quantum engineers, researchers, and scientists, we will discuss and summarize the practical challenges of implementing quantum computing algorithms and quantum communication protocols in today's real-world hardware systems. We will begin the discussion about the noise and its effect on quantum coherence and the mathematical models to represent the impact of noise on the physical systems. Furthermore, we will discuss the basic concepts of noise that practically limit quantum computation and quantum communication. We will discuss several mathematical methods to characterize, model, and represent the practical impact of noise. Next, we will discuss how photon loss impacts quantum communication protocols. We will summarize the current physical limitations and challenges facing quantum computation and quantum communication over optical fiber. We will also discuss technology options that can mitigate or eliminate the physical limitations for realizing quantum computation and quantum communication protocol. Later we will consider the methods being developed to mitigate such losses in larger-scale communication systems. We will investigate the current limitations of quantum computing algorithms and the need to develop near-term practical applications that can be successfully performed on noisy qubits. We will also review the challenges associated with implementing algorithms on the relatively noisy, intermediate-scale qubits used in today's technology domain. Finally, we will investigate how to benchmark qubits and quantum gates in the presence of noise. We will discuss several methods to benchmark quantum states and quantum gates and finally implement benchmarking of qubits in a real physical quantum computer on the IBM Q Experience.

1 Introduction

We will manifest quantum mechanical effects that enable quantum computers to process information efficiently, [1–14] facing the practical challenges in implementing quantum algorithms in quantum communication. We will look at noise, its impact on quantum coherence, and how it impacts gate operations. We will also look at how we can mitigate certain types of noise to retain some of that coherence. We begin by discussing the ubiquity and challenges of noise and its impact on quantum information. We will discuss how to characterize and quantify noise processes and how to represent noisy qubits using the density matrix formalism [15, 16]. We then study the difference between classical and quantum noise, and we will visualize the resulting qubit dephasing and energy decay on the Bloch sphere. Then, We will look at practical algorithms being implemented at a small scale, and discuss the challenges associated with running those algorithms in the presence of noise [17, 18]. We will discuss the practical realities of implementing

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the quantum algorithms and quantum cryptography [19], using the smaller error-prone machines we have today. Next, we will look at the practical aspects of quantum communication, including photon loss and its impact on long-distance quantum communication. We turn to the practical issues and challenges of implementing quantum communication schemes. We start by revisiting quantum entanglement [20], the generation and detection of Bell states, and the challenges associated with implementing Bell's inequality experiments [21, 22]. We can use entanglement to build a quantum version of an optical repeater to extend the communication distance [23]. We then will discuss the practical issues associated with distributing such entanglement in the presence of photon loss in optical fibers [23, 24]. It motivates the need for quantum repeaters. We will study several challenges associated with quantum key distribution, from having bright photon sources to high fidelity, fast photon detectors, all of which enable high key generation rates. Next, we will transition to the challenges and opportunities of contemporary quantum computing [25, 26]. That is, what algorithms can implement now or in the near future, given the noisy short-depth circuits we have available today. We will discuss at contemporary demonstrations of noisy intermediate-scale quantum algorithms, the so-called NISQ algorithms [27, 28], targeting machine learning, support vector machines [29], and variational quantum eigensolvers [30–33], as well as the HHL algorithm for linear systems [34]. Another hybrid quantum-classical algorithm is Variational Quantum Fidelity Estimation [35], Variational Quantum Factoring (VQF) algorithm [36]. Finally, we will investigate how to benchmark qubits and benchmark quantum gates in the presence of noise. We will discuss several techniques used to quantify the quality of realistic quantum machines. We study state and process tomography techniques [37] and how they are applied in practice to determine the fidelity of qubit states and quantum operations. In the end, we will characterize noise in benchmark qubits on the IBM quantum experience [38, 39] and implement quantum state tomography [40] using the qubits on the IBM quantum experience [38].

2 Density Matrices Introduction

The definitions of the Dirac notation used in this discussion [41–46]. The Hadamard transform (or Hadamard gate) is an operation that maps state

$$|0\rangle \rightarrow \frac{|0\rangle+|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \text{ and } |1\rangle \rightarrow \frac{|0\rangle-|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$$

In this text, we will find the basics on Dirac notation and matrix representation of quantum states and operators.

Single-qubit system:

The computational basis for a single-qubit is expanded by the eigenvectors of the Pauli matrix Z-gate or σ_Z ,

$$Z = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

This eigenvectors are written in Dirac notation as $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$, and in matrix form as

$$|0\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad |1\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

In Dirac notation, their conjugate transpose are $\langle 0|$ and $\langle 1|$, and in matrix form

$$\langle 0| = (1 \ 0), \quad \langle 1| = (0 \ 1). \quad (3)$$

The computational basis is defined as orthonormal, since its elements are perpendicular and have norm one,

$$\begin{aligned}\langle 1 | 0 \rangle &= (0 \ 1) \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = 0, \\ \langle 0 | 1 \rangle &= (1 \ 0) \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = 0,\end{aligned}\tag{4}$$

and

$$\sqrt{\langle 0 | 0 \rangle} = 1, \sqrt{\langle 1 | 1 \rangle} = 1.\tag{5}$$

While the single-qubit identity matrix is given by

$$I = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}\tag{6}$$

the projectors of $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ are

$$\Pi_0 = |0\rangle \langle 0| = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}\tag{7}$$

and

$$\Pi_1 = |1\rangle \langle 1| = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}\tag{8}$$

An arbitrary single-qubit state, $|\psi\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle$, can be written in matrix form as

$$|\psi\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{pmatrix}\tag{9}$$

and its norm can be computed by finding $||\psi\rangle| = \sqrt{\langle\psi|\psi\rangle}$ or

$$||\psi\rangle| = \sqrt{(\alpha^* \ \beta^*) \begin{pmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{pmatrix}} = \sqrt{|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2},\tag{10}$$

where α^* and β^* are the complex conjugate of α and β .

The projector of any pure state $|\psi\rangle$ can be written as

$$|\psi\rangle \langle\psi| = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{pmatrix} (\alpha^* \ \beta^*) = \begin{pmatrix} |\alpha|^2 & \alpha\beta^* \\ \beta\alpha^* & |\beta|^2 \end{pmatrix}\tag{11}$$

The tensor product between two single-qubit states, $|\psi\rangle$ and $|\phi\rangle$, can be computed in matrix form as

$$|\psi\rangle \otimes |\phi\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} \gamma \\ \delta \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha \begin{pmatrix} \gamma \\ \delta \end{pmatrix} \\ \beta \begin{pmatrix} \gamma \\ \delta \end{pmatrix} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha\gamma \\ \alpha\delta \\ \beta\gamma \\ \beta\delta \end{pmatrix}\tag{12}$$

Two-qubit system:

The computational basis is spanned by

$$|0\rangle|0\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, |0\rangle|1\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, |1\rangle|0\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, |1\rangle|1\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (13)$$

which comes from calculating the tensor product between $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$, i.e

$$|0\rangle|0\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \\ 0 \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (14)$$

For simplicity, most people usually write $|00\rangle$ instead of $|0\rangle|0\rangle$, and the same for the other elements of the basis.

$$|01\rangle \equiv |0\rangle|1\rangle, |10\rangle \equiv |1\rangle|0\rangle, |11\rangle \equiv |1\rangle|1\rangle. \quad (15)$$

To keep track of which qubit the state belongs, we can use the subscripts in the labels of the state, such as $|0_A\rangle$ to indicate that this is the state $|0\rangle$ for qubit A.

The two-qubit identity matrix is given by

$$I = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (16)$$

and the projectors of the computational basis by

$$\Pi_{00} = |00\rangle\langle 00|, \Pi_{01} = |01\rangle\langle 01|, \Pi_{10} = |10\rangle\langle 10|, \quad (17)$$

and $\Pi_{11} = |11\rangle\langle 11|$.

An arbitrary two-qubit state with qubit A and B,

$$|\psi_{AB}\rangle = \alpha|0_A0_B\rangle + \beta|0_A1_B\rangle + \gamma|1_A0_B\rangle + \delta|1_A1_B\rangle, \quad (18)$$

can be written in matrix form as

$$|\psi_{AB}\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \\ \gamma \\ \delta \end{pmatrix} \quad (19)$$

and its norm can be computed by finding $\|\psi_{AB}\| = \sqrt{\langle\psi_{AB}|\psi_{AB}\rangle}$ or

$$\|\psi_{AB}\| = \sqrt{\begin{pmatrix} \alpha^* & \beta^* & \gamma^* & \delta^* \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \\ \gamma \\ \delta \end{pmatrix}} = \sqrt{|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 + |\gamma|^2 + |\delta|^2}, \quad (20)$$

where $\alpha^*, \beta^*, \gamma^*, \delta^*$ are the complex conjugate of $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta$.

The projector of the two-qubit state $|\psi_{AB}\rangle$ can be written as

$$|\psi_{AB}\rangle\langle\psi_{AB}| = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \\ \gamma \\ \delta \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha^* & \beta^* & \gamma^* & \delta^* \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} |\alpha|^2 & \alpha\beta^* & \alpha\gamma^* & \alpha\delta^* \\ \beta\alpha^* & |\beta|^2 & \beta\gamma^* & \beta\delta^* \\ \gamma\alpha^* & \gamma\beta^* & |\gamma|^2 & \gamma\delta^* \\ \delta\alpha^* & \delta\beta^* & \delta\gamma^* & |\delta|^2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (21)$$

Further tensor product examples

The tensor product between an operator A and the identity I is

$$A \otimes I = \begin{pmatrix} a_A & c_A \\ b_A & d_A \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_A \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & c_A \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \\ b_A \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & d_A \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \end{pmatrix} \quad (22)$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} a_A & 0 & c_A & 0 \\ 0 & a_A & 0 & c_A \\ b_A & 0 & d_A & 0 \\ 0 & b_A & 0 & d_A \end{pmatrix} \quad (23)$$

and

$$I \otimes A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} a_A & c_A \\ b_A & d_A \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \begin{pmatrix} a_A & c_A \\ b_A & d_A \end{pmatrix} & 0 \begin{pmatrix} a_A & c_A \\ b_A & d_A \end{pmatrix} \\ 0 \begin{pmatrix} a_A & c_A \\ b_A & d_A \end{pmatrix} & 1 \begin{pmatrix} a_A & c_A \\ b_A & d_A \end{pmatrix} \end{pmatrix} \quad (24)$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} a_A & c_A & 0 & 0 \\ b_A & d_A & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & a_A & c_A \\ 0 & 0 & b_A & d_A \end{pmatrix} \quad (25)$$

Given two 2 by 2 matrices, A and B,

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_A & c_A \\ b_A & d_A \end{pmatrix}, B = \begin{pmatrix} a_B & c_B \\ b_B & d_B \end{pmatrix}, \quad (26)$$

The tensor product between them is given by

$$A \otimes B = \begin{pmatrix} a_A & c_A \\ b_A & d_A \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} a_B & c_B \\ b_B & d_B \end{pmatrix} \quad (27)$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} a_A \begin{pmatrix} a_B & c_B \\ b_B & d_B \end{pmatrix} & c_A \begin{pmatrix} a_B & c_B \\ b_B & d_B \end{pmatrix} \\ b_A \begin{pmatrix} a_B & c_B \\ b_B & d_B \end{pmatrix} & d_A \begin{pmatrix} a_B & c_B \\ b_B & d_B \end{pmatrix} \end{pmatrix} \quad (28)$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} a_A a_B & a_A c_B & c_A a_B & c_A c_B \\ a_A b_B & a_A d_B & c_A b_B & c_A d_B \\ b_A a_B & b_A c_B & d_A a_B & d_A c_B \\ b_A b_B & b_A d_B & d_A b_B & d_A d_B \end{pmatrix} \quad (29)$$

We have described quantum mechanics using four postulates. However, for quantum error correction [47, 48], we need more. We need classical statistics. Consider this question with probability $1/2$, and we were given either ψ or ϕ . How do we describe this state? It is not a single quantum state, but rather a statistical combination of two possible states with equal probability. We may recall that in quantum mechanics, this is described by a density matrix [16]. Here, it is the sum of the two outer product vectors of the quantum state. we call this ρ . To further appreciate the need for density matrices in describing stochastic combinations of quantum states, consider the following scenario, we have a two-part state ψ_{AB} . This state may draw as this quantum circuit, which originates from a single place. The two-qubit state will be this particular position and have parts a and b . A will be the first label, and B will be the second label in each of the kets. Is the question supposing B measures B 's part of the state? What describes A 's part of this bipartite quantum state? This state will be a statistical mixture, because what A obtains differs, depending on what B 's measurement result. If B measures a 0 , then A has a 0 . If B measures a 1 , A has a 1 . each one of these happens with a different amplitude. So, we get one or the other of these two states with the two different amplitudes. Let us call this statistical mixture, Mixture 1. now, imagine another separate scenario. In this scenario, B measures but on a different basis, rather than in this computational 0 and 1 basis, as shown above. We have the same bipartite state as an input to this quantum circuit. B before a measurement, let us say, performs a Hadamard transform. The question again is, what is A 's state? A will see something that we may interpret as being different, depending on what B 's measurement result is. The state before B 's measurement is written here. It is a superposition where the second ket has had a Hadamard operation applied to it. Therefore, we can read off from this what A state is going to be. A will see when B measures a 0 , a superposition of $1/\sqrt{4}$, 0 , and $1/\sqrt{4}$, 1 . If B measures a 1 instead, A state will be different with a minus sign instead of a plus sign. Now, this is another statistical mixture. The mixture is of these two states, one with a plus, and one with a minus. They are superpositions in contrast to Mixture 1. Let us call this Mixture 2. certainly, and it looks very different from Mixture 1. The question is, how are these two statistical mixtures different? Or might they be the same mixture in some sense? To answer this question, we will need to turn to the definition of a density matrix. For these statistical mixtures, we have written here using this circle-plus as an or sign. The density matrix is defined as the sum over the outer product of each of the elements in this statistical mixture as given here. We call ρ the density matrix. Let us explore some sample density matrices. Recall that the state 0 is a two-component vector, $1, 0$, and the state 1 is $0, 1$. The density matrices corresponding to these are given by the outer products. So, 0 is $1, 0, 0, 0$. And 1 is $0, 0, 0, 1$. The cross term, $0, 1$, has the 1 in the upper right-hand corner. Furthermore, this is easy to understand by labeling the rows and columns appropriately with 0 on the left and the top. We may also explicitly multiply the column and row vector to obtain this matrix form. Using these matrices, we now write off the density matrices, which correspond to the mixtures that we have studied. The first statistical mixture let us call it row 1, turns out to be the density matrix given by the sum $3/4$ of 1 and $1/4$ of 1 gives we $1/4$ times 3001 . The second statistical mixture is where we need the cross-terms because the states are superpositions. These cross-terms give rise to off-diagonal elements in the density matrix, summing as before, we find, though, something very interesting. The result is the same density matrix as for Mixture 1. we conclude from this that the two are the same state. Note: The section above currently contains an error in the treatment of mixture 2. Firstly, the normalization factor $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$ is missing and, secondly, the final calculation of the density matrix should read

$$\rho_2 = \frac{1}{8} \begin{bmatrix} 3 & \sqrt{3} \\ \sqrt{3} & 1 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{1}{8} \begin{bmatrix} 3 & -\sqrt{3} \\ -\sqrt{3} & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{8} \begin{bmatrix} 6 & 0 \\ 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{4} \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (30)$$

3 Density Matrices Properties

More about this can be understood by returning to the formalism of density matrices. Let us begin by defining a density matrix [15]. A density matrix is a matrix ρ , which has two particular properties. First, the trace of ρ must equal 1. Second, the density matrix ρ must be positive. In other words, for all possible states that one might choose, the expectation value of ρ must be real and greater than or equal to 0. How do we construct a density matrix from states? First, let us make this claim, that a density matrix may be constructed from a probabilistic combination of pure states. P here is a probability. Ψ is stated, which for now let us take to be orthogonal. We may prove that this statistical combination is a density matrix by checking the two constraints. First, we know that its trace is equal to 1 since p 's are probabilities. Moreover, second, it is clear that the matrix is positive. So, we can construct density matrices this way. In the reverse direction, given a density matrix, how can we interpret it? We claim that any density matrix ρ can be expressed as a stochastic combination of pure states. So, that is exactly in the form we have just seen using a stochastic combination of pure states. Let us prove this claim as follows. A density matrix is positive, and thus it has a spectral decomposition into eigenvalues and eigenvectors. Furthermore, this spectral decomposition gives us exactly what we want. We may see this straightforwardly by writing out the spectral decomposition with $\lambda_{sub k}$ being the eigenvalue for state k . Note that the trace is 1, and thus the eigenvalues must sum to 1, meaning they are a probability distribution. They are also real-valued. ρ is positive by construction. This decomposition, known as an unraveling, allows us to consider some useful definitions. ρ is known as being pure when its decomposition results in a single pure state alone. Otherwise, ρ is known as being a mixed state, meaning that it is a stochastic combination of multiple pure states. Given these two constructions, let us consider a quick question. How about a stochastic combination of density matrices? Given p is as probabilities and ρ_s as density matrices, is this combination a legal density matrix? It is a simple thing to work out. The answer is, yes. So, try it ourselves and see if we can prove this to be true. The concept of unraveling a density matrix into a stochastic combination of pure states was considered by Von Neumann and is very interesting. It is an important lemma about unravelings. Let ρ be unraveled as a stochastic combination with probabilities p and states ψ . It turns out that this unraveling is not unique in general for mixed states. For a mixed state, the density matrix may also be unraveled with probabilities p and states ϕ under the following condition. That is, that the square root in the sense of this decomposition. The square root of p and state ψ is related by a unitary transformation to the other decomposition with square root q and states ϕ . The physical origin of this infinity of possibilities of unravelings may be interpreted as arising from the fact that it does not matter which basis b measures in the original scenario. We started the discussion today. Let us now turn to another definition. We will say that purification of a density matrix, ρ_s of a , is a state size of a b , a pure state, such that ρ_s of a is obtained by taking the partial trace over a b of the density matrix given by the pure state. This partial trace operation removes the degrees of freedom associated with b and can be viewed in terms of the quantum circuit that we started today. Namely, that we have a bipartite system, and the b part of the system is measured, leaving ρ of a as the final state. This concept of having infinite unravelings and the interpretation of density matrices in purified forms will be key ideas in understanding the intuition behind quantum error correction [49].

A known and well-defined quantum state that can be written as a single state $|\phi\rangle$ is referred to as a pure state. In contrast, the system states that it can only be expressed as statistical mixtures of several pure states called mixed states. A general approach that accommodates both pure and mixed states uses density operators and matrix form density matrices ρ .

A pure state $|\phi\rangle$ is mathematically represented using a single state vector, for example [50],

$$|\phi\rangle = |0\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (31)$$

Note, a coherent superposition of pure states, such as $\alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle$, is also a pure state.

The density matrix representation of a pure state is the outer product of the pure state with itself, for example:

$$\rho = |\phi\rangle\langle\phi| = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (32)$$

By extension, a mixed state is a statistical mixture of pure states $|\phi_i\rangle\langle\phi_i|$ with individual weights or probabilities $0 \leq p_i \leq 1$, and it is expressed as sum over all possible states

$$\rho = \sum_i p_i |\phi_i\rangle\langle\phi_i|. \quad (33)$$

Note that some states in the sum may have $p_i = 0$.

A density matrix that describes pure and mixed states has the following properties:

$$Tr(\rho) = \sum_i \rho_{ii} = 1 \quad \text{normalization} \quad (34)$$

$$\langle\psi|\rho|\psi\rangle = \sum_i p_i |\langle\psi|\phi_i\rangle|^2 \geq 0 \quad \text{positivity} \quad (35)$$

First, a density matrix is normalized to unity. In general, the trace of a matrix equals the sum of its eigenvalues. In the case of a density matrix, the basis of the density matrix spans a complete set of states, and the diagonal elements represent the probabilities of the system being in these various basis states. Therefore, the trace of the density matrix equals one.

Second, the expectation value that a system is found in state $|\psi\rangle$ is calculated using the density matrix, as shown above. The result is manifestly positive because the density matrix itself is expanded into a basis of projectors with manifestly positive weighting coefficients. This property is called positivity.

The density matrix ρ_p of a pure state is a projection matrix a matrix that projects the system onto the basis state (or states) that comprise the pure state. For a pure state, a second projection leaves the result unchanged, and hence $Tr(\rho_p) = Tr(\rho_p^2) = 1$ for a pure state. In contrast, a mixed state represented by a density matrix ρ_m is not a projection matrix, and consequently $Tr(\rho_m^2) < 1$. This follows, because the weightings $0 < p_i < 1$ of the mixed state become smaller when squared, $p_i^2 < p_i$. In the case of the pure state discussed before, only one particular p_i equals one, and so it remains one when squared.

$$\text{pure state: } Tr(\rho_p^2) = Tr(|\phi\rangle\langle\phi|\langle\phi|\langle\phi|) = Tr(|\phi\rangle\langle\phi|) = Tr(\rho_p) = 1 \quad (36)$$

$$\text{mixed state: } Tr(\rho_m^2) = Tr\left(\sum_{i,j} p_i p_j |\phi_i\rangle\langle\phi_i|\langle\phi_j|\langle\phi_j|\right) = \sum_i p_i^2 < 1 \quad (37)$$

In conclusion, the trace of a density matrix is required to be unity, whether a pure state or a mixed state. However, the trace of the density matrix squared depends on the degree of purity, and it is thus used to assess the purity of an arbitrary system state.

A common visualization of density matrices is illustrated in the following figure for a pure state, a mixture of pure states, and Bell-state entanglement of pure states $|\Phi^-\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle|0\rangle - |1\rangle|1\rangle)$.

Figure 1: DVS

Unitary operations alter quantum states and, thus, they also modify density matrices [51]. For example, a pure state $|\phi\rangle$ altered by a unitary operator U is transformed into $U|\phi\rangle = |\tilde{\phi}\rangle$. The density matrix is modified according to: $\tilde{\rho} = |\tilde{\phi}\rangle\langle\tilde{\phi}| = U|\phi\rangle\langle\phi|U^\dagger = U\rho U^\dagger$. This transformation generalizes for any density matrix: U alters ρ according to $U\rho U^\dagger$.

1. A pure state $|\psi\rangle$ can be written as a density matrix $\rho = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$.

Solution:

Any pure state, such as

$$|\psi\rangle_{AB} = \alpha|0\rangle_A|0\rangle_B + \beta|1\rangle_A|1\rangle_B = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \beta \end{pmatrix},$$

can be written as a density matrix ρ ,

$$\begin{aligned} \rho &= |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|, \\ &= (\alpha|0\rangle_A|0\rangle_B + \beta|1\rangle_A|1\rangle_B)(\alpha^*\langle 0|_A\langle 0|_B + \beta^*\langle 1|_A\langle 1|_B), \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \alpha \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \beta \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha^* & 0 & 0 & \beta^* \end{pmatrix}, \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} |\alpha|^2 & 0 & 0 & \alpha\beta^* \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \beta\alpha^* & 0 & 0 & |\beta|^2 \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned}$$

The diagonal elements of a density matrix are the probabilities associated with each projector on to the elements' corresponding basis states. In the previous example, the first diagonal element, $|\alpha|^2$, is the probability associated with the projector $|0\rangle_A|0\rangle_B\langle 0|_A\langle 0|_B$. Since the diagonal

elements are measurement probabilities across a complete basis set, they must sum to unity, $|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 = 1$. Density matrices not only can be constructed as probabilistic combinations of pure states, they can also be constructed as combinations of mixed states.

4 Density Matrices

Consider the bipartite two-qubit state discussed in the first section

$$|\psi_{AB}\rangle = \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}|0_A\rangle|0_B\rangle + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}}|1_A\rangle|1_B\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}} \end{pmatrix} \quad (38)$$

where A and B are the labels assigned to each qubit. State $|0_A\rangle$ corresponds to the $|0\rangle$ state for qubit A, and $|0_B\rangle$ corresponds to the $|0\rangle$ state for qubit B.

In the first part of this exercise, we will work through the steps to find the probability of projecting qubit B on to state $|0_B\rangle$, and then determine the resulting density matrix for qubit A following this specific projection. In the second part of this exercise, we will apply the same steps to find the probability of projecting qubit B on to state $|1_B\rangle$, and then find the resulting density matrix for qubit A. In the last part of this exercise, we will use the above results to write the density matrix for qubit A.

Section I

The conjugate transpose of the two-qubit state $|\psi_{AB}\rangle$ is

$$\langle\psi_{AB}| = \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}\langle 0_A|\langle 0_B| + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}}\langle 1_A|\langle 1_B|, \quad (39)$$

or, alternatively in matrix form,

$$\langle\psi_{AB}| = \left(\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}} \right) \quad (40)$$

If qubit B is projected on to state $|0_B\rangle$, then the two-qubit state after the measurement becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(I_A \otimes \Pi_0)|\psi_{AB}\rangle}{\sqrt{N}} &= \frac{(I_A \otimes |0_B\rangle\langle 0_B|)}{\sqrt{N}} \left(\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}|0_A\rangle|0_B\rangle + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}}|1_A\rangle|1_B\rangle \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}}\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}(I_A \otimes |0_B\rangle\langle 0_B|)|0_A\rangle|0_B\rangle \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}}\sqrt{\frac{1}{4}}(I_A \otimes |0_B\rangle\langle 0_B|)|1_A\rangle|1_B\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

where I is the identity operator, Π_0 is the single-qubit projector $|0\rangle\langle 0|$, and N is a normalization constant. We can simplify equation (41) by replacing with the values of the inner products

$\langle 0_B | 0_B \rangle = 1$, $\langle 0_B | 1_B \rangle = 0$, and noting that the identify operator will leave a state unchanged,

$$\frac{(I_A \otimes \Pi_0) |\psi_{AB}\rangle}{\sqrt{N}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} |0_A\rangle |0_B\rangle \quad (42)$$

From equation (42) we determine that the normalization constant is $N = \frac{3}{4}$, such that the norm of $(I_A \otimes \Pi_0) |\psi_{AB}\rangle / \sqrt{N}$ is equal to one,

$$\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} \langle 0_A | \langle 0_B | \right) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} |0_A\rangle |0_B\rangle \right) = 1. \quad (43)$$

The state of qubit A after the measurement is

$$|\psi_{A,0}\rangle = \sqrt{\frac{4}{3}} \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} |0_A\rangle = |0_A\rangle \quad (44)$$

The probability of projecting qubit B on to state $|0_B\rangle$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} p_{B,0} &= \langle \psi_{AB} | (I_A \otimes \Pi_0) | \psi_{AB} \rangle \\ &= \langle \psi_{AB} | (I_A \otimes |0_B\rangle \langle 0_B|) | \psi_{AB} \rangle \\ &= \langle \psi_{AB} | \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} |0_A\rangle |0_B\rangle \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} \left[\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} \langle 0_A | \langle 0_B | + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}} \langle 1_A | \langle 1_B | \right] |0_A\rangle |0_B\rangle \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} \left[\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} \langle 0_A | 0_A \rangle \langle 0_B | 0_B \rangle + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}} \langle 1_A | 0_A \rangle \langle 1_B | 0_B \rangle \right] \\ &= \frac{3}{4} \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

2. Writing a Density Matrix I; if qubit B is projected to state $|1_B\rangle$, what is the state of qubit A after the measurement?

- $|\psi_{A,1}\rangle = 0 |0_A\rangle + 1 |1_A\rangle$
- What is the probability of projecting qubit B to state $|1_B\rangle$?
- $p_{B,1} = 0.25$

Solution:

If qubit B is projected to state $|1_B\rangle$, then the two-qubit state in Dirac notation becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(I_A \otimes \Pi_1) |\psi_{AB}\rangle}{\sqrt{N}} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \left((I_A \otimes |1_B\rangle \langle 1_B|) \left(\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} |0_A\rangle |0_B\rangle + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}} |1_A\rangle |1_B\rangle \right) \right), = \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}} |1_A\rangle |1_B\rangle, \end{aligned}$$

From here, we notice that the normalization constant is equal to $N = 1/4$, such that the state of qubit A after the measurement is

$$|\psi_{A,1}\rangle = \sqrt{\frac{4}{1}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}} |1_A\rangle, = |1_A\rangle.$$

The probability of projecting qubit B to state $|1_B\rangle$ is given by

$$p_{B,1} = \langle \psi_{AB} | (I_A \otimes \Pi_1) | \psi_{AB} \rangle, = \langle \psi_{AB} | \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}} |1_A\rangle |1_B\rangle, = \frac{1}{4}.$$

3. Writing a Density Matrix II; If there is no information regarding on to which state qubit B was projected, then the state of qubit A has to be described by a density matrix ρ_A given by: the probability of projecting qubit B on to $|0_B\rangle$ times the projector for the qubit-A state after the measurement, $|\psi_{A,0}\rangle \langle \psi_{A,0}|$; plus the probability of projecting qubit B on to $|1_B\rangle$ times the projector for the qubit-A state after the measurement, $|\psi_{A,1}\rangle \langle \psi_{A,1}|$.

- Write the density matrix ρ_A using Dirac notation

$$\rho_A = 0.75 |\psi_{A,0}\rangle \langle \psi_{A,0}| + 0.25 |\psi_{A,1}\rangle \langle \psi_{A,1}|$$

- Write the density matrix ρ_A using matrices

$$\rho_A = 0.75 \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} + 0.25 \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

5 Dephasing Channel on the Bloch Sphere

In order to be useful machines, quantum computers like classical computers must be built from robust elements. Gate fidelity is one metric that quantifies the robustness of a qubit. Intuitively, it is related to the number of gates one can apply to the qubit, on average, before an error occurs, and the qubit state is lost. As we in section one, there are two fundamental ways in which a qubit loses quantum information. The first is energy exchange with the environment related to the coherence time, t_1 . The second is dephasing, a loss of coherence in a superposition state. The coherence time t_2 is then related to both the dephasing and energy exchange processes. In this section, we will look at a method to treat qubit errors on the Bloch sphere using probabilistic error channels based on qubit gates. While this simple model is not entirely general, it does provide a simple means to visualize concepts like depolarization and dephasing as represented by a density matrix. Thus, with that introduction, let us discuss about error channels, depolarization, dephasing, and the Bloch sphere. If we want to discuss quantum channels in the most generality [52], there are completely positive trace-preserving maps, and they are complicated, even to write down the definition of. Well, maybe not to write down the definition, but intuitively, they are quite difficult to understand. Today, we will tell we the simplest kind of quantum channel [53], which is we mean, we can do everything we want to in this section with that kind of channel. So, what is a quantum channel? So, what we are going to do is we are going to expressive a quantum channel as a mixture of simple channels. So, that is not always true. Let us do the easiest one first, what we will call the dephasing channel. So, let us say with probability one minus p, we do nothing. Probability, p, apply σ_z . So, let us put a quantum state into the depolarizing channel. So, suppose we put in α zero plus β one. we get out a mixture. we get out one minus p, probability, α zero plus β one, and with p probability, we get out α zero minus β one. from the last section, we know this can be expressed as a density matrix. So, the density matrix is one minus p, α zero plus β one, α zero plus β one, plus p. Same thing with minus signs. That is one minus p, α squared. Let us assume α and β are real, because $\alpha \beta$, $\alpha \beta$, β squared because

otherwise, we get a whole bunch of complex conjugates, which we do not want to mess up. Plus, now down here, we get α zero minus β one. That trick gives us α squared, minus $\alpha\beta$, minus $\alpha\beta$, β squared is equal to well, one minus $p\alpha$ squared plus α squared. $p\alpha$ squared is just α squared. the same thing for β squared. α squared, one minus $2p$, $\alpha\beta$, one minus $2p$ $\alpha\beta$, β squared. the density matrix we put in was α squared, $\alpha\beta$, $\alpha\beta$, β squared. So, the depolarizing channel we can see from this example. Moreover, this example is, well, this is as general as possible, really, except we also should check that it works with α and β complex. So, what the depolarizing channel does is it multiplies the off-diagonal elements of the density matrix. Sorry, the dephasing channel. The dephasing channel multiplies the off-diagonal elements of the density matrix by some constant. Next, we want to tell us what happens to the dephasing channel when we look at it in the Bloch sphere. Let us go back and draw the Bloch sphere. So, the Bloch sphere looked like zero one, plus-minus. When we multiply the off-diagonal elements by q , we get one, one, one, one. That is one half goes to one half, one, one minus q , one minus q , one. Are we are just moving the Bloch sphere into the middle, because we are taking this. We are multiplying it by one minus q , and we are adding q amount of diagonal, or q amount of the identity. So, that goes here. Furthermore, in general, this is going to go to an ellipsoid. It is still zero, this is still one, and this is one, one minus q , one minus q , one. So, we shrink the Bloch sphere into an ellipsoid with the vertical axis stays the same, and everything else shrinks by the same factor.

6 Depolarizing Channel on the Bloch Sphere

There is another channel we would like to discuss the depolarizing channel. ρ goes to $1 - p$ ρ plus $p/3$ $\sigma_x \rho \sigma_x$ plus $p/3$ $\sigma_y \rho \sigma_y$ plus $p/3$ $\sigma_z \rho \sigma_z$. So, with $1 - p$, we do nothing. Probability of the $p/3$ we will apply each of the three Pauli matrices. So, is there an easier formula for this? Yes, ρ goes to, we guess, $1 - 4/3 p$ ρ plus identity. the reason for this is for any density matrix, ρ plus $\sigma_x \rho \sigma_x$ plus $\sigma_y \rho \sigma_y$ plus $\sigma_z \rho \sigma_z$ equals. So, this is completely unnormalized. So, we want this to be $we/2$. we want this to be $1/4$. probability $1/4$, we apply σ_x . $1/4$, we apply σ_y . $1/4$ we apply σ_z . we get $we/2$. Proof that is tau. $\sigma_x \tau \sigma_x$ equals $\sigma_y \tau$. σ_y equals $\sigma_z \tau$. σ_z equals tau. Why is that? If we multiply this by σ_y in front and σ_y behind, this gets taken to this σ_y . This gets taken to ρ . $\sigma_x \sigma \rho \sigma_x$ gets taken to σ_z , $\rho \sigma_z$. this gets taken to this. So, it is invariant. So, this is true of tau. Now the only density matrix tau, which has this property, is $we/2$. Let us say tau equals $a b c d$. $\sigma_x \tau \sigma_x$ equals $b d a c$. So, a has to be equal to b . $\sigma_z \tau \sigma_z$ equals $a - z$ minus $d b$. So, c has to be 0, and d has to be 0. So, that means tau has to be the identity. Alternatively, the identity over 2, because we know it is the trace, is 1 because it is the density matrix. So, what does the depolarizing channel look like in the Bloch picture? Furthermore, everything moves to the center at the same rate. So, it goes to that. We probably should draw the axes, so; we know it is not misplaced. So, these are the two channels we will be discussing. There are many, many other ways to get the depolarizing channel. We should also say that the binary symmetric channel corresponds to the depolarizing channel because the depolarizing channel, there is no preferred basis. The binary symmetric channel, remember, took the 0 to 1 with probability p and vice versa. There is no preferred input. So, we take a density matrix ρ , and with probability $1/4$, we do nothing. We apply the identity. Probability $1/4$ we apply σ_x . Probability $1/4$ we apply σ_y . Probability $1/4$ we apply σ_z . it is now easy to see that $\sigma_x \tau \sigma_x$ is equal to tau because what happens when we apply σ_x to tau? Well, ρ goes to $\sigma_x \rho \sigma_x$. And $\sigma_x \rho \sigma_x$ goes to ρ . Since $\sigma_x \sigma_y$ is equal to, we σ_z , $\sigma_y \rho \sigma_y$ goes to $\sigma_z \rho \sigma_z$ and vice versa. we should put a conjugate here because σ_y is not self-adjoint, is not self-adjoint. So, we really should put all of these conjugates on all

of these and conjugate here and a conjugate here.

The robustness of quantum systems is limited by noise. The effect of noise on a system of qubits can be described within the density matrix formalism by using a mapping $\rho \rightarrow \mathcal{E}(\rho)$. The different noise mechanisms and the means by which they affect the system are called noise channels. In this text unit, we will look at three simple models for noise channels: depolarization, amplitude damping, and dephasing.

Consider a quantum system that is initialized in a well-defined pure state. Over time, environment noise “mixes” the quantum system with a large ensemble of unknown quantum systems in the environment. The initialized quantum system loses its “purity,” and this results in a probabilistic manifestation of errors.

In the case of the depolarizing channel, we assume that a quantum system interacting with its environment will have an error with probability p . We model these errors through the use of quantum gates, an X-gate, a Y-gate, and a Z-gate, and we assume that each is equally likely with probability $p/3$. In this sense, the depolarization channel models errors as bit flips and phase flip.

The mapping of a density matrix assuming a depolarizing channel is:

$$\rho \rightarrow \mathcal{E}(\rho) = (1 - p)\rho + \frac{p}{3}(X\rho X + Z\rho Z + Y\rho Y), \quad (46)$$

Where the density matrix remains unaffected with probability $(1-p)$, it has an error with probability p . It is modelled as an X-gate, Y-gate, and Z-gate rotation with probability $p/3$ each. The net effect of many such errors is to stochastically depolarize the qubit state to the center of the Bloch sphere, and thus the origin of the name.

$$\mathcal{E}(\rho(\vec{q})) = \frac{1}{2} \left(I + \left(1 - \frac{4}{3}p \right) (q_1 X + q_2 Z + q_3 Y) \right). \quad (47)$$

A second noise model is amplitude damping, which is a model of energy loss from the quantum system to the environment. Amplitude damping channel maps a density matrix ρ according to,

$$\rho \rightarrow \mathcal{E}(\rho) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & \sqrt{1-p} \end{pmatrix} \rho \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & \sqrt{1-p} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \sqrt{p} \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \rho \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ \sqrt{p} & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (48)$$

Where an amplitude damping event occurs with probability p . If $p=0$, the density matrix remains unchanged. With amplitude damping, a qubit represented on the Bloch sphere contracts to a scaled spheroid with a center that moves toward the ground state (north pole).

Lastly, the dephasing channel acts to dephase the qubit through the application of the phase gate Z according to the mapping:

$$\rho \rightarrow \mathcal{E}(\rho) = (1 - p)\rho + p(Z\rho Z) = \begin{pmatrix} \rho_{11} & (1 - 2p)\rho_{12} \\ (1 - 2p)\rho_{21} & \rho_{22} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (49)$$

The probability of an error is p , and the density matrix remains unchanged with probability $(1-p)$. The phase damping channel transforms the Bloch sphere to a prolate spheroid along the z-axis with scaled x and y axes.

Figure 2: shrinking of the Bloch sphere

The loss in purity represented by the shrinking of the Bloch sphere is detrimental to any computation. In order to reliably trace states and exploit quantum interference with maximal efficiency, pure states are needed, and these are only found on the surface of the sphere. Points inside the sphere correspond to mixed states and are indicative of a loss of quantum coherence.

7 Noise Processes

We looked at how quantum computing algorithms and quantum communication protocols work in an ideal sense in section two. We assume perfect qubits on which to apply our algorithms or perfect control electronics and optics to implement these protocols [54]. In this section, we are now turning our attention to the practical realities of quantum technologies. one of the main challenges to building robust systems is the presence of noise. Noise has an impact on nearly every aspect of quantum information. For example, in quantum communication, it can be manifest as photon loss in a long optical fiber or a measurement error in a photodetector. quantum computing causes qubit decoherence or control errors when implementing a qubit gate, both of which reduce gate fidelity. Indeed, noise is ubiquitous. it is a problem because it causes errors. practically, these errors translate to reduced communication rates, limits on the length or circuit depth of a computation, an increase in the amount of overhead needed to combat those errors, and, in the worst case, even system failure. we will focus here on examples related to quantum computing. However, the concepts are relevant for quantum communication as well. Noise can be categorized into two primary types systematic noise and stochastic noise. Systematic noise arises from a process that ultimately can be traced back to a systematic error. For example, we want to apply an X-gate to a qubit. However, the control field is not tuned properly. So, rather than rotating the qubit 180 degrees, the pulse slightly over-rotates or under-rotates by a fixed amount. Now, in this case, the underlying error is always the same. it is, in this sense, systematic. However, the symptoms we observe in measuring the output of our qubit may look like noise. They are not always the same. It is because we do not always apply the pulse in the same way. It could be applied to a different number of times, or it could be interspersed with different pulses in different ways. Thus, in general, it differs from experiment to experiment. However, such systematic errors can generally be corrected once They are identified

through proper calibration or improved hardware. The second type of noise is stochastic noise. this is the random fluctuation of a parameter that is coupled to our qubit. For example, the thermal noise of a 50-ohm resistor will have voltage, and current fluctuations called Johnson noise. They are proportional to temperature. Alternatively, the oscillator we using to create an X-pulse has amplitude fluctuations due to noise in the internal electronics [55, 56]. In principle, any randomly fluctuating parameter that couples to the qubit can cause decoherence. In the case of superconducting qubits [57, 58], this could be a fluctuating magnetic field through the superconducting qubit loop or trap magnetic field vortices that move around [59]. It could also be fluctuating charges in the substrate or charges we call quasi-particles that tunnel across the Josephson junction [?, 60–62]. It can be the loss of energy due to phonon or photon emission. it could also be noise that comes in and out of our control line. there are many, many others. To see how noise affects qubit operations, let us first examine an example of qubit control in the absence of noise and compare those ideal results to the same experiment in the presence of noise. In this case, we apply a control field resonant with the qubit along the x-axis of the Bloch sphere. we leave this control field on. The Bloch vector then rotates around this field from north pole to south pole and back again and continues to do this. The Bloch vector's projection along the z-axis is plotted on the right, and it oscillates up and down between the north and south poles. It is called a Rabi oscillation. the frequency of this oscillation is proportional to the amplitude of the control field. Now, we notice that this looks like an ideal cosine. It oscillates with full contrast between plus and minus one, and it has a fixed frequency. This is an ideal result because we have assumed that there is no control or environmental noise. remember that when we measure the z-axis, we get either state zero, a plus one on the graph, or state one, a minus one on the graph, and that is it. So, we have two identically prepare, control, and measure the qubit a large number of times at each time step and average these results to generate the cosine experimentally. For example, when the qubit is at the north pole, all measurements will yield a plus one, and the average is obviously plus one. when the qubit is at the south pole, all measurements yield a minus one. Thus, the average there is minus one. Now, on the equator, for example, the qubit is in an equal superposition state. Thus, half of the time, we measure one, and half of the time, we measure minus one. Thus, the average there is zero. The cosine trace represents the average of many, many measurements, and, in fact, so many in this case that we cannot even resolve the statistical sampling error. Now, as an aside, if we had stopped the pulse after the first quarter period of the cosine wave, then the Bloch vector stops on the equator, and this is $\pi/2$ pulse around the x-axis. If we had instead stopped the pulse after half a period, the Bloch vector rotates 180 degrees around the x-axis, and this is an X-gate. so, what happens in the presence of noise? we will assume that we have one specific type of noise, amplitude noise on the control field. since the Rabi frequency is proportional to amplitude, fluctuations in the control field amplitude cause fluctuations in the Rabi frequency. To help visualize what is happening, we will also assume that the noise is quasi-static, which means that the amplitude is fixed for one whole Rabi trace, but fluctuates to a different value according to some probability distribution for each new Rabi trace. Essentially, we are saying that the amplitude changes slowly in time, or equivalently, that this is low-frequency amplitude noise. Again, we simulate multiple nominally identical trials. However, due to the noise, different trials have different Rabi frequencies. The Bloch vector begins to diffuse. Some instances are rotating faster, and others are rotating slower. on the right, individual instances are shown in gray while the average value is green. The net result is that the Rabi oscillations decay in time due to the frequency fluctuations caused by the amplitude noise of the control field. The actual form of the decay function turns out to be Gaussian because we assumed low-frequency quasi-static noise. we can see how this type of noise then causes small errors in the $\pi/2$ in π pulse gates. Although this example considered only one type of noise, control field amplitude fluctuations, it gives an intuitive picture of how noise can

cause gate errors in general. In the next section, we will examine how noise is measured and characterized through a two-time correlation function and a corresponding noise power spectral density.

8 Noise Characterization and the Noise Power Spectral Density

In the last section, we saw an example of how a specific type of noise amplitude noise on a control field can cause Rabi oscillations to decay due to the resulting fluctuation of the Rabi frequency. However, how do we characterize and quantify these types of noise processes in a real physical system? Moreover, how do we relate the temporal behavior of noise to its frequency spectrum? In this section, we will overview the standard approach to characterizing and representing noise processes via the autocorrelation function and the noise power spectral density. To get started, let us consider a system with a noisy parameter, x . As an experimentalist, we set up a detector in our system to measure x and record how it varies in time [63]. Ideally, we would like to calculate the statistics of x from the single time trace. After all, it is a straightforward measurement. We only needed one system to do it. We do not necessarily know the explicit probability density function of the noise processes that underlie the fluctuations in x . So, instead, we just measure them. In the limit, we measure for a long time. We get a reasonable estimate for the statistics of x . As long as it fluctuates the same way tomorrow as it did today, this approach works. On the other hand, we could, in principle, set up an ensemble of n identical systems and record one sample of x from each of them at the same time. Then, we could calculate the ensemble average statistics across all end samples. In the limit of large n , we would, again, be able to obtain the statistics of x . It is notionally how theorists would calculate the properties of a system. They ideally have a model in mind that yields a probability distribution function that describes the fluctuations in x . It also seems reasonable as long as it describes the system accurately at any time. For example, the first-order time average of x is the time integral of x over a duration, T , that we take to be large and then normalized by T to obtain the average value of x . We will denote time averages with a bar over the variable x . In comparison, the first order ensemble average, which we denote with brackets, is defined as a sum over all members of an ensemble, at a particular time, T_1 , and then divided by n to obtain the average value. We generally do not have identical copies of an experiment. Thus, the calculation is performed using a presumed known probability density function, p . P tells us the probability of obtaining any value x at a time, T . The ensemble average follows by integrating, overall, x . The variable x times the probability distribution function, p . Similarly, one can define an autocorrelation function between two points of a measured time trace separated by a time τ . Alternatively, one can find the average ensemble version of this, the covariance, by using a joint probability distribution function, as shown here. Now, ideally, we would like to work with systems where these two approaches give the same results that time averaging is equivalent to ensemble averaging. Such systems are called ergodic ensembles, and their statistics are called ergodic. If the statistics calculated from a time trace are independent of time, then the noise is statistically stationary. For example, the autocorrelation function of a statistically stationary process would depend only on the time difference τ between the two samples independent of when it is measured. While ergodicity implies stationarity, the opposite is not always true. Now, ergodicity and stationarity, in the strictest sense, must be true to all orders of the statistics. However, for what we will look at next, we only require what is called weak stationarity or wide sense stationarity, which means that the mean value is constant in time. The autocorrelation function depends only on the time difference τ . We will see, if we

know or can measure the autocorrelation function of a wide sense stationary process, we can find the power spectral density using the Wiener-Khinchine theorem. Wiener-Khinchine tells us that the autocorrelation function and the power spectral density are Fourier transform pairs. Let us assume we have a fluctuating parameter λ , for example, magnetic flux. Then if we take the Fourier transform of an autocorrelation function over the time difference, τ , we will obtain the power spectral density in units of λ squared per Hertz. In turn, if we take the inverse Fourier transform of the power spectral density, we will get back the autocorrelation function with units, λ square. S of ω is called the noise power spectral density. we plot S of ω for both positive and negative frequencies. Now, for noise at the qubit frequency, which can exchange energy with the environment, positive frequencies correspond to the qubit emitting energy to the environment. negative frequencies correspond to the qubit absorbing energy from the environment. we will return to this in a moment. First, though, let us look at an example of low-frequency noise, such as $1/f$ noise. In this case, S of ω 's peaked at zero frequency. it decreases with frequency as $1/f$. we have taken the noise to be symmetric about zero frequency. as we may remember for Fourier transform pairs, symmetric infrequency implies that a signal is manifestly real in the time domain. Thus, this represents a real fluctuating signal. we can represent it using a classical variable of λ . Thus, these symmetric power spectra are often called classical noise. Next, we can include thermal noise or a Johnson noise. Johnson noise is proportional to temperature. it is called white noise because it is constant over all frequencies. In electrical systems, Johnson noise is the voltage or current noise present in a resistor at a given temperature, T . This is also an example of classical noise because it is symmetric in frequency. Next, let us consider an example of quantum noise or Nyquist noise, which is not symmetric in frequency. Nyquist noise is proportional to frequency ω . it is only present at positive frequencies. This asymmetry implies that the time domain signal is not manifestly real. this arises from the fact that Nyquist noise must be described using quantum operators. we promote the λ variable to an operator. the operators, λT , do not commute with one another at different times. The computation relation can include imaginary terms. Thus, the power spectrum needs no longer be symmetric. Nyquist noise is responsible for spontaneous emission of energy from a qubit to its environment. That is, if we put the qubit in its excited state, it will relax back to its ground state by emitting a photon at a frequency ω_q . It happens, even if the environments at zero temperature, and is a complete absence of classical noise. Now, a zero-temperature environment cannot drive the qubit from its ground state to its excited state. It has no energy to do this. if the environments at non-zero temperature, then we can have classical Johnson noise, which drives transitions in both directions, $0 \rightarrow 1$ and $1 \rightarrow 0$, because of its symmetric infrequency. However, Nyquist noise is different. It represents an additional spontaneous emission component. Together, these two processes are called Johnson-Nyquist noise. Now, note that generally speaking, only noise at the qubit frequency, at plus or minus ω_q , causes transitions and energy exchange with the environment. These are T_1 processes. In contrast, classical noise that is off-resonance with the qubit contributes to its dephasing. With knowledge of the noise power spectral density, as seen by the qubit, one then understands the frequency content of the various noise sources that cause decoherence.

In this section, we will review the distinction between time averaging and ensemble averaging. We will also review the Wiener-Khinchine theorem, which relates the two-time correlation function to the noise power spectral density.

There were two types of noise discussed in the section: systematic noise and stochastic noise. Systematic noise arises from a systematic source, for example, a fixed offset in driving field amplitude that causes a fixed amount of over-rotation or under-rotation when performing a particular quantum gate. Despite being systematic errors, measurement results may still differ

in the presence of such errors because the experiments may differ. For example, when applying different numbers of gates or interspersing the gates with different assortments of other gates, measurement results may give an appearance of noise. This type of error can generally be corrected with better calibration or hardware improvements.

Here, we will focus on stochastic noise processes. Noise is a random fluctuation of a parameter in space and time. It is characterized statistically, either via temporal averaging or through ensemble averaging. The distinction is related to how averaged quantities are determined:

1. Temporal (spatial) averaging: averaging the time (or spatial) record of a single system
2. Ensemble averaging: averaging over many identical systems at a fixed time (or spatial position)

Time averaging and ensemble averaging

$$\overline{x^{(i)}(t)} = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_{-T/2}^{T/2} x^{(i)}(t) dt \quad (50)$$

$$\overline{[x^{(i)}(t)]^2} = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_{-T/2}^{T/2} [x^{(i)}(t)]^2 dt \quad (51)$$

$$\overline{x^{(i)}(t)x^{(i)}(t+\tau)} = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_{-T/2}^{T/2} x^{(i)}(t)x^{(i)}(t+\tau) dt \equiv \phi_x^{(i)}(\tau) \quad (52)$$

In the above definitions, the time T is the length of the time window being used to estimate the statistics of $x^{(i)}(t)$, and the estimate becomes “sharp” in the limit $T \rightarrow \infty$. We have also defined the autocorrelation function $\phi_x^{(i)}(\tau)$ in the last line. Note that the “overbar” is used to represent time-averaged quantities.

Similarly, one can respectively define ensemble-averaged quantities using N identical systems, as defined at a certain point in time t_1 for a parameter $x(t_1)$ as:

$$\langle x(t_1) \rangle = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x^{(i)}(t_1) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x_1 p_1(x_1; t_1) dx_1 \quad (53)$$

$$\langle [x(t_1)]^2 \rangle = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [x^{(i)}(t_1)]^2 = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x_1^2 p_1(x_1; t_1) dx_1 \quad (54)$$

$$\langle x(t_1)x(t_2) \rangle = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x^{(i)}(t_1)x^{(i)}(t_2) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x_1 x_2 p_2(x_1, x_2; t_1, t_2) dx_1 dx_2 \quad (55)$$

In these definitions, N is the number of ensemble members used to make an estimate for the statistics of $x(t_1)$, and the estimate becomes “sharp” in the limit $N \rightarrow \infty$; we have implicitly defined $x_1 = x(t_1)$ and $x_2 = x(t_2)$; and the quantities $p_1(x_1; t_1)$ and $p_2(x_1, x_2; t_1, t_2)$ are respectively the first-order and second-order joint probability density functions.

Ergodicity and Stationarity

The ensemble average is generally a theoretical concept that describes a system's statistics by a probability density function derived from a particular theoretical model. Since it is generally impractical to make N identical systems and measure them all simultaneously, one generally characterizes the statistics of a single system through time averaging of a measured time trace. These theoretical and experimental approaches are equivalent to an ergodic ensemble, that is when the system is said to be ergodic.

A system is stationary if quantities such as $\overline{x^{(i)}(t)}$ and $\overline{[x^{(i)}(t)]^2}$ are independent of time (when they are measured), and quantities such as $\phi_x^{(i)}(\tau)$ depend only on the time difference τ . In other words, the statistics do not change with time. This can be further quantified by the order of stationarity: a stochastic process is stationary to order k if its k^{th} -order probability density function is time-independent. Similarly, there are degrees of ergodicity (e.g., ergodicity in the mean, etc.).

Ergodicity implies stationarity since one sample function represents the entire process. However, although stationarity implies ergodicity (that time averaging and ensemble averaging is equivalent), this is not always the case. For example, consider a bucket of batteries of varying types and select one at random. Let us say we picked a 9V battery. We find that the mean battery voltage $\overline{v(t)}$ is independent of time, so we infer that it is the first-order stationary. However, this battery is but one type of battery. What if the bucket also had other types of batteries, such as 1.5V batteries? In that case, the statistical ensemble average would be different. Thus, one, in general, cannot infer ergodicity from stationarity, without additional (often reasonable) assumptions. Here, we would need to assume that the bucket only holds nominally identical 9V batteries, for instance.

Noise power spectral density and the Wiener-Khintchine theorem

A system is called wide-sense stationary or weakly stationary if its mean and auto-correlation function are stationary. For wide-sense stationary processes, the Wiener-Khintchine theorem relates the autocorrelation function $\phi_x^{(i)}(\tau)$ to the noise power spectral density $S_x(\omega)$:

$$S_x(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \phi_x(\tau) e^{-i\omega\tau} d\tau, \quad (3.7) \quad (56)$$

$$\phi_x(\tau) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} S_x(\omega) e^{i\omega\tau} d\omega, \quad (3.8) \quad (57)$$

Where we have defined $S_x(\omega)$ as a bilateral spectral density defined overall negative and positive frequencies to accommodate the potential for asymmetric spectra, negative frequencies correspond to noise processes associated with a qubit absorbing photons from the environment, and positive frequencies correspond to the qubit emitting photons to the environment. The asymmetry between photon absorption and emission arises due to spontaneous emission: a qubit in its excited state can emit a photon to its environment even if that environment is at zero temperature whereas it cannot absorb energy from a zero-temperature environment (the environment has no energy to give). The origin of asymmetric spectra is traceable to the fact that quantum operators generally do not commute at different times. Instead, their commutation

relation is in general imaginary, and Fourier spectra are only symmetric in frequency when their time-domain counterpart is manifestly real.

Characterizing the power spectral density of noise seen by the qubit is a first step to mitigate that noise, whether by reducing the source of the noise or by designing the qubit to be insensitive to it. With knowledge of the frequency spectrum, one can design noise filter functions that decouple the qubit from certain types of low-frequency noise. This type of noise mitigation is achieved by applying gate operations (for instance, X-gates, Y-gates,) to the qubit in a specified manner. The pulse sequence in the time domain corresponds to a filter function in the frequency domain. These types of noise mitigation techniques are essentially a filter-design problem, and they are enabled by knowing the noise power spectral density.

Lastly, its worth noting that the auto-correlation function and noise power spectral density are second-order statistics. While this generally captures the predominant noise sources affecting qubits today, environmental noise may also exhibit higher-order correlations and correspondingly higher-order noise spectra.

The image below represents the “static noise” that we may remember seeing when we had poor analog TV reception. Let us take the reception here to be very poor, such that there is no underlying image and only static noise.

For this problem, let us assume that each pixel has a “brightness” that varies continuously between white (bright) and black (dark), with all shades of grey in between. For a given pixel, we will assume the brightness is fluctuating randomly in time according to a uniform probability distribution. That is, all shades of grey (including black and white) are equally likely to appear at any given time. We will also assume that the correlation time is infinitesimally short. Finally, we will assume that all pixels behave this way, but are completely independent of one another. To characterize this noise, let us assign the value zero to black, one to white, with all grey shades being the values in between zero and one.

Figure 3: static noise

There are two ways to calculate statistical averages of this noise:

1. By looking at one pixel and averaging its fluctuating brightness over time.
2. By taking a screenshot at a fixed time, and averaging the brightness across all pixels.

These two alternatives correspond to the temporal average and the ensemble average, respectively. By assumption, the temporal auto-correlation of a given pixel is how the brightness of a pixel at one time is related to its brightness at a later time to be very small. Since the auto-correlation is very short in time, by Fourier transform properties, the noise power spectral density

is essentially uniformly distributed in frequency (“white noise”). After carefully staring at the screen for a very long time, we determine that both the mean and the autocorrelation function in time are equivalent to the mean and covariance of the pixel ensemble.

4. Density Matrices; In Density Matrix, we discussed how to write the density matrix of a single-qubit. To do so, we considered the two-qubit state $|\psi_{AB}\rangle = \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}|0_A\rangle|0_B\rangle + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}}|1_A\rangle|1_B\rangle$ and found the probability of projecting qubit B onto the states $|0_B\rangle$ and $|1_B\rangle$. we used these results to write the density matrix of qubit A after the measurement of B,

$$\rho_A = p_{B,0} |\psi_{A,0}\rangle \langle \psi_{A,0}| + p_{B,1} |\psi_{A,1}\rangle \langle \psi_{A,1}|, = \frac{3}{4} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} + \frac{1}{4} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (58)$$

In this assessment, we should use the same steps used to compute the density matrix of qubit A after measuring qubit B if a Hadamard gate is applied on B before the measurement.

Start by considering the two-qubit state after the Hadamard gate and its complex conjugate

$$\begin{aligned} |\psi'_{AB}\rangle &= \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}|0_A\rangle \frac{|0_B\rangle + |1_B\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}}|1_A\rangle \frac{|0_B\rangle - |1_B\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \\ \langle \psi'_{AB}| &= \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}\langle 0_A| \frac{\langle 0_B| + \langle 1_B|}{\sqrt{2}} + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}}\langle 1_A| \frac{\langle 0_B| - \langle 1_B|}{\sqrt{2}} \end{aligned} \quad (59)$$

The probability of projecting qubit B on to state $|0_B\rangle$ and $|1_B\rangle$ is given by $p'_{B,0} = \langle \psi'_{AB}| (I_A \otimes \Pi_0) |\psi'_{AB}\rangle$ and $p'_{B,1} = \langle \psi'_{AB}| (I_A \otimes \Pi_1) |\psi'_{AB}\rangle$ respectively. Here, I is the identity operator, Π_0 is the single-qubit projector $|0\rangle\langle 0|$, and Π_1 is the single-qubit projector $|1\rangle\langle 1|$. To find the probabilities $p'_{B,0}$ and $p'_{B,1}$, it is easier to first calculate

$$(I_A \otimes \Pi_0) |\psi'_{AB}\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}|0_A\rangle|0_B\rangle + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}}|1_A\rangle|0_B\rangle \right) \quad (60)$$

and

$$(I_A \otimes \Pi_1) |\psi'_{AB}\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}|0_A\rangle|1_B\rangle - \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}}|1_A\rangle|1_B\rangle \right) \quad (61)$$

The probabilities are then given by:

$$\begin{aligned} p'_{B,0} &= \langle \psi'_{AB}| (I_A \otimes \Pi_0) |\psi'_{AB}\rangle \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \langle \psi'_{AB}| \left(\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}|0_A\rangle|0_B\rangle + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}}|1_A\rangle|0_B\rangle \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (62)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} p'_{B,1} &= \langle \psi'_{AB}| (I_A \otimes \Pi_1) |\psi'_{AB}\rangle \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \langle \psi'_{AB}| \left(\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}|0_A\rangle|1_B\rangle - \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}}|1_A\rangle|1_B\rangle \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (63)$$

We may wish to use Wolfram Alpha online to calculate square roots. Round results to two decimal places, if necessary.

5. Density Matrices Part A;

- What is the state of qubit A if B is projected to $|0_B\rangle$?

- $|\psi'_{A,0}\rangle = 0.86 |0_A\rangle + 0.5 |1_A\rangle$

- What is the state of qubit A if B is projected to $|1_B\rangle$?

- $|\psi'_{A,1}\rangle = 0.86 |0_A\rangle - 0.5 |1_A\rangle$

Note that we ask about the amplitudes, not the probabilities, in the fields above (round to two decimal places).

Solution:

The probability of projecting qubit B to state $|0_B\rangle$ is given by $p'_{B,0} = \langle \psi'_{AB} | (I_A \otimes \Pi_0) | \psi'_{AB} \rangle$, where I is the identity operator and Π_0 is the single-qubit projector $|0\rangle\langle 0|$. To find the probability $p'_{B,0}$ we first calculate

$$\begin{aligned} & (I_A \otimes \Pi_0) | \psi'_{AB} \rangle \\ = & (I_A \otimes |0_B\rangle\langle 0_B|) \left(\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} |0_A\rangle \frac{|0_B\rangle + |1_B\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}} |1_A\rangle \frac{|0_B\rangle - |1_B\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \\ = & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} |0_A\rangle + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}} |1_A\rangle \right) |0_B\rangle, \end{aligned}$$

and then

$$p'_{B,0} = \langle \psi'_{AB} | (I_A \otimes \Pi_0) | \psi'_{AB} \rangle = \frac{1}{2}.$$

In the same way, to find the probability of projecting qubit B to state $|1_B\rangle$, we first calculate

$$\begin{aligned} & (I_A \otimes \Pi_1) | \psi'_{AB} \rangle \\ = & (I_A \otimes |1_B\rangle\langle 1_B|) \left(\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} |0_A\rangle \frac{|0_B\rangle + |1_B\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}} |1_A\rangle \frac{|0_B\rangle - |1_B\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right), \\ = & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} |0_A\rangle - \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}} |1_A\rangle \right) |1_B\rangle, \end{aligned}$$

and then

$$p'_{B,1} = \langle \psi'_{AB} | (I_A \otimes \Pi_1) | \psi'_{AB} \rangle = \frac{1}{2}.$$

The two-qubit state after qubit B is projected to $|0_B\rangle$ and $|1_B\rangle$ is given by

$$\frac{(I_A \otimes \Pi_0) | \psi'_{AB} \rangle}{\sqrt{\langle \psi'_{AB} | (I_A \otimes \Pi_0) | \psi'_{AB} \rangle}} = \left(\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} |0_A\rangle + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}} |1_A\rangle \right) |0_B\rangle,$$

and

$$\frac{(I_A \otimes \Pi_1) | \psi'_{AB} \rangle}{\sqrt{\langle \psi'_{AB} | (I_A \otimes \Pi_1) | \psi'_{AB} \rangle}} = \left(\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} |0_A\rangle - \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}} |1_A\rangle \right) |1_B\rangle.$$

Thus the state of qubit A after qubit B is projected to $|0_B\rangle$ and $|1_B\rangle$ is

$$|\psi'_{A,0}\rangle = \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}|0_A\rangle + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}}|1_A\rangle,$$

$$|\psi'_{A,1}\rangle = \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}|0_A\rangle - \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}}|1_A\rangle, \text{ respectively.}$$

6. Density Matrices Part B;

- If there is no information about to which state qubit B was projected, what is the density matrix that describes the state of qubit A?
- In Dirac notation,
- $\rho_A = 0.5 |\psi'_{A,0}\rangle \langle \psi'_{A,0}| + 0.5 |\psi'_{A,1}\rangle \langle \psi'_{A,1}|$
- In matrix form,
- $\rho_A = 0.75 \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} + 0.25 \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$

Solution:

If there is no information about to which state qubit B was projected, the state of qubit A can be described by the density matrix

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_A &= p_{B,0} |\psi'_{A,0}\rangle \langle \psi'_{A,0}| + p_{B,1} |\psi'_{A,1}\rangle \langle \psi'_{A,1}|, \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}|0_A\rangle + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}}|1_A\rangle \right) \left(\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}\langle 0_A| + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}}\langle 1_A| \right) \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \left(\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}|0_A\rangle - \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}}|1_A\rangle \right) \left(\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}\langle 0_A| - \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}}\langle 1_A| \right), \\ &= \frac{3}{4}|0_A\rangle \langle 0_A| + \frac{1}{4}|1_A\rangle \langle 1_A|, \\ &= \frac{3}{4} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} + \frac{1}{4} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned}$$

Noise Mechanisms: Superconducting Qubit Example

Figure 4: Noise Mechanisms

Rabi Oscillation: Amplitude Noise

Figure 5: Rabi Oscillation

Time Average versus Ensemble Average

Figure 6: Noise Characterization and the Noise Power Spectral Density

9 Quantum Communication Perspectives

In this section, we will look at the practical challenges faced by realistic quantum communication today. As we have seen throughout the section, the promise of quantum communication centers on achieving quantum advantage for applications such as secret sharing, networking, authentication, and key distribution. For many of these schemes, entanglement is a resource that enables quantum enhancement when shared between two or more parties [20]. However, we face several practical issues when implementing quantum communication protocols, and we will touch on several of those in this section. We will revisit Bell states and discuss a game related to Bell's classical argument that forms a well-defined inequality that classical probability arguments must respect, but one that quantum mechanics consistently violates. We will also look at the challenges of long-distance entanglement distribution using repeaters to mitigate photon loss and other schemes being developed to enable long-distance QKD. Moreover, finally, we will take a deep dive into quantum entanglement, exploring its mathematical representation and measures [64], as well as its fungibility. However, first, to get started, let us discuss about entropy and channel capacity, fundamental concepts of information theory, and their representations in noisy classical and quantum communication. An insightful perspective for quantum communication is provided by starting with the scenario of classical communication. Here, the goal is to transmit a message, say, x , described by its probability distribution function. What is received is a noisy message from the output of the channel, call that y . The input to the channel is x . Two principal ideas describe this scenario mathematically. First, H of x , known as the entropy of x , is the number of bits needed to represent the message, x , on average faithfully. Second, the capacity, c , is the max overall probability distributions of something called the mutual information. We are x, y , which is the maximum error-free communication rate achievable over the noisy channel. The two key concepts here are the entropy, H of x , and the mutual information, I of x, y . There are parallels to this in quantum communication. In this scenario, the source messages are described by a density matrix. It is a distribution, which may be viewed as a dis-

tribution over pure states, for example. These may be non-orthogonal states, in contrast to the classical case. A density matrix also describes the received message. Furthermore, in contrast to the classical case, this is possibly decoded quantum mechanically, say by a quantum computer. Analogous to the classical case, the Von Neumann entropy describes the number of qubits needed to represent the density matrix ρ faithfully. This is asymptotical. This entropy is similar to but different from the Shannon entropy, as we will see. Also, there are several distinct scenarios for noisy communication. After all, classical data may be the source as well as the received data. Alternatively, this source may be quantum data. Alternatively, the receiver may receive and decode quantum mechanically. Alternatively, both the sender and receiver may be quantum. It is known that these channel capacities are ordered. CCC is less than CQC and CCQ and is less than CQQ. There are even richer scenarios beyond these four. Entanglement may also be used to assist, for example, classical communication. When the sender and receiver have pre-shared entangled qubits, this may change the time of capacity. Another set of capacity measure results when quantum information is allowed to be sent, but only one way or two ways, and possibly, in addition to having a classical side channel. Beyond this, quantum communication may also involve multiple parties. Quantum communication is thus a fascinating field of study.

Information exchange between a sender and receiver is conducted over communication channels. Wherever previously, we considered ideal communication channels, we will address the practical issues and challenges associated with communicating on realistic, physical channels. A primary consideration is the reduction of signal integrity due to information loss in the channel and/or the addition of noise to the channel.

Its classical counterpart inspires the characterization of quantum communication. The characterization of classical communication comprises two primary figures of merit. The first figure of merit is the entropy H , which is related to the average number of bits m required to represent a message M . The averaged Shannon entropy is defined as $H(M) = -\sum_i^{2^m} p(M_i) \log_2 p(M_i) = m$, with each bit being equally likely $p(M_i) = \frac{1}{2}$. Within this definition, the entropy $H(M)$ is the same for all messages M with m bits. The second figure of merit is the maximal achievable error-free communication rate, referred to as the channel capacity, which can be deduced by comparing the shared mutual information of the received message \tilde{M} with the original message M .

The characterization of quantum information on quantum channels follows an analogous definition for entropy. The von Neumann entropy $S(\rho) = -Tr(\rho \ln \rho)$ describes the number of qubits required to represent a density matrix ρ corresponding to the quantum information being transmitted. Similarly, the channel capacity can be inferred by comparing the received density matrix $\tilde{\rho}$ to the initial density matrix ρ , and there are several definitions for channel capacity, depending on how the information is sent and received.

While a quantum communication channel generally transmits information encoded in quantum states, in practice, many schemes also require parallel classical channels to implement fully a particular protocol. Upon receipt, the information may either remain quantum-mechanical, for example, be stored in a quantum system for further processing, or it may also be measured to retrieve an underlying classical output.

10 Quantum Weirdness

we will be discussing quantum weirdness. We think of discussing this, and we first want to go back to a paper by Einstein, Podolsky, and Rosen. That is EPR 1935. What Einstein argued was that quantum mechanics is incomplete. So, what Einstein used in this paper were position

and momentum. However, we are working with discrete quantum mechanics, so we will just use, well, up and down or 0 and 1. So, we want to give Einstein's argument. So, suppose Alice and Bob share a pair of entangled particles like this. Alice measures in the 0, 1 basis. Bob will have the opposite particle, no matter what Alice measures. So, if she measures a 0, he gets a 1, and if she measures a 1, he gets a 0. If she measures in the plus or minus basis, Alice gets a plus, and Bob will always get a minus. If Alice gets a minus, Bob will always get a plus. Because Alice and Bob can be reasonably far apart and can measure at the same time with relativistic speeds, Bob's particle cannot know whether Alice measured a 0 or 1 when Bob measures it. If Alice can predict what Bob gets, which she can because she can predict in the plus, minus basis if she measures in the plus, minus basis. If she can predict on the 1, 0 bases if Bob measures on the 1, 0 bases. If Alice can always predict 100% what Bob will do, then there must be something in the quantum state that tells what Bob will get when he measures it. So, we would think that there is something in this quantum state that tells whether it is going to be a 0 or 1 when Bob measures it. However, we know, according to quantum mechanics, that there is nothing in this state that tells whether it is going to be a 0 or a 1. So, what that means is that there must be a more complete theory of reality than quantum mechanics. So, this is what Einstein argued. Schrodinger wrote a paper that answered that. Schrodinger's paper said that qubits particles are verschränkten, which is a German word that means crossed arms or crossed legs, or intertwined fingers. That is why this happens, which is not that great of an explanation. Then Schrodinger, we know, later translated verschränkten into English as entangled, because crossed would not have worked. Nobody paid much attention to Einstein's argument for the next 25 or 30 years or so. Einstein was never satisfied with quantum mechanics completely. However, quantum mechanics worked. So, they ignored this objection to it. Then, in 1964, Bell published a paper that said Einstein was both rights in that there is something very strange going on here. However, wrong in that, there is no way to complete this theory to a real theory because the arguments of quantum mechanics contradict classical probability theory.

11 Bell's Argument as a Classical Game

we are going to present Bell's argument first. Originally, it is a statement about the marginal probabilities of a joint probability distribution. Nevertheless, we find it makes much more intuitive sense if we discuss it as a game that two players are cooperatively trying to play. It is called the CHSH game with Alice and Bob. So, Alice and Bob are two of the prototypical participants in cryptosystems. So, they are playing a game. They want to cooperate to win with as high a probability as possible. So, we have a referee who does not make any decisions. He just flips coins and does what the instructions tell him so, and he sends a bit to Alice and Bob. So, we will have him send A to Alice and B to Bob. Then Alice and Bob, who are in separate rooms and cannot communicate, get these two bits and output two more bits x, y, two bits. We should say the referee chooses his bits completely at random. So, now, we need to tell us when people win and lose to determine the game. So, Alice and Bob win if $x \oplus y = a \oplus b$. we should say $x \oplus y \pmod 2$. So, that is an x exclusive or y. So, that should be pretty clear, but we want to put up a little chart. So, a can either be 0 or 1 b can either be 0 or 1. Alice and Bob win if $x \oplus y = 0$ $x \oplus y = 0$, $x \oplus y = 0$, and $x \oplus y = 1$. Now let us pretend that Alice and Bob have to do this deterministically. So, Alice has a little chart. If x equals 0, output 0. If x equals 1, output 1 or something like that. There is a general theory in games like this, Alice and Bob cannot do any better with a probabilistic strategy than a deterministic strategy. We will get to that later. So, this is $x_0 \oplus y_0$ x_0 being the bit that Alice outputs if a is 0. It is $x_0 \oplus y_1$. It is $x_1 \oplus y_0$, and this is $x_1 \oplus y_1$. These are all mod 2. So, this is what

Alice and Bob want. Now, can anyone tell why they cannot win with probability 100%? That is right. So, we sum everything up. That is $2x_0$ plus $2x_1$, plus $2y_0$, plus $2y_1$ is equal to 1 mod 2. That does not work, because there are 2 x_1 's in this chart, 2 x_0 's, 2 y_1 's, and 2 y_0 's. Alice and Bob can only win with a probability of 75%. Why is this? So, there is no choice of x_0 and x_1 for Alice and Bob x_0 , x_1 , y_0 , and y_1 that makes this perfect. So, let us suppose that Alice and Bob have agreed in advance to some combination of x_0 , x_1 , y_0 , and y_1 . The referee comes along and sends them two bits, which randomly select one of these four boxes. We know one of these four boxes has to disagree with what Alice and Bob want because they cannot all work. So, at least one has to be wrong. If one is wrong, and the referee picks that one, which he does 1/4 of the time, then Alice and Bob lose. So, that is 75%. Now, we want to argue why a random strategy cannot do any better. So, for a random strategy, we have a probability that they win equals the sum probability of So, random strategy, we can always think of this as Alice, and Bob gets some set of random bits. We do not care whether They are correlated or not. Then, for these random bits, they pick a deterministic outcome of x_0 , x_1 , y_0 , and y_1 . So, the probability that Alice and Bob win with a random strategy is equal to sum times the probability of string r , random bits, times the probability that Alice and Bob win given r . So, this is essentially an average of how often they win given any particular string of random bits. So, if this was greater than 3/4, there must be some string of random bits, which gives Alice and Bob a deterministic strategy of winning with probability at least 3/4. We just argued that it was impossible. So, that is the classical part. So, now we want to say that if Alice and Bob have an EPR pair of qubits $0,1$ minus $1,0$, then they can win with probability larger than 75%. The problem with 1 over 2 , $0,1$ minus $1,0$ is that Alice and Bob get opposite answers every time. We find it much harder to think about getting opposite answers than getting the same answer. So, we want to find a way that Alice and Bob can arrange to get the same answer. In the CHSH game, Alice and Bob have spatially separated from each other from the time that the game starts until it is over, and they cannot communicate. The game starts when the referee randomly selects two bits, a and b , and sends a to Alice and b to Bob. Alice outputs the bit x , Bob outputs bit y , and both send their bits to the referee. After receiving the output bits x and y , the referee determines if the input and output bits satisfy the condition $x \oplus y = ab$ If the condition is satisfied, then Alice and Bob win; otherwise, they lose.

12 EPR Pair Violation: Introduction

Alice and Bob share $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|00\rangle + |11\rangle)$. Fact, if Alice and Bob measure the form $\alpha|0\rangle + \sigma|x\rangle$ and $\sigma|z\rangle$ so, they both make the same measurement, which is on this great circle of the Bloch sphere they get the same outcome. if they measure with the observable $\sigma|y\rangle$, they get opposite outcomes. So, we can easily check that proof for α equals 0 and α equals 1. here, we probably should have said $\alpha^2 + \beta^2$ is one, α, β real. So, proof for α equals 0 and α equals 1 α equals 1, that is $\sigma|z\rangle$. they just measure in the $0|1\rangle$ basis, which means they either get both 0 or they both get 1. α equals 0 is easy. α equals 1 that is $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|01\rangle + |10\rangle)$. we are going to put another one of $\sqrt{2}$ here. So, this is Alice's state, and this Alice Bob, Alice Bob. When we multiply this by this, we get 0 Bob. we multiply this by this, and we get 0 1 Bob. there is a 1/2 in front of here. similarly, if we had a minus here and a plus here, we would get a minus there. So, when we take the projection onto $0|1\rangle$, we get 0 plus 1. When we take the projection onto $0|0\rangle$, we get 0 minus 1. the proof for arbitrary α is not so hard. we are not going to go through it right now for lack of time. However, we want to use this. What is our strategy? Well, so, $0|1\rangle$ plus-minus and these are the points that are 45 degrees. So, this is the slice, vertical slice through the Bloch sphere. So, Alice chooses $0|1\rangle$ or plus-minus. So, Alice

and Bob are going to measure each going to measure their half of this state. we want to say, Alice chooses 0 1 or plus-minus with a probability depending on what bit a was. So, a equal 0 and a equal 1. we need variables. So, let us call this s and this axis t. So, Bob chooses s and the opposite of s, if b equals 0. he chooses t an opposite state of t if b equals 1.

13 EPR Pair Violation: Protocol

We want to say the first column here, the output is going to be 0, and the right column here will be the output is going to be 1. So, let us label this diagram. So, this is Alice, Alice, Alice, Alice, Bob, Bob, Bob, Bob. here, this is 0. we want a equal 0, a equal 1, b equals 0, and b equals 1. the outputs are going to be 0, 0, 0, 0. So, this is x. This is y. This is x. This is y. x equals 1, y equals 1, x equals 1, y equals 1. So, Alice gets a bit from the referee, and if the bit is 0, she chooses this basis, and if the bit is 1, she chooses that basis. Ditto from Bob. if Bob gets this state, he outputs 0, and if he gets this state, his outputs 1. So, suppose Alice gets a equal 0, and Bob gets b equals 0. Alice gets observable σ_z , and now we see that we should never have used x and y as the bits, because we have σ_z , which is and Bob measures the observable $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\sigma_x + \sigma_z)$. So, suppose Alice measures 0, and Bob has qubit 0. He measures it with $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\sigma_x + \sigma_z)$. So, what is the probability that he gets the eigenvector plus 1 for this? One way to do this is to compute the eigenvector plus 1 and take the inner product of it with 0 and square it. However, there is an easier way. It should be a root 2. The expectation of Bob's value is $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\langle \sigma_x + \sigma_z \rangle)$. So, how do we compute that? Well, it is just 1, 0. That is 0. 1, 1, 1, minus 1. So, that is $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\sigma_x + \sigma_z)$. Because σ_x was 1. 1 here. And σ_z was 1 minus 1. Must put a 1 over root 2 in front of that, times. It should have been a row vector, and this should be a column vector. These times that is 1, so this is 1 over root 2. Nevertheless, this is equal to the probability that Bob gets 0 minus the probability that Bob gets 1 because the expectation of this observable, and this observable has two eigenvalues, 1 and minus 1. The probability and the one eigenvalue corresponds to Bob getting a 0 are getting y equals 0, and the minus eigenvalue corresponds to an ability that Bob gets y equals 1. Thus, if we want two numbers whose difference is 1 over root 2 and whose sum is 1 because of the probability sum to 1. So, this is $\frac{1}{2}$ half plus 1 over root 2, and this is $\frac{1}{2}$ minus 1 over root 2. So, this is the probability that Bob wins if Alice measures a 0. So, what is that probability? It is 0.854 roughly. let us go back and look. it is also equal to the cosine of $\pi/8$ squared. So, let us go back and look at this picture again. That was the probability that Alice and Bob won if they, we know if they got a equal 0, b equals 0. Well, the probability that we win if they get b equals 0 and a equal 1 is also Yes? 1 over 2 roots 2 and 1 over 1/2 minus 1 over 2 roots 2. Thank we very much. However, this is 0.854.

14 EPR Pair Violation: Violation

So, let us go back and look at this diagram some more. That was the probability Alice and Bob win if they use these two axes, or these two yes, these two points on the Bloch sphere, which have, differ by an angle of $\pi/4$. But we know. If they use these two points on the Bloch sphere, which also differ by $\pi/4$, they also win without probability, because the only thing that matters when telling whether two axes on the Bloch sphere agree is the angle between the points. For b equals 1 and a equal 1. Well, how about b equals 1 and a equal 0? we know that a equal 1 and b equals 1, Bob gets 0, and Alice gets 1. So, this point and this point, and we want to know how often does occur together. Well, they occur together with 1 minus the probability that these two give

the same answer, because y is 0, and here y is 1. So, x and y agree for these exactly when x and y disagree for these. Nevertheless, x and y disagree exactly when, but we know, if Alice will get this answer and Bob will get this answer, the probability is also 0.854. So, that means that Bob and Alice got (0,1), (0,0) and (1,0), they wanted their bits to agree. If they chose a equal 1 and b equals 1, they want their bits to disagree, and they disagree with exactly the same probability that these two things would agree. We do not think we said that very well, but hopefully, we understand what we mean. X equals 0, and b equals 1 are the vice versa, x plus y equals one with a probability of 0.854. So, this is what we wanted to happen. So, Alice and Bob can win this game with a probability of 0.854, which is bigger than 0.75. There are two more things we want to say. Let us draw another thing. If this is θ , these two observables agree with probability $\cos^2 \theta/2$. So, that is $\cos^2 \pi/8$. However, we know, if Bob, we know, if we have measured these two observables simultaneously, the probability that they would be agreed would be called $\cos^2 \pi/4$, which is $1/2$. We know that these two observables, we know, that Alice measures 0 and Bob measures plus, they agree with the probability of $1/2$. These two observables never agree, and that is cosine squared $\pi/2$. So, this is the general formula for, we know, if Alice and Bob have an entangled state, and they measure something, two observables θ apart, its cosine squared θ over 2. we are not going to prove that. Yes. So, this means that this particular strategy is the optimal one? That is the next thing we were going to say. We can prove that this particular strategy is the optimal one. They cannot do better than 0.854 at this game, and that is well. We are not going to prove it in this section because it is a little more complicated than everything we have done so far. However, we think it is the one who proved it. So, now this gives a game that Alice and Bob can win with higher probability if they have an entangled state than if not.

We generally observe and accept that quantum systems behave differently than classical systems. However, in practice, how are they different? Furthermore, are there means to quantify or even prove this distinction? For example:

1. Is the seemingly “weird behavior” (i.e., non-classical behavior) associated with quantum systems simply a result of quantum mechanics being somehow an “incomplete description” of the system behavior implying that, if we had a complete description, then such quantum “weirdness” would be understandable and consistent with our classical notion of proper behavior and no longer strange?

- 2, Or, is quantum mechanics fundamentally different, implying that the quantum description is already complete, and the observed “weirdness” is fundamental?

The weirdness of quantum mechanics and quantum entanglement, in particular, has bothered many great minds since the advent of quantum theory. Most notably, in 1935, Albert Einstein, Boris Podolsky, and Nathan Rosen (EPR) presented a thought experiment on quantum weirdness, which initiated a several-decades-long debate on the theory of quantum mechanics itself.

The thought experiment called the EPR paradox centers around two, distant entangled particles; for example, two polarization-entangled photons, one in Alice’s lab and one in Bob’s lab, with the labs separated by a very large distance. Let us take as an example the entangled state $|\Psi^-\rangle = (1/\sqrt{2})(|H\rangle_A|V\rangle_B - |V\rangle_A|H\rangle_B)$, where $|H\rangle$ and $|V\rangle$ are the two basis states for the polarization of the photon, which stand for horizontal and vertical, respectively. As usual, $\langle V|H\rangle = 0$.

We know that when Alice and Bob measure their photons using the same measurement basis, they will have correlated measurement results. For example, if Alice measures H polarization, then Bob will measure V polarization and visa versa. It is not yet the weird part, as we know that if one photon is H, then the other must be V.

Now, if Alice and Bob choose to measure in different measurement bases, then the result may change. For example, let us say Alice again measures in the H-V basis, and Bob decides to measure in the A-D basis, where $|A/D\rangle \equiv (1/\sqrt{2})(|H\rangle \pm |V\rangle)$. In this case, no matter what Alice measures whether an H or a V Bob will always have a 50/50 chance of measuring A or D. In other words, there is no longer any correlation between Alice's result and Bob's result.

Here is where it gets weird. Assume that Alice and Bob are separated by a very large distance much larger than the distance it would take light to travel in a reasonable amount of time such that choice of Alice's measurement basis cannot reach Bob in time to influence his choice of basis or measurement outcome. We will assume that Alice and Bob each independently, randomly, and at the same time, decide a basis to measure in, either the H-V basis or the A-D basis. In this situation, the choice of Alice and Bob's measurement bases whether the same or different bases will affect the outcome of their measurement, but there is no way (even traveling at the speed of light) that any information about one's choice of basis could influence the other's measurement! Nevertheless, it does: the presence or absence of observed correlations depended on their independent choices.

Einstein, Podolsky, and Rosen did not like this seemingly "spooky action at a distance," asserting that Alice's measurement cannot possibly influence Bob's measurement due to the large distance. The only explanation for the observed correlations is the underlying "hidden variables" that are not captured in the quantum theory that predetermines the measurement result. In other words, quantum mechanics is incomplete.

In response, Niels Bohr, a contemporary of EPR, argued that the theory of quantum mechanics merely describes the interaction of the measured quantum system with the measurement apparatus and not the intrinsic character of the quantum system itself. Therefore, one cannot assume that measurements do not disturb a quantum system. Hence, EPR's conjecture that quantum theory must be incomplete without hidden variables does not warrant a rather uninspiring explanation.

In 1964, John Bell developed a theorem Bell's inequality based on classical probability arguments that could distinguish whether quantum mechanics is incomplete requiring hidden variables or is indeed fundamentally correct "as is". Five years later, John Clauser, Michael Horne, Abner Shimony, and Richard Holt presented a physical method to test a specific case of Bell's inequality theorem, referred to today as the CHSH inequality. Essentially, if observed experimental results respect the CHSH inequality based on classical probability arguments, then a "hidden variables"-type argument must be invoked. In contrast, if experimental results do not satisfy the inequality referred to as a "violation" of the inequality, quantum mechanics is a complete theory.

POINCARÉ SPHERE

Figure 7: Poincare

Let us consider an example of the CHSH inequality. Suppose there is a source creating pairs of polarization-entangled photons such as $|\Psi^-\rangle = 1/\sqrt{2}(|H\rangle_A|V\rangle_B - |V\rangle_A|H\rangle_B)$. One photon of the entangled pair is routed to Alice and one to Bob. Alice and Bob simultaneously measure their photons in their distant labs upon arrival of their share of the entangled photon pair. The measurement scenario is a bit different than the one described above. Alice randomly measures her photon either along the Poincaré sphere's z-axis horizontal $|H\rangle$ or vertical $|V\rangle$ polarization or along the x-axis diagonal $|D\rangle$ or antidiagonal $|A\rangle$ polarization denoted as M_A^z and M_A^x , respectively. Bob, on the other hand, randomly measures his photon along with a different pair of axes either along the axis halfway between the z- and x-axes or the axis halfway between the z-axis and the negative x-axis here referred to as M_B^{z+x} and M_B^{z-x} , respectively. Using any of these four bases, a measurement will project out either “up” or “down” along that axis, corresponding to 1 or -1, respectively.

According to the EPR argument, measurement results depend on underlying “hidden variables” such that a measurement of one party has no “non-classical” influence on the other party’s measurement. To see this, let us define a quantity: $Q = M_A^z(M_B^{z+x} + M_B^{z-x}) + M_A^x(M_B^{z+x} - M_B^{z-x})$ and make a table of all possible measurement outcomes with the EPR assumptions.

Table 1: All possible measurement outcomes with the EPR assumptions

Measurement Results and Expectation Value for Q		$M_A^z \Rightarrow 1$	$M_A^z \Rightarrow 1$	$M_A^z \Rightarrow -1$	$M_A^z \Rightarrow -1$
		$M_A^x \Rightarrow 1$	$M_A^x \Rightarrow -1$	$M_A^x \Rightarrow 1$	$M_A^x \Rightarrow -1$
$M_B^{z+x} \Rightarrow 1$	$M_B^{z-x} \Rightarrow 1$	2	2	-2	-2
$M_B^{z+x} \Rightarrow 1$	$M_B^{z-x} \Rightarrow -1$	2	-2	2	-2
$M_B^{z+x} \Rightarrow -1$	$M_B^{z-x} \Rightarrow 1$	-2	2	-2	2
$M_B^{z+x} \Rightarrow -1$	$M_B^{z-x} \Rightarrow -1$	-2	-2	2	2

As seen from the table, over many measurements, the expectation value $E(Q)$ must satisfy:

$$-2 \leq E(Q) \leq 2 \quad (64)$$

$$-2 \leq E(M_A^z M_B^{z+x}) + E(M_A^z M_B^{z-x}) + E(M_A^x M_B^{z+x}) - E(M_A^x M_B^{z-x}) \leq 2 \quad (65)$$

The expanded version of $E(Q)$ is called the CHSH inequality.

As intended, results which satisfy the inequality are consistent with classical probability arguments; the previous paragraph ignored the impact of quantum mechanics on measurement outcomes. If we instead now assume that measuring the polarization of a photon is a quantum measurement and therefore requires a quantum mechanical description, the expectation value of $\langle Q \rangle$ yields a different result. For example, a calculation of $\langle \hat{M}_A^z \hat{M}_B^{z+x} \rangle$ yields:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \Psi^- | \hat{M}_A^z \hat{M}_B^{z+x} | \Psi^- \rangle &= \frac{\langle H|_A \langle V|_B - \langle V|_A \langle H|_B}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\hat{z} \otimes \frac{\hat{z} + \hat{x}}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \frac{|H\rangle_A |V\rangle_B - |V\rangle_A |H\rangle_B}{\sqrt{2}} \\ &= \frac{\langle H|_A \langle V|_B - \langle V|_A \langle H|_B}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{|H\rangle_A (|H\rangle_B - |V\rangle_B) + |V\rangle_A (|H\rangle_B + |V\rangle_B)}{2} \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{-1 - 1}{2} = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} = \langle \hat{M}_A^z \hat{M}_B^{z+x} \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (66)$$

And, one can similarly derive: $\langle \hat{M}_A^x \hat{M}_B^{z+x} \rangle = -1/\sqrt{2}$, $\langle \hat{M}_A^z \hat{M}_B^{z-x} \rangle = -1/\sqrt{2}$, and $\langle \hat{M}_A^x \hat{M}_B^{z-x} \rangle = 1/\sqrt{2}$. The resulting expectation values following the rules of quantum mechanics violate the CHSH inequality.

$$\langle Q \rangle = \langle \hat{M}_A^z \hat{M}_B^{z+x} \rangle + \langle \hat{M}_A^z \hat{M}_B^{z-x} \rangle + \langle \hat{M}_A^x \hat{M}_B^{z+x} \rangle - \langle \hat{M}_A^x \hat{M}_B^{z-x} \rangle = -2\sqrt{2} < -2 \quad (67)$$

With such a “yes/no” inequality in hand, one can experimentally test whether the calculated inequality is satisfied or not. To date, numerous examples of experiments have violated Bell’s inequality using a number of physical systems.

However, as we might expect, scientists over the years have pointed out “loopholes” in the experimental realizations of the inequality test, such as the measurement loophole, or the communication loophole, and related to the fact that our detectors are not perfect, or the distance may not be large enough to avoid speed-of-light communication. Recently, all of these loopholes have been closed except one: the “free-will” loophole, which essentially questions whether or not Alice and Bob can truly pick their measurement bases independently and at random in other words, do we have “free will”. Nonetheless, with this one exception, all experimental results are consistent with a quantum description of the world, and hidden variables are not required to describe physical reality.

15 Quantum Repeaters: Introduction

In the section, we have looked at quantum communication and the promise for quantum advantage in applications such as secret sharing, networking, and authentication. We have also looked in detail at how to implement quantum key distribution using single and entangled photon polarization states. For many of these schemes, we have seen that entanglement is a resource that needs to be distributed between two or more parties separated by some distance in order to implement the protocols. In this section, we will address a practical concern that we will face in any realistic quantum communication implementation. Namely, over long distances, how do we ensure that our photons and quantum information make it through the communication channel without getting lost along the way? While this might seem like a trivial concern at first glance, we know from the no-cloning theorem that quantum states cannot simply be amplified in the way that we amplify classical signals, and so, the nature of quantum mechanics leads to a fundamental complication which demands a more clever solution. As we will see, here again, quantum mechanics takes away with one hand and gets back with another. Consider the following. Alice and Bob want to establish a secure communication link using a QKD protocol. Both Alice and Bob have access to the required photon sources, detectors, and other tools that we have discussed previously. There is just one problem. Alice and Bob live in cities that are 500 kilometers away from one another. To complicate matters, there is a large mountain range in between these two cities which prevents any direct free space communication between the two. There are other issues with free-space communication, but let us go with the scenario. Free space communication is just not possible here. Thankfully, the two cities are connected by a run of optical fiber. Just like the fiber optic cable that an internet provider uses to deliver high-speed web access, this cable is simply a flexible transparent glass fiber designed to guide and transmit light over long distances. So, in principle, all Alice and Bob need to do is plug their photon sources and detectors into each end of the fiber, and it will guide their photons from one city to the other, winding over and between the mountains in between. The practical issue is that, as we may already know or may have surmised, optical fiber does not transmit light perfectly. After a photon enters one end of the fiber, as it is guided along, there is a small but non-negligible probability that the photon will be lost along the way and not make it out the other side. It is usually due to a combination of incoherent scattering and photon absorption due to the various types of inhomogeneity in the glass. For typical optical fibers, the losses are really low, only about 0.2 dB per kilometer. There is only a 5% chance of a photon getting lost for a one-kilometer length of the fiber. So, that is not too bad. However, the problem is that this loss scales exponentially with the length of the cable. If we assume a constant loss of 0.2 dB per kilometer and calculate the loss, we would expect over 500 kilometers connecting Alice and Bob, and we find that the probability of a single photon successfully making it through is only about one part in 10 billion, and continues to plummet as we add each additional kilometer. Now, we use optical fiber for intercity and classical transoceanic communication all the time. So, we have solved this problem for classical optical signals. For these signals, we overcome the intrinsic loss by installing amplifiers periodically throughout the fiber. When a given photon successfully travels through a length of the fiber and reaches an amplifier, it is amplified, or duplicated into multiple copies, which then continue through the fiber. Now, many of these copies will subsequently be lost in the next section of fiber. However, as long as the amplifiers appear often enough, some fraction of the photons will succeed in making it to the next amplifier. In this way, the loss is overcome, and the signals faithfully transmitted from one end of the fiber to the other. That is classical optical communication. We know from this section that this type of amplification will not work for quantum communication due to the no-cloning theorem. Let us say Alice prepares a single photon in a particular but arbitrary polarization state. The photon travels a length of the

fiber and encounters some amplifier, which we hope would somehow duplicate the photon and its quantum state. However, this sort of amplifier violates the no-cloning theorem. There is simply no physical device that can take an arbitrary quantum state and generate multiple copies. So, classical amplification is not going to help overcome photon loss in our fiber. Fortunately, all is not lost. As it turns out, we can use quantum entanglement to our advantage here. As we have seen previously, entanglement can be swapped between pairs of qubits [65]. we can use a variant of entanglement swapping to teleport the state of one qubit onto another qubit without the two qubits ever directly interacting. To see how this helps, we will take a step back and review how quantum teleportation works. we will start with Alice and her polarized photon at the stateside, which she is trying to send to Bob. Imagine that halfway down the fiber line connecting Alice and Bob, we install an entangled photon source. This source generates two photons in a maximally entangled bell state. the two photons are sent in opposite directions through the fiber, one to Alice and one to Bob. So, Alice now has two photons. The photon whose stateside she wants to send to Bob, and one photon of four entangled pair that she shares with Bob. Alice now takes her two photons and performs a Bell state measurement. Regardless of the initial state of the two photons, this measurement process untangles the two photons and projects them onto one of the foreign Bell state measurement outcomes. It yields two classical bits of information. So, what happens to Bob's photon? Alice's measurement has the remarkable effect of projecting Bob's photon onto one of four disentangled states, depending on the outcome of Alice's Bell measurement. as we can see, the state of Bob's photon is now essentially the same state as Alice's original photon, say, for one of four different rotations corresponding to Alice's for measurement outcomes. To undo these rotations, Alice simply needs to call Bob on the phone and tell him the outcome of her measurement, the two classical bits of information that she gleaned. Bob then performs the necessary inverse rotation and recovers the state of Alice's original photon. So, what did all this buy us? Notice that by implementing this protocol, Alice successfully transferred the quantum state of her photon to Bob 500 kilometers away. However, none of these photons ever had to travel more than 250 kilometers, half the fiber length. since photon loss scales exponentially with length, even cutting the distance in half has dramatically increased the likelihood that the photons will make it through the fiber. we do not need to stop there. we can imagine placing many such sources periodically along the length of the fiber, swapping entanglement pairwise along all of the nodes, and thereby establishing a quantum link between Alice and Bob along which a quantum state can then be teleported. Each node in this network of entangled photon sources and detectors is called a quantum repeater. with each additional quantum repeater, the average distance that each individual photon needs to travel decreases linearly. It, in turn, exponentially decreases the probability of a photon getting lost in the fiber. Thus, although we never amplify the quantum signal, we do prevent it from being lost. Now, there are other challenges associated with building quantum repeaters. As we discuss, the generation of entangled photons is stochastic, and so, entangled photons generally will not arrive at each node simultaneously. Thus, we need a means to store quantum information at each node, effectively a quantum memory, until all entangled pairs are present, and the entire link is ready to be established. we may also want to error correct that memory in order to increase the overall likelihood of success. Although there is still much work to do, quantum repeaters will enable long-distance entanglement distribution in quantum communication. As we just discussed, with only a linear increase in resources, we could exponentially suppress the loss of quantum information over long distances. In the next section, we will discuss more quantum repeaters and their application to quantum networks [66–68].

Long-distance quantum communication is challenging due to photon loss inherent in realistic optical channels. This problem is dealt with classically using amplifiers, known as “repeater stations,” which are interspersed along the transmission channel to compensate for the reduction

in signal power due to loss. Unfortunately, the no-cloning theorem prohibits the amplification of an unknown quantum state, as it would allow for a single photon to be copied into more than one photon carrying the same quantum information. Therefore, classical amplification techniques cannot be used to extend the range over which quantum information can be transmitted.

Optical fibers are made of silica (SiO_2), and it has two leading loss mechanisms which dominate at different wavelengths. At shorter wavelengths, the primary loss mechanism is elastic scattering, in the form of Rayleigh scattering, which can change the propagation direction of the light enough that it escapes the fiber. Alternatively, at longer wavelengths, the dominant loss mechanism is absorption by the material itself. At approximately 1550 nm, the combined loss due to both of these effects is at a minimum of about 0.2 dB/km, a value which is referred to as the attenuation coefficient. Away from this optimal wavelength, the attenuation coefficient increases, defining a “sweet spot” around 1550 nm that is widely used for telecommunications today. It should be noted that the optimal attenuation coefficient for silica of 0.2 dB/km should be thought of as the lower bound for attenuation coefficients found in real fibers where other loss mechanisms such as absorption due to material impurities or fiber bending also contribute to the overall attenuation.

Fiber loss is approximately constant throughout a fiber, so the total attenuation is related to the transmission distance. For context, assuming the optimal attenuation coefficient for silica of 0.2 dB/km, 95% and 1% of the initial signal power remains after a transmission distance of 1km and 100 km, respectively. Unfortunately, the transmitted power scales very poorly with distance, and at 500km (100dB loss), only one in every 10^{10} photons is transmitted through the channel.

A sophisticated approach to overcoming the limits imposed by attenuation and the no-cloning theorem is the “quantum repeater.” Quantum repeaters operate on two entangled states that span consecutive distances of $L/2$, such that, through a process of measurement and entanglement swapping, the final state of the system is a single entangled state which spans the entire distance L . To be more specific, if we have two Bell states which span the $L/2$ distances, then a Bell state measurement on the two collocated qubits in the center along with classical communication of the measurement results to the end stations will result in the entanglement between the two outermost photons which span L . This process can be thought of as the quantum teleportation of a quantum state from the central station to one of the end stations where the initial entanglement of the state is teleported along with it. In general, this process can be nested as many times as needed to span a given initial distance L .

The final entangled state distributed by quantum repeaters can be used as a resource for many quantum communication protocols. For example, this state can now be used to teleport an unknown quantum state over the total distance L in a deterministic fashion. It could be contrasted with direct transmission, which would have only been successful if the photon had not been lost in transit over this entire distance. It is important to note that, in this example, the quantum repeaters have not only allowed for the transmission of a quantum system over a large distance the original aim but have also shifted the problem of probabilistic losses to a part of the protocol, e.g., the entangled-state generation which can be repeated until successful without risking the loss of the unknown state. In realistic quantum repeaters, this will be facilitated by local quantum memories that can store entangled states as they are generated until each node of the quantum link is established.

16 Quantum Repeaters: Applications

In classical communication systems, amplifiers, and the ability to repeat or regenerate, a signal is taken for granted to extend the transmission distance between the sender and receiver. Fundamentally, quantum communication is complicated by the no-cloning theorem for quantum information. It has been leveraged for very useful secure communication in quantum key distribution, or QKD, systems, but it presents a fundamental complication to long-distance quantum communication. QKD systems to date have therefore been limited to a maximum practical distance on the scale of 100 kilometers in optical fiber, far below the global reach of today's classical internet. The goals for communicating quantum information extend far beyond the challenge of increasing the maximum distance of QKD systems. As quantum computers increase in capability, an increasing need to interface and connect these systems is merging. The vision of a quantum internet has been an exciting prospect for the community for a long time, most famously spelled out in a 2008 Nature Review article by Jeff Kimble. On a practical level, protocols from blind quantum computing, which gives the true user and privacy guarantees in a cloud computing model, and distributed quantum computing, which may enable new computational scaling flexibility, require the exchange of quantum information. Within the space of quantum metrology and sensing [69], long-range entanglement can be used as a resource to increase the precision of measurements. The situation is even further complicated because quantum information is often stored in a form that is very hard to transmit in the first place. The superconducting circuit qubit [70] platforms that IBM, among many others, is seeking to develop store quantum information in a microwave state [71, 72] that is only free of a thermal background at extremely low temperatures. Other platforms store such quantum information as electronic or nuclear spins. In all of these cases, the information must first be transduced from the initial state to an optical photon through a quantum state preserving coherent process. Even in systems where direct optical interrogation of the quantum state is possible, such as in trapped ion qubits [73–79], the optical frequency of the atomic transitions rarely matches with the required frequencies for free space or fiber communication and must be converted for transmission. The high state-energy, weak light-matter interaction in existing telecommunication infrastructure makes optical photons ideal carriers of quantum information. However, optical photons still suffer exponential loss in transmission, as described by the Beer-Lambert Law. In the absence of amplification, we can expect the error rate of transmission to increase exponentially with the distance of transmission. Technological limits, such as the dark count rate of the receiving single-photon detector, will set a maximum transmission distance for quantum information. To avoid these limitations, Knill and Laflamme introduced the first quantum computer proposal in 1996, based on the concepts of quantum error correction. Here, an intermediate node, analogous to classical communication amplifier, could be used to restore the received quantum information for retransmission. However, the constraint of the no-cloning theorem places a hard boundary at 50% maximum link loss between repeater nodes. If we revisit the problem of attenuation and transmission of optical photons, there is a very inconvenient case. Even with that 0.2 dB per kilometer loss of modern optical fiber, the maximum distance between repeaters would be limited 15 kilometers in the most optimal case. In 1998, the authors of the BDCZ Proposal introduced a landmark quantum repeater protocol with three key elements. First, it used two-way communication between nodes to achieve entanglement purification, even when using imperfect components. Second, the protocol supported swapping the intermediate nodes and entanglement in a nested protocol to entangle the endpoints. Third, the computational resources required that each node had a modest scaling with the transmission distance. In this scheme, the goal is to establish entanglement between two remote nodes to be used as a resource for any communication, computation, or measurement application. The challenge in all of this is the requirement that the quantum

computer nodes contain a quantum memory that remains coherent over the total communication latency needed to establish the entanglement. The magnitude of this quantum memory challenge resulted in an alternative proposal in 2001 known as the DLCZ Protocol. In this scheme, atomic ensembles are used as the long-coherence memory and entangled by measuring the emitted photons from an optical ray pulse through a beam splitter [80]. These neighboring ensembles can then be entangled by sending a read pulse and measuring the emitted photons through a beam splitter, as before. At that time, ultra-cold atom systems were the only known implementation. Nevertheless, recent progress has extended this concept to rare-earth ions and crystals to form a solid-state memory that can be leveraged as a resource for a quantum repeater. Still, many technical challenges remain for a DLCZ-based link to offer an improved endpoint entanglement rate relative to direct transmission. As the field of quantum information science has matured over the past two decades, the theoretical requirements for a BDCZ-based quantum repeater protocol have been reduced. At the same time, the capabilities of existing hardware systems have increased. Today, robust quantum repeater protocols can support a fixed resource per node on the order of 100 qubits, with memory coherence times that are on the order of 100 milliseconds. Systems of this order are not far from what can be envisioned with a foreseeable roadmap of quantum computing systems. As such, a practical quantum repeater demonstration is now being discussed as the next achievable milestone in quantum information science [81].

The secure communication of information on a global scale is fundamental to our digital world. As we have seen throughout contemporary encryption methods used to communicate information generally rely on an assortment of mathematical constructs that are presumed to be hard to compromise using available computational resources. As such, these conventional protocols are generally not proven to be perfectly secure. Rather, they are constructed to offer acceptable levels of security based on reasonable assumptions surrounding the mathematical problems and computing power available today [82]. Alternatively, the various quantum key distribution (QKD) protocols offer the promise of communication with quantum-enhanced levels of randomness and security.

In QKD, two distant users generate a shared random bit string, referred to as a secret key, which can subsequently be used to encrypt a message using a symmetric-key protocol. The key generation process generally involves one user preparing quantum states of light and transmitting them to the other user, who then measures them. Subsequently, they compare what was sent versus what was measured via classical communication channels. Attempts to eavesdrop on the transmitted states will disturb the measured results in a detectable manner, enhancing the protocol's security.

A major drawback of current QKD implementations is its relatively limited operational distance compared with conventional classical-communication methods. For example, QKD realizations based on single or few-photon quantum states are limited to operational distances of at most a few hundred kilometers to retain any notion of a practical communication rate. Due to the exponential scaling of photon loss with distance relevant for both free-space atmospheric links and optical fiber links, a problem is generally addressed using distributed amplification in conventional classical communication schemes. In the quantum setting, however, conventional amplification is not an option due to the no-cloning theorem.

One possibility for overcoming photon loss in QKD systems is to use quantum repeaters. Quantum repeaters improve the rate-loss scaling of long-distance quantum communication by converting the problem of distributing a single quantum state over a long distance into one of distributing several quantum states over shorter distances and then coordinating them to create a long-distance quantum link. While quantum repeater research is progressing, many engineering challenges remain to be addressed before quantum repeaters will be ready for practical deploy-

ment.

In the context of free-space communication, the use of a satellite or a constellation of satellites as an intermediary between ground stations affords an improvement over solely terrestrial free-space communication. In these schemes, a ground-based station communicates first with a satellite orbiting the Earth. Although the overall distance from the ground station to the satellite remains considerable (several hundred to thousands of kilometers), the thinning of the atmosphere with altitude means that loss due to atmospheric turbulence and absorption decreases rapidly with distance. It significantly limits the overall loss compared with manifestly terrestrial free-space links of the same distance. Once the quantum information is at a satellite, it can then be passed between other orbiting satellites (e.g., as in a repeater scheme) with much lower loss before being transmitted back to Earth. Further, the use of satellites enables the option of having the satellite implement the QKD protocol based on keys shared independently with each ground station. For example, once a satellite establishes independent keys with each ground station, it can encrypt and transmit a shared key to both locations.

In 2016, China launched the satellite 'Micius' with the primary purpose of performing quantum information science demonstrations [68]. Micius orbits the Earth at an altitude of 500 km and a speed of 7.6 km/s. Since its launch, Micius has been used to demonstrate QKD at kHz rates over satellite-to-ground distances of 1200 km. Originating the QKD protocol at the satellite, as opposed to the ground stations, is because of atmospheric turbulence. Turbulence causes "beam wandering," the redirection of an optical beam due to passage through a turbulent atmosphere, and such atmospheric turbulence is largest near the surface of the Earth. Since a beam naturally broadens as it propagates, the wandering is a proportionately smaller effect if it occurs once the beam has already broadened (rather than while it is tightly confined at the source with a long distance still to go). For context, the beam used to communicate with Micius broadens to a diameter of 12 m after traveling 1200 km.

Micius has also been used to demonstrate QKD between two different ground stations simultaneously, one in Europe and one in China, separated by 7600 km on the Earth. Then, as described above, the satellite could use these two independent QKD sessions to create a shared secret key between the two ground stations, thereby performing intercontinental quantum communication. Finally, the shared key was used to seed a conventional AES (advanced encryption standard) protocol with 128 bits in order to perform 75 minutes of encrypted video conferencing between Europe and China, consuming a total of 70 kB of the shared key.

The Micius experiments definitively demonstrate that a global communications network based on QKD-enhanced key exchange is possible. However, many challenges remain before satellite QKD becomes practical; in particular, the need to increase communication rates from the kilohertz range to more practically useful levels.

17 QKD: Practical Issues and Challenges

In section two, we discussed quantum key distribution, or QKD, in which the BB84, Ekert 91, and BBN92 protocols were explained. All of these protocols enable two remote users, Alice and Bob, to accumulate a shared string of random bits while precluding an eavesdropper, known as Eve, from learning anything about those bits. Randomness, as we discussed, is a valuable resource. Shared randomness, in particular, is of great value for secure communication because, as we have also seen, it enables Alice and Bob to communicate in complete secrecy employing one-time pad encryption and decryption. It is especially important because the advent of quantum computers with their possibility of running Shor's factoring algorithm will break the RSA public

key infrastructure on which internet commerce relies. Thus, it should come as no surprise that QKD systems are now commercially available and that QKD networks have been demonstrated in the United States [83], Canada [84], Europe [85], and Japan [86]. One is entering a large scale deployment in China. Nevertheless, there is a host of issues related to QKD that awaits a solution before one-time pad communication becomes the norm. These include providing security against quantum hacking, increasing the distance over which QKD can be accomplished, and increasing the rate at which the secret key can be accumulated. QKD security proofs generally guarantee the security of the protocol, not its hardware implementation. It leaves open the possibility of quantum hacking, in which Eve exploits equipment vulnerabilities to break the protocol by gaining partial or complete information about Alice and Bob's key. In BB84, for example, Alice sends bits at the single-photon level to Bob, who performs polarization analysis on them using single-photon detectors. In a blinding attack, Eve illuminates Bob with laser pulses that enable her to control which detector will click, hence giving her what she needs to obtain information about the key. Measurement device-independent QKD eliminates Alice and Bob's vulnerability to photodetector hacking but at the expense of some implementation complications not present in BB84. More generally, anticipating all possible hacking attacks on a particular QKD implementation can be a daunting task. The exception is device-independent QKD, a protocol based on the Bell inequality, which makes no assumptions about the functioning of the equipment used in its implementation. The price paid for this immunity, however, is severe. Device-independent QKD's predicted secret key rate is far below what BB84 affords. Its maximum distance of operation is much shorter than what BB84 offers. The distance over which a QKD system operates, and the secret key rate that it provides at that distance, are quintessential figures of merit. If an optical fiber links Alice and Bob with no intervening equipment, then a BB84 system in which Alice sends single photons at a rate of R per second, and Bob has a perfect single-photon detector, gives a secret key rate in bits per second that is proportional to R times the fraction of Alice's photons that reach Bob. For standard low loss fiber, that fraction is 10% at a 50-kilometer distance. 1% at 100 kilometers. 10-billionths of a percent at 500 kilometers. A direct fiber connection between Alice and Bob will not do for transcontinental or intercontinental QKD. One approach to reaching such distances is to employ quantum repeaters. Let us see how this can be done. Suppose Alice and Bob each have entanglement sources that produce a pair of polarization-entangled signal and idler photons. That Alice and Bob each send their signal photons to a repeater station while retaining their idler photons in quantum memories. The repeater station performs a Bell state measurement on the signal photons it receives and then uses a classical link to communicate that measurement outcome either 00, 01, 10, or 11 to Alice and Bob. They then will know that their stored idler photons are in a particular polarization-entangled state. This operation, called entanglement swapping, performed over a chain of such repeater stations can distribute entanglement and hence enable QKD between much longer distances than is practical with a direct fiber connection. Making such a repeater chain practical requires substantial technology developments in quantum memories and quantum processors. Hence, an alternative approach to long-distance QKD, the use of quantum satellites recently demonstrated by China, is worth considering. Putting aside for now extending the reach of QKD beyond metropolitan area distances, let us address the secret key rates that can be achieved within that more limited operational range. The state of the art is a BB84 system that provides a megabit per second class secret key rate over 50 kilometers of optical fiber. However, is this enough? For one-time pad encryption of large files to be transmitted at internet speeds, gigabit per second secret key rates should be available. To push the record-setting BB84 system to such rates at 50-kilometer range would require increasing its clock rate by a factor of 10 and multiplexing 100 wavelength channels, all operating at that increased clock rate. Next, we will look at a new QKD protocol for reaching gigabit per second secret key rates in a metropolitan

area setting with a substantially lower implementation burden than 100 channel BB84.

18 Floodlight QKD

In this section, we will continue the discussion of QKD. specifically, why BB84 and the other QKD protocols we have seen are incapable of a gigabit per second secret key rates at metropolitan area distances unless they use massive amounts of wavelength division multiplexing. we will also look at a new protocol that offers such performance without any multiplexing. To begin, however, let us explain how classical fiber optic communication easily achieves multi-gigabyte per second rates over such distances in single wavelength operation, and why those approaches are unavailable for BB84. Remember that without quantum repeaters, only 10% of the BB84 light is entering 50 kilometers long, and low-loss optical fiber will emerge from that far end. for 100 kilometers long fiber, that fraction drops to 1%. Classical communication systems overcome these losses by transmitting many photons per bit and using an optical amplifier when necessary to boost signal strength. BB84, like all QKD protocols, must be secure against an all-powerful Eve, which includes an Eve who collects all the light lost in propagation from Alice to Bob but does nothing that affects the light reaching Bob. Alice's transmitting her BB84 bits at the single-photon level offers protection against this passive eavesdropper, because quantum mechanics No-Cloning Theorem precludes Eve from perfectly duplicating Alice's photons. No Cloning, unfortunately, also impacts Bob, who is unable to noiselessly boost the signals he receives from Alice, because amplified, spontaneous emission noise will unavoidably be present in his amplifier's output. Floodlight QKD is a new protocol, in which Alice transmits many photons per bit, and Bob uses an optical amplifier [87]. However, it is immune to passive eavesdropping and is capable of a gigabit per second, secret key rates at metropolitan area distances in single wavelength operation. Floodlight QKD, unlike BB84, is a two-way protocol. Alice first sends unmodulated light to Bob. Bob encodes a random bit string on the light he receives, then amplifies that light, and sends it back to Alice for decoding. In particular, Alice uses an optical amplifier to produce terahertz bandwidth, high brightness, Amplified Spontaneous Emission light, containing tens of thousands of photons per second per hertz of optical bandwidth. She splits off a tiny fraction of that ASE light containing, on average, less than one photon per second per hertz of optical bandwidth. She transmits it to Bob while retaining the high brightness remainder in optical fiber for decoding the light she will receive from Bob. Bob imposes his random bit string on the light he receives at a multi-gigabit per second rate employing binary phase-shift keying, in which 0's and 1s are represented by 0 and π radian phase shifts. Bob amplifies his modulated light to overcome propagation loss on the return path to Alice, which has the added benefit of bearing that amplified, modulated light in his amplifier's high brightness, ASE noise. Nevertheless, Alice can successfully recover Bob's bit string by a coherent detection process in which he beats the light she receives from him against the ASE light she has stored on a conventional linear mode photodiode. That coherent detection affords Alice a processing gains equal to the product of our ASE light's optical bandwidth and Bob's bit time. Eve, operating as a passive eavesdropper, cannot decode Bob's bit string. The light she collected from the Alice-to-Bob channel is too low brightness for coherent detection to work, and the No Cloning Theorem forbids her from faithfully converting it to a high-brightness replica. Let us put some numbers together. Suppose that a pair of 50-kilometer-long optical fibers connect Alice and Bob. Alice sends 2 terahertz bandwidth light to Bob, and Bob uses 10 gigabits per second modulation, and a 40 decibel gain optical amplifier. Then, Alice is sending 20 photons for each of Bob's bit times at of brightness of 1/10th of a photon per second per hertz of optical bandwidth. Although Alice receives 2,000 photons of modulated light per bit embedded in 20,000 ASE photons per

bit, her 200-fold processing gain, $1/10$ th nanosecond times 2 terahertz of bandwidth, makes that effectively 2,000 signal photons embedded in 100 ASE photons. There is, unfortunately, a very definite fly in the preceding QKD ointment. Because Floodlight QKD is a two-way protocol, Eve can inject her own broadband, low-brightness light into Bob's terminal, while retaining a suitable high-brightness reference for decoding Bob's modulation of her light, despite its being buried in the ASE from Bob's amplifier. To defeat this active eavesdropping attack, Alice and Bob perform a channel monitoring operation, in which they rely on the photon pairing mission from a spontaneous parametric down converter. Alice has that source and multiplexes its signal beam output in with the ASE she is transmitting to Bob while recording time-tagged values of idle or photon detections. Bob taps a small portion of the light he receives from Alice and records the time tag values of his photon detections. By sharing their photon detection times, Alice and Bob can calculate the fraction of light entering Bob's terminal that was due to Eve, and thus determine how much secret information they can safely distill. Where is floodlight QKD now? Tabletop demonstration of Floodlight QKD has demonstrated 1.3 gigabits per second secret key rate through a channel with attenuation that was equivalent to 50 kilometers of optical fiber. Work is continuing on both the theory and experiment of Floodlight QKD, with major tasks on the agenda being bringing the current security level up from a collective attack to the ultimate coherent attack and implementing the protocol on a deployed metropolitan area scale fiber. FL-QKD is immune to a passive-eavesdropping attack. This immunity arises from the high number of photons transmitted per bit over a more significant number of optical modes as compared to other QKD protocols, which transmit no more than one photon per bit. If we want to know more about FL-QKD, we encourage to go through this paper [87].

19 QKD: Implementation Challenges and Potential Solutions

The end goal of quantum key distribution, or QKD, is to establish a shared list of random numbers that can be used for encryption. This list of random numbers is called a key. After a successful QKD session, the transmitter, Alice, and the receiver, Bob, should end up with identical copies of the key. At the same time, an eavesdropper, Eve, should have no information about the random numbers in the key. One way to assess the performance of a QKD system is to look at its secret key rate, that is, how quickly the secret random numbers are shared in units of bits per second. The required secret key rate depends on the encryption algorithm that will use the keys and the desired rate of secure communication [88]. The holy grail of secure communication is the one-time pad, an encryption algorithm that is mathematically proven secure. Even if Eve had the most powerful supercomputer in the world, or even if she had a quantum computer, she would not be able to crack the one-time pad. However, the one-time pad is a challenging encryption scheme to use because it consumes one bit of the secret key for each bit of the message to be encrypted. The secret keys cannot be reused. There are many different implementations of QKD transmitters and receivers. In general, the hardware limits how quickly the transmitter can produce quantum states and how quickly the receiver can detect them. For example, it might take a finite amount of time to prepare a quantum state. Alternatively, after a receiver detects a photon, it might take a finite amount of time to reset the receiver and prepare it to detect another photon. As a result, both the transmitter and receiver place limits on the achievable secret key rate. The secret key rate is also strongly affected by the quantum channel. A crucial issue that affects every real-world QKD system is the loss in the quantum channel. Because of loss, only a fraction of Alice's transmitted photons will reach

Bob's receiver. The value of the fraction depends on the properties of the quantum channel. One of the most common channels is an optical fiber. For example, an illustration of an optical fiber link between Lincoln Laboratory and MIT is used for quantum communication experiments. Over an optical fiber, the probability of successful photon transmission decreases exponentially as the fiber gets longer. For example, if the quantum channel is 50 kilometers of standard optical fiber, we would expect only 10% of the transmitted photons to reach the receiver. If the fiber length is doubled from 50 kilometers to 100 kilometers, then the transmission is reduced from 10% to 1%. These are the ideal transmission values for those fiber lengths, but real-world fiber optic links tend to have lower than ideal transmission. Our 43-kilometer fiber has between 2 and 1/2% and 5% transmission. In classical optical fiber communication, a decrease in transmission can be overcome by optically amplifying the signal. However, optical amplifiers cannot be used in quantum communication and QKD. Because according to the laws of quantum mechanics, it is impossible to make a perfect copy of a quantum state. It means that the transmission of the quantum channel fundamentally limits the achievable secret key rate. Many researchers are working on new technologies that can overcome this limitation, but a practical solution is still a few years away. In the meantime, QKD researchers are investigating different strategies to increase secret key rates using currently available technology. One strategy is to take advantage of the properties of optical fiber. A single optical fiber can guide many different wavelengths, or colors, of light at the same time. Alice and Bob could raise their secret key rate by running several QKD systems simultaneously, with each system operating at a unique wavelength. Using a technique called wavelength division multiplexing, Alice can combine the quantum outputs of all of her transmitters onto the same optical fiber, and Bob can separate the quantum signals so that a separate receiver detects each wavelength. The resulting secret key rate scales linearly with the number of multiplex systems. Two systems would result in double the secret key rate of a single system, and four systems would quadruple the rate of the single system, and so on. The drawback of this strategy is that we need multiple transmitters and multiple receivers. It could be challenging if we are operating under constraints on the available size, weight, power consumption, or cost of the system. Another strategy involves changing the way the photons are used to carry information. We have discussed encoding information in a photon's polarization state. For example, horizontal polarization could correspond to bit value zero, and vertical polarization could correspond to bit value one. Because there are two possible bit values, 0 and 1, the polarization encoded photon could contribute at most one bit of information to the secret key. It would be useful if there were a way to encode information in photonic states and get more than one bit of information from a single photon. It is called high dimensional encoding. As an example, if a photon could be in one of four possible states with bit values 0 0, 0 1, 1 0, and 1 1, then that photon could carry up to two bits of information. However, on a given basis, there are only two possible polarization states. So, instead of using polarization, Alice and Bob need to encode information in the photon's different properties. Several properties can be used, but not all of them are compatible with optical fiber channels. For example, a popular research area is encoding more than one bit of information using what is called the orbital angular momentum modes of a photon. However, those modes cannot be easily transmitted over optical fiber. Instead, for a fiber-compatible, high-dimensional encoding scheme [89], the transmitter can prepare the photon by putting it in one of many different time slots. The receiver can detect which time slot had the photon in it. Each time slot corresponds to a different bit value, and the total number of time slots determines the number of bits of information that each photon could carry. Four-time slots correspond to two bits per photon, eight time slots correspond to three bits, 16-time slots correspond to four bits, and so on. The more possible time slots there are per photon, the fewer possible photons can be transmitted per second. That is, there is a trade-off between how much information a photon can carry and how many photons can be transmitted

per second. It is useful because, as discussed earlier, there is often a mismatch between the transmitter and receiver. So, the transmitter can produce quantum states much more quickly than the receiver can detect them. The photons that are not detected and the information that they carry are wasted and cannot contribute to this shared key. This high dimensional time slot scheme encodes the same amount of information into a smaller number of photons, which makes this scheme especially useful when the receiver is saturated. Practically speaking, this often happens over metropolitan area distances of a few tens of kilometers. There is a potential drawback to using high dimensional encoding for QKD. The transmitter and receiver become more complex compared to a binary encoded system. Depending on the situation, the potential gain in the secret key rate could be worth the additional complexity. We have discussed the constraints on the secret key rate achievable by a QKD system and about strategies to increase the secret key rate under those constraints. There is no single best QKD system or strategy that covers all operation scenarios. The most important point is that the optimal system and strategy depend heavily on the available hardware and the channel properties.

20 Entanglement as a Physical Resource

In this section and previously, we have seen how quantum entanglement is used as a resource for various aspects of quantum communication, from key distribution to random number generation to quantum repeaters. In this deep dive, we will explore the resource model of quantum entanglement. We will start by asking what it means for entanglement to be a resource, both at an intuitive level, as well as in mathematical terms. We will then provide a general definition of entanglement and introduce mathematical measures, the entropy, and the Schmidt number that quantify the degree of entanglement in a given system. Lastly, we will show that entanglement is fungible. That is, entangled bipartite pure states are asymptotically equivalent and, therefore, constitute a physical resource. So, with that brief introduction, let us discuss about the resource model of quantum information theory and quantum entanglement. Space, time, and energy are fundamental physical resources. Does quantum information theory introduce additional such resources? For example, we have seen how noisy classical channels may provide a correlation between the two signals, x , and y . Shared classical randomness is known to be useful for cryptography. Might noisy quantum channels also be resources? Could entangled quantum states be resources? Well, let us see what entanglement may be useful. We have seen that teleportation [90] may be utilized to turn one entangled pair, called an ebit, plus two classical bits into the ability to communicate one quantum bit. Such conversion is not possible without entanglement. Another well-known protocol is superdense coding by which an ebit and one qubit are used to communicate two classical bits. Entangled quantum states are also known to be useful for clock synchronization, distributed quantum computation, and cryptography, such as quantum key distribution. Entanglement may also sometimes replace classical shared randomness. So, given that entanglement is useful, the problem is, is entanglement a resource, and by this, we mean a formal mathematical definition of resource? For example, here are two entangled states, $|00\rangle + |11\rangle$ versus $0.9 \sqrt{0.01} |00\rangle + 0.1 \sqrt{1.1} |11\rangle$. How are these the same or different? After all, one cannot have different kinds of resources for different states. For entanglement to be a resource, there must be a way to convert between states of different qualities of entanglement. One strict criterion for a definition of a resource is to say that A and B are equivalent if there is a mechanism to convert from A to B and from B to A. Does this apply to entangled states? In fact, yes, to some degree. A state ψ and another ϕ , which are pure bipartite states, are equivalent under local operations and classical communication [91], that is, operations which do not create entanglement, if and only if ψ majorizes ϕ and ϕ also majorizes ψ . Here, ψ and ϕ

are the Schmidt decomposition coefficients of the pure bipartite states. Equivalently, the eigenvalues of the reduced density matrices of ψ and ϕ for one side or another must be the same. It is a fine criterion, but it is too strict because it means that we would have many different categories of entanglement. A better approach utilizes a broader concept for what a resource is. It is an asymptotic equivalence. For example, currency, such as dollars and the English pound, are considered equivalent, because they may be converted to each other at a constant rate with a fixed fee. We capture this idea mathematically with the following definition, saying that A and B are asymptotically equivalent, if there exists a conversion rate that is a ratio, which we will call R, such that for some ϵ and δ greater than 0, there exists a size n such that when the amount being converted is larger than capital N, we have a procedure which takes n times R plus δ copies of A and returns n copies of B and n copies of B may be converted to n times R minus δ copies of A. These conversions should be possible with an error less than ϵ . Think of R as being the exchange rate and δ as being the fee. This model works for many resources. Does it work for entanglement? Do entangled states have a well-defined notion of asymptotic equivalence? Let us find out.

21 Entanglement - Definition and Measures

Let us define quantum entanglement and how entanglement may be quantitatively measured. For a pure state ψ AB, a composite state of two systems A and B, we say that ψ is entangled if and only if there does not exist a pure state ϕ of A and χ of B, such that ψ of A and B is the tensor product of ϕ A and χ B. Entanglement is more than just a binary state, however. There are measures that quantify how entangled a given state is. The most important of these is the entropy. Let ρ sub-A be the trace over B of the bipartite AB system. The entanglement of ψ AB is defined as the Von Neumann entropy of this reduced density matrix on A or the reduced density matrix on B. This is called The Entanglement, with a capital E because of how important this measure is. For example, consider the bipartite state 0-0 plus 1-1. The density matrix of this state is a familiar quantity, which has four 1/2 values in the corners. The reduced density matrix is the identity matrix divided by 2, and thus the entropy is one bit, and the entanglement is, therefore, one ebit. We will see this defines an ebit. Another useful measure is the Schmidt number. It is the number of non-zero coefficients that appear in the Schmidt decomposition of a bipartite pure state. More explicitly for ψ AB, this means we take the Schmidt decomposition, which is a sum over square root λ times K sub-A, K sub-B, where the square root of λ sub K is the Schmidt coefficient. For example, consider two ebits of the form 0-0 plus 1-1. Let us expand this, keeping A in blue and B in orange. When we expand this product, we end up with the A and B labels all mixed up. This is a very inconvenient representation. So, let us collect all the A terms together and all the B terms together. That gives us 0-0 0-0 plus 0-1 0-1 plus 1-0 1-0 plus 1-1 1-1. this is conveniently represented by taking x to be an integer from 0 to 3, and it is a sum of x x. The Schmidt number for this state is 4. this representation, a sum over x of x x, is a general and very useful representation for maximally entangled states.

22 The Fungibility of Entanglement

we now show that quantum entanglement can be thought of as a physical resource, in the sense of this claim. we claim that all entangled bipartite pure states are asymptotically equivalent. Different forms of entanglement are fungible. we may prove this claim by showing there is a gold standard for entanglement. we will use the state 00 plus 11. Specifically, there are two

parts to the argument. First, is entanglement concentration. There must exist a mechanism to take n copies of a partially entangled state ψ and turn them into a smaller number of good standard states, which we will call ϕ , capital ϕ . In particular, we will show that concentration produces N times E of ψ minus δ of these states' ϕ . The second part of the argument is entanglement dilution. we start with N times E of ψ plus δ copies of the maximum entangled state. obtain n copies of the less entangled state. These protocols will work with ϵ - δ parameters greater than zero, and in the asymptotic limit of sufficiently large N . ϵ , here is the probability of error of the protocol. Let us first look at the concentration. Without loss of generality, we may take the state ψ as being a bipartite state with coefficients $1 - \phi$ square root 00 , and the square root of P , 11 . This is the form provided by the Schmidt Decomposition. Recall that the entanglement of this state ψ is given by the Von Neumann entropy of the reduced density matrix of half of this state. we find this is nothing more than the binary entropy of P , which we have seen several times. What we need from concentration is to be able to take n copies of the state ψ into approximately E of ψ copies of the maximum entangled state. δ here will be the ϕ that is paid to be able to create these EPR pairs. Since the protocol uses N copies of ψ , let us explicitly write out this tensor product of N copies. we may express this tensor product using a binomial expansion where each of the usual binomial coefficients multiplies the term x^k . Here, the absolute value of x denotes the number of ones in the binary string x . Let us rewrite using the number of ones as w , giving us a slightly simpler expression where we may take into account that there are multiple values of x with the same weight w . The superposition of all of the states with the same weight, w , is useful to define. Here we give that the name s_w and normalize it properly by the number of possibilities that is the square root of $\binom{n}{w}$. Each s_w state is a maximally entangled state in a Hilbert space of dimension $\binom{n}{w}$. Meaning equivalently, $\log \binom{n}{w}$ chooses w E bits. What we have, though, is not a single s_w state, but rather with side ψ to the n , a superposition over a variety of s_w states. Each with an amplitude with a form, which has a binomial coefficient, as shown here. This superposition of maximally entangled states is quite useful, despite the different sizes. that is because we may obtain one of them simply by following this procedure, Alice and Bob, A and B, both independently measure w , the Hamming weight of the strings that they have. This collapses the superposition into a single s_w requiring no communication between the two parties. The probability of a given weight is $\binom{n}{w} p^w (1-p)^{n-w}$. this is approximately Gaussian for large n . The mean value of w obtained is n times p . and the variance is $n p (1-p)$. The average number of entangled pairs obtained is the log of $\binom{n}{w} p^w (1-p)^{n-w}$, which is approximately the binary entropy of p . this is nothing more than n times e , the entanglement. To be a little more precise, we do not get exactly nE , but rather nE minus some overhead, which goes something like the width of the variance that is the square root of n . this determines our overhead ϕ cost δ . Choosing δ to go as $1/\sqrt{n}$, thus allowing us to obtain a final protocol, which succeeds in producing approximately n times e minus δ EPR pairs with high probability. This completes the argument for part one of the proof. The second part of the proof requires that we go in the opposite direction to dilute a given number of EPR pairs. Specifically, n times e plus δ of these EPR pairs into n copies of ψ . we want to turn ebits into arbitrating bipartite entangled states. An elegant way to do this uses teleportation. One party, say, Alice. Starts by generating n copies of the state ψ locally, in her own apparatus. Remember, this is a bipartite state. She takes half of this state n qubits and compresses it to produce using Schumacher compression. For example, an output that has approximately nE qubits. Here, the δ is the overhead required for the compression. Separately, Bob shown here in purple produces n perfect EPR pairs. Perhaps with a little overhead δ , Bob, who holds this entangled state, then sends half of those qubits that are approximately nE qubits over to Alice. Alice performs

a Bell basis measurement between the compressed state and this half of the EPR pairs, sends the classical measurement result to Bob. He fixes up the other half of the EPR pairs using the normal teleportation protocol. remember, there are nE of these qubits. Decompresses with the reverse of the Schumacher compression, obtaining a state with n qubits. Altogether then, what Bob and Alice have is with high probability n copies of the state ψ_{ab} . For this protocol, the fixed parameter is δ . The overhead and ϵ the error is determined by the Schumacher compression and decompression steps. This completes part two of the proof. Thus, now we have the full proof providing a foundation for conceptually understanding how entangled bipartite pure states a physical resource is, which are fungible and may hold quantifiable intrinsic value.

7. CHSH-type Game: Classical Approach; In the CHSH-type game, Alice and Bob are spatially separated from each other from the time that the game starts until it is over, and they cannot communicate. The game starts when the referee randomly selects two bits, a and b , and sends a to Alice and b to Bob. Alice and Bob then return values x or y for the bits x and y . After receiving the values for bits x and y , the referee determines if the input and output bits satisfy the condition

$$x \oplus y = ab. \tag{68}$$

If the condition is satisfied, then Alice and Bob win; otherwise, they lose. Their goal is to find the best strategy that maximizes their likelihood of winning the game, and this depends on how they choose their bit values $x_{0,1}$ and $y_{0,1}$. Note that we do not specify which of $x_{0,1}$ and M take on value 0 or 1. That assignment is the strategy that Alice and Bob must find.

In the classical deterministic case, Alice agrees to output the bit value $x = x_0$ when M , and M when M . Similarly, Bob agrees to output the bit value M when M , and M when M . The table below shows the different possibilities of the game for the possible values of a and b .

Table 2: Different possibilities of the game for the possible values of a and b

a	b	ab	$x \oplus y$
0	0	0	$x_0 \oplus y_0$
0	1	0	$x_0 \oplus y_1$
1	0	0	$x_1 \oplus y_0$
1	1	1	$x_1 \oplus y_1$

When $a = 0$, Alice outputs x_0 . However, there is no way to infer from the table that Alice has assigned $x_0 = 0$ and $x_1 = 1$, or visa versa.

8. CHSH-type Game: Quantum Approach; In the CHSH-type game, Alice and Bob are spatially separated from each other from the time that the game starts until it is over, and they cannot communicate. The game starts when the referee randomly selects two bits, a and b , and sends a to Alice and b to Bob. Alice and Bob then return values x or y for the bits x and y . After receiving the values for bits x and y , the referee determines if the input and output bits satisfy the condition

$$x \oplus y = ab. \tag{69}$$

If the condition is satisfied, then Alice and Bob win. Otherwise, they lose. Their goal is to find the best strategy that maximizes their likelihood of winning the game, [92] and this depends on how they choose their bit values $x_{0,1}$ and $y_{0,1}$. Note that we do not specify which of $x_{0,1}$ and $y_{0,1}$ take on value 0 or 1. That assignment is the strategy that Alice and Bob must find.

In the quantum version of the CHSH game, Alice and Bob start with a shared quantum state, for example, a Bell state:

$$\frac{|0_A 1_B\rangle + |1_A 0_B\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}. \quad (70)$$

In order to maximize their likelihood of winning, Alice and Bob must decide how they will perform measurements on this state and how the results of those measurements will determine the bit values $x_{0,1}$ and $y_{0,1}$ that they will return to the referee.

In general, if Alice receives the bit $a = 0$, she measures in the basis expanded by the states

$$\begin{aligned} |\psi_{A,0}\rangle &= \cos(\theta_{A,0}) |0_A\rangle + \sin(\theta_{A,0}) e^{i\phi_{A,0}} |1_A\rangle \\ |\psi_{A,0}^\perp\rangle &= \sin(\theta_{A,0}) |0_A\rangle - \cos(\theta_{A,0}) e^{-i\phi_{A,0}} |1_A\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (71)$$

where $\theta_{A,0}$ and $\phi_{A,0}$ are the angles that define the states in the Bloch sphere.

If she receives the bit $a = 1$, she measures in the basis spanned by the states

$$\begin{aligned} |\psi_{A,1}\rangle &= \cos(\theta_{A,1}) |0_A\rangle + \sin(\theta_{A,1}) e^{i\phi_{A,1}} |1_A\rangle \\ |\psi_{A,1}^\perp\rangle &= \sin(\theta_{A,1}) |0_A\rangle - \cos(\theta_{A,1}) e^{-i\phi_{A,1}} |1_A\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (72)$$

9. When Bob receives the bit $b = 0$ or $b = 1$, he measures in one of the two bases spanned by analogous states as Alice's states above.

Solution:

Alice and Bob are not constrained to always measure on the same basis. , their best strategy in the quantum case is to measure in different bases.

10. Entanglement: Definition and Measures; Regarding the quantification of entanglement. Solution:

Quantum entanglement is not a binary quantity, meaning that it is not just zero or one (if we normalize it), but it can also take values in between. For a product state as $|0\rangle_A|0\rangle_B$ is zero, and for a Bell state $\frac{|0\rangle_A|0\rangle_B + |1\rangle_A|1\rangle_B}{\sqrt{2}}$ is maximal. However, for an arbitrary state

$$\alpha|0\rangle_A|0\rangle_B + \beta|0\rangle_A|1\rangle + \gamma|1\rangle|0\rangle + \delta|1\rangle|1\rangle,$$

it can take continuous values in between depending on the parameters $\alpha, \beta, \gamma,$ and δ .

Figure 8: QKD Issues and Challenges

23 Introduction to NISQ and Short-depth Quantum Circuits

In this section, we will look at the practical challenges and opportunities faced when implementing realistic quantum algorithms on the hardware that is available today [93]. As we have seen throughout the section, the promise of quantum computing centers on finding quantum advantage for useful, meaningful problems that do not currently have a known fast [94], and one for which a fast quantum algorithm exists. In sections one and two, we looked at several examples, such as Shor’s algorithm, the simulation of quantum chemistry and quantum materials [95] in optimization problems [96]. In all of these cases, we assumed that we had perfect qubits. However, as we now know, the physical qubits we have today are far from perfect. They are subject to noise, and the noise reduces the overall gate fidelity, limiting the number of gates that one can perform before quantum information is lost [1]. Furthermore, as we will see in section four, the path forward is to implement fault-tolerant quantum error correction [63, 97–99]. Basically, by adding additional qubits, we can achieve system resilience through hardware redundancy. With error-protected logical qubits, we can envision making fault-tolerant circuits with arbitrarily large complexity. Now, that is fine, but at the current error rates we have today, even for the leading qubit modalities, it would require around 1,000 physical qubits to error-protect a single logical qubit [100]. This line of work certainly needs to be done, and it will be, but still, several years before we have fault-tolerant error-corrected systems. Furthermore, that is the subject of section four. For now, and over the next several years, we will have quantum computing testbeds with a few hundred to a few thousand noisy physical qubits that are not fully error corrected. The question is, what useful, commercialize tasks can we perform with these types of computers? This is a very important question because we know from experience, much like with classical digital computers, that the investment required to push the technology development that enables scaling to larger sizes, that this requires a commercial product and revenue stream to supplement government investments. The revenue from this generation of quantum computers would be used to push the next node and enable better performance in the next generation, which in turn generates more revenue. Furthermore, this virtuous cycle continues. The status today is that we have known useful algorithms that require many more qubits than we currently have in practice. The question is, are there near-term applications that solve real-world problems using noisy, intermediate-scale quantum computers, or NISQ computers [27]. It is currently an area of active research and is growing rapidly due to the need to find such applications. There is certainly hope that smaller-scale quantum computers, working as a co-processor for a classical computer, may provide a quantum advantage for certain types of problems in machine learning [101], simulation, optimization, or quantum dynamics. However, the reality is, we just do not know yet, because we are just getting started. Getting 50 to 100 qubit testbeds online so that computer scientists can start playing with them is a very important step. Also, there is a strong motivation to continue to improve gate fidelities, reduce error rates to allow for more gates that can be used for larger quantum circuits [102], even before fault-tolerant error correction is implemented. Finding a useful killer app that offers some level of an advantage when using NISQ scale quantum computers would be a tremendous advance, one that would potentially kickstart a virtuous cycle that ultimately leads, in the long term, to large-scale fault-tolerant quantum computers. Furthermore, that is what we need in the end to realize the promise of quantum computation fully [103]. Thus, in the meantime, we need to identify NISQ scale applications, which brings us to this section, realistic quantum computation [1]today, challenges, and opportunities. This section will discuss what types of algorithms have been demonstrated at a small scale, the challenges they faced, how they benchmarked their systems, what they learned, and its

implications as we move into the NISQ scale era of quantum computing [104]. There is question about, are quantum computers fundamentally realizable? in a quantum computer, there are so many degrees of freedom, Let us say that we have say, 300 qubits, so we have two to the 300 degrees of freedom in our Hilbert state, and based on that, we have to control all two to the 300 degrees of freedom, which basically, if we calculate that out, that is more than all of the atoms in the known universe. so, if that were true, that would be a very difficult prospect. But, we know that is not the case, we have to control all two to the 300 degrees of freedom explicitly. That quantum mechanics provides quantum parallelism in a way that allows us to control large areas of the Hilbert space simultaneously, with far fewer gates than that. So that is one major misconception. Another one is this idea that, we will never be able to control the noise to this level, and that is going to be there, errors in these computers that cannot be corrected, and we think that this gets into the concept of fault-tolerance and error correction. The idea here is that, we know, quantum computing, is indeed analog up to some extent, but measurement allows us to digitize quantum information, and when we do a projective measurement, and in particular the syndrome measurements that we need to perform to do error correction, we can project a quantum system on to a state of error, or no error. that is a very important statement. Because, in doing that, we can do those projections, as we will discuss, we can do those projections in a way that tells us there is an error. It can tell us the type of error. But it never projects out the quantum information. so, once we know the type of error, and where it occurred, we can go back in and correct it. For example, we might discuss that a bit-flip occurred. State zero became state one, or state one became state zero. We can look that occurred, but we never look that the computer was in state one or state zero. we just discussed that a bit-flip occurred, and so we can go back in and fix it, by flipping the bit back. Now, we never lose the quantum information in this process, and it requires specially-designed syndromes, and also, the concept of fault tolerance. That when an error occurs, it does not propagate into more and more errors downstream, and that is an architectural question. we think that is important to realize. Now, it is certainly true that there is a lot of hype in the field these days, probably more than is warranted at this stage. This is a new technology, and developing technologies takes time, it takes engineering. it is natural that with any exciting technology, that we get excited about it, and we want it to occur faster than it is going to occur. But as we discuss, if we look at the time scale over which classical computing developed, we remember that the triode diode was invented in 1906, and it was not until 1946 that we had ENIAC, which was the first very, we know, by today's standards, a very primitive classical electronic computer. the transistor was invented a year later, but it was not until the '70s and '80s that we had chips that we think of in our computers today., whereas we started with vacuum tubes, and we moved to discrete transistors, and eventually we moved on to CMOS where are today. we know, there were many steps along the way. The technologies changed and pivoted. But we think, had we not followed this thread of development, we would not have got to where we are today. So certainly there is a lot of hype today, and this is a hard problem. But if we think back to many of the major technological advances that have been made over the decades, and even centuries, it is littered with people who say that things just cannot happen, right? And, they are almost always proven wrong. so, we think that quantum computing is hard, but we will succeed, and we will have quantum computers, and what they look like, that is to debate, but they will happen.

24 Quantum Volume

How powerful is a quantum system? Furthermore, how do we compare quantum computers based on different technologies? There is much more to the answer than the number of qubits, just as

we would not think of measuring a laptop performance by the number of transistors. Meaningful performance metrics are just being formulated. The quantum volume was created to capture key aspects of noisy intermediate quantum systems that operate using quantum circuits constructed from the universal gate set [105]. Note that this metric would not be appropriate for quantum annealers, nor fully fault-tolerant quantum computers. The quantum volume metric incorporates the number of physical qubits and errors due to gates, quantum crosstalk, decoherence, measurements, the topology of qubit connectivity, the gate set implemented, and parallelism. How many gates can be run in parallel? Let us think about each of these issues separately. Consider gate errors when preparing a 3 qubit GHZ state. A first CNOT is used to entangle the top and middle qubits. Then, a second CNOT entangles them with the bottom qubit. If each CNOT has an error of ϵ , then the total gate error is the product of the fidelities, or the quantity $1 - \epsilon^2$, for this example. To first order in ϵ , the fidelity is then $1 - 2\epsilon$. For the quantum volume to represent typical quantum approximate optimization algorithms [106–109] or variational quantum eigensolvers [31, 32], we must implement a circuit comprised of d layers of U4 or general two-qubit unitaries, which can be decomposed into three CNOT gates [110]. These errors of each U4 is then 3ϵ , to first order in ϵ . Other errors could also be introduced when making the GHZ state. For example, during the first CNOT gate between the top and middle qubits, the state of the bottom qubit could be affected by the control signal. We call this spectator qubit error. Significant errors also accrue if the qubits decohere appreciably while executing a circuit of great depth. Furthermore, measurement errors directly impact the fidelity of a circuit. We have chosen to implement the quantum volume metric with randomly chosen U4 unitaries between random qubit pairs. Qubit technologies with gates only between neighboring qubits must then teleport or swap the quantum states around an interconnection lattice to cause the desired qubit states to interact. Either of these operations introduces more gates and errors. For example, to implement a U4 unitary between non-neighbor qubits 0 and 2, a 3 CNOT sequence to swap qubits 0 and 1 would first need to be executed. Each quantum system may implement a different set of gates, natively in their control hardware. The Solovay-Kitaev algorithm approximates any two-qubit unitary to within a specified error with multiple gates. Therefore, systems that natively implement more unitaries than the simplest universal gate set accrue fewer gates and less error. Finally, overall execution time, hence, decoherence, can be reduced if the unitaries can be implemented in as parallel a manner as possible. So, how are all these effects incorporated into one expression for the quantum volume metric? The quantum volume expresses accessible quantum states, so, it is exponential in the number of accessible qubits, m . If the error per 2 qubit gates is large, then not all qubits can be entangled with useful fidelity. So, m is less than or equal to the number of physical qubits. The depth of the quantum circuit, d , is defined as the number of layers of permutations, π , and U4 unitaries executed on the hardware. The number of accessible qubits is then the minimum of m prime and the circuit depth, d . If the gate error is high, the depth may be small. If too large, an m prime is chosen. We maximize the quantum volume by choosing the largest n prime less than or equal to the number of available qubits that maximizes m . We have implemented this algorithm on our quantum experience hardware. We compiled random circuits offline using a greedy algorithm to determine the sequence of random 2 qubit unitaries combined with added swaps or teleportation to execute on our hardware. After multiple random trials, we arrive at an average quantum volume of 8 for a 5-qubit quantum experience processor. The quantum volume metric is a stringent test of near-term universal quantum hardware capabilities. We expect this and new metrics to evolve as we discuss more benchmarking quantum systems [28, 111].

Quantum volume is a metric that attempts to quantify the computational utility of a quantum computing platform. It is designed to be an architecture-neutral means to compare capabilities across platforms with potentially widely differing characteristics [112]. Platforms with higher

values of quantum volume can, in principle, implement more complex quantum algorithms.

The computational power of a quantum device depends not only on the number of qubits but also on their gate fidelities, the types of qubit interactions, their connectivity, as well as several other characteristics that may influence computing performance. For example, the increased connectivity of an ion-based quantum processor may offer certain advantages over the generally nearest-neighbor connectivity of a superconducting qubit processor [113]. This goes beyond a solely fidelity-based comparison between platforms.

Conceptually, while the quantum volume is a metric for the utility of a quantum processor when executing a particular algorithm, it does not provide any insight into specific aspects such as the overall computational time. Rather, it quantifies the “space-time” volume occupied by a hypothetical circuit with random two-qubit interactions that can be reliably executed on the processor. The “space,” as its represented here, translates to the number of active qubits n' out of all available physical qubits n in the quantum processor. The “time,” in turn, translates to the depth of the circuit d . The quantum circuit depth reflects the maximum possible number of sequential quantum operations that can be reliably applied to the processor. Implementing a model algorithm with a depth greater than d runs the risk of erroneous output due to the accumulation of noise and gate errors. The circuit depth depends on the number of active qubits and the per-gate error rate ϵ_{eff} such that $d = 1/n'\epsilon_{\text{eff}}$. The quantum volume QV is an expression for the “reachability” of the quantum state space, and it is thus exponential in the number of “reliable” qubits m . The number m is smaller or equal to the actual number of active physical qubits, as it also depends on the per-gate error rate.

$$QV = 2^m = 2^{\max\{\min\{n',d\}\}} = 2^{\max\{\min\{n',1/n'\epsilon_{\text{eff}}\}\}}. \quad (73)$$

In this way, the QV attempts to quantify the state-space accessibility, a proxy for the utility of a quantum processor, which, in aggregate, effectively incorporates the different strengths and weaknesses of different quantum computing architectures and platforms [112, 114]. Further reading, Validating quantum computers using randomized model circuits [115], Quantum optimization using variational algorithms on near-term quantum devices [116].

There are several aspects that need to be considered when quantifying the efficiency or power of a quantum computer. In March 2017, IBM published the paper, “Quantum optimization using variational algorithms on near-term quantum devices.” In this paper [116], they defined a new architecture-neutral metric based on the question: Can this quantum computer run a given algorithm? Their metric, called Quantum Volume, QV, takes into account the minimum number of qubits, N , required to run a quantum algorithm, and the necessary number of steps, also known as the circuit depth d . Some of the hardware aspects that Quantum Volume QV incorporates are.

- The number of gates that can be applied before decoherence affects the results.
- Connectivity between qubits.
- Available quantum gates.
- The number of gates that can be run in parallel.

25 Demonstration of Quantum Advantage in Machine Learning

As we have seen so far, currently available quantum processors are mostly limited to the handful of qubits and noisy quantum gates. For this reason, demonstrating a definite advantage of quantum

over classical computing is an ongoing challenge [117,118]. In this section, we will present an experiment we did at Raytheon BBM Technologies in collaboration with IBM Research, where a clear quantum advantage for a specific algorithm appears with only a few highly noisy qubits. The problem we consider is known in classical computing as Learning Parity with Noise, or LPN for short. At the center of the problem is a device, also called an oracle, with an unknown string, k , encoded on it. Our goal is to discuss what the k is by observing the effect of the oracle on random input bits. The bitstream, k , is related to the action of the oracle on the input, D , by this relation. In words, the oracle takes the bit, D_i , for which k_i equals 1, calculates their parity, and writes it into the result bit, A . For instance, let us take an oracle of dimension 2 and k equals 1, 1. These are some of the possible outcomes. After a few attempts, it is easy to figure out that it contains the result of both bits. So, we conclude that k equals 1, 1. However, the problem is not trivial in the presence of errors. Imagine that with some probability, the result of either d_1 , d_2 , or are randomly flipped. As we can see, it is now much harder to find the relation between the output. It can be shown that the number of queries grows nearly exponentially with the amount of noise. Interestingly, if one uses a quantum oracle, the difficulty of the problem can be drastically reduced. The circuit implements a quantum version of the Oracle. Now, the input and the result bits are quantum bits. and the function is implemented as a series of Hadamard gates and CNOT gates. The Hadamard gates create an equal superposition of input states. Then, a CNOT is applied between every qubit D_i for which k_i equals 1 and the target A . The effect of the CNOT gate is to map the parity of qubits D_1 up to the D_n onto qubit A , reproducing the classical LPN Oracle on a quantum circuit. Our system of choice to implement the circuit is an IBM five-qubit superconducting quantum processor. Each qubit is coupled to a microwave resonator, like the one shown here, to deliver control and readout pulses. The interaction between the middle qubit, A , and the other four are mediated by other resonators, in blue. this is what allows us to implement the desired CNOT gate. we use this circuit to implement an LPN oracle. we now compare these strategies to find k for a classical and for a quantum learner, both using the results of this oracle. In a classical case, for every call of the oracle, the learner simply measures the output register and collects the results. Let us go back to the example with k equals 1, 1. These are some of the possible results we may obtain for five queries. Remember that, ideally, a should equal the parity of d_1 , d_2 . Even in the presence of errors, with enough statistics, one can find that the most consistent solution for these data is k equals 1, 1. This is the experimental result for the four different two-bit oracles. As expected, the higher the number of queries, the lower the error probability. Despite using a quantum oracle, the learning here is completely classical. we take the measurement results, which are classical, and analyze them on a classical computer. The power of quantum processing only appears when we are allowed to manipulate the output state of the oracle. Because the state is quantum, we can apply a Hadamard gate on all qubits. This is the final stage before measurement. This is an entangled state of the ancilla with the data qubits. As we can see, when the ancilla is measured to be 0, the data qubits are also projected into 0. we obtain no information on k . Because of this, we discard all the results were an equal 0. On the other hand, when a equal 1, we project the data qubits onto k , which is exactly the solution we are looking for. Finally, we take the bitwise majority vote for d_1 and d_2 to find the best guess for k . As we will see later, this makes the protocol particularly robust to errors. This is now how the error probability decreases with the number of queries in the experiment. Let us look again at the classical solver for comparison. Whereas the error probability is comparable in the two cases, for k equals 0, 0, 0, 1, or 1, 0, the behavior starts to differ for k equals 1, 1. This is the most complex of the four circuits, including two CNOT gates, each introducing errors. This suggests that as the problem gets harder, quantum learning is more efficient. Let us indeed increase the problem size in the experiment. we go from two to three data qubits for the oracle. this is the result we obtain for the error averaged over the eight computational

input states. Clearly, not only the quantum learner retains an advantage, but the gap with the classical learner increases with the oracle size. Finally, let us consider how robust this protocol is to additional errors. As an example, consider the case where we introduce additional noise on the result qubit, a . On the x-axis, we denote with η the probability that we make an error in reading its state. On the y-axis, we indicate the number of queries required to find k with a 1% error probability. As η increases, this number only slowly increases for a quantum learner. On the other hand, the number of queries required to a classical learner grows by up to two orders of magnitude. To summarize, the learning parity with noise is an experimental realization of a quantum advantage using current noisy quantum circuits. Not only is quantum learning more efficient in this case than the classical counterpart, but also, the performance gap increases with the difficulty of the problem, either by increasing the oracle size or by adding noise to the system.

Encoding messages using a parity function and a secret bit string, or “key,” is a straightforward encryption scheme. The output is formed by a single-bit parity measurement of an n -bit message that is bitwise combined with an n -bit key using an XOR operation. To unravel the key using classical methods, up to 2^n different input messages have to be compared with their corresponding encrypted output bit. As we might expect, the power of quantum parallelism and interference may again provide an advantage over classical approaches.

A parity encryption scheme consists of an input bit string D bit-wise combined with the key k such that $f(D,k) = D \cdot k \pmod 2$. This represents the bit-wise multiplication of the elements of vectors D and k , followed by the mod-2 addition of the resulting values, which is very similar to how a dot product between vectors works. The parity function $f(D,k)$ yields a 0 for an even parity, or a 1 for an odd parity. The algorithm’s task is to identify the underlying key k .

Suppose a quantum processor is comprised of 3 qubits, with 2 qubits serving as input states $D = [d_1, d_2]$, and the remaining qubit as an auxiliary qubit a on which the result of $f(D,k)$ is stored. The unknown bit string k is implemented on the quantum processor as an oracle function. For an $n=2$ -bit key k , there are $2^n = 4$ different possible keys $k = [k_1, k_2]$, which are $\{11, 10, 01, 00\}$. The following tables summarize the value of a depending on the input bits d_1, d_2 , and the bit string k .

k=11			k=10			k=01			k=00		
d_1	d_2	a									
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0
1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0

Figure 9: Riste

A quantum algorithm to determine an encoded 2-bit key k with 2 qubits serving as input states for $D = [d_1, d_2]$ and 1 auxiliary qubit $|0\rangle_a$. At first, all qubits are initialized in the ground state. Then, a Hadamard gate acts on each of the data qubits. Next, the oracle implements the parity operation with the bit string k , storing the result on the auxiliary bit. $k_i = 0$ is equivalent to an identity gate, and $k_i = 1$ can be implemented with a $CNOT_{i \rightarrow a}$ gate acting on the auxiliary qubit with qubit i as the control [119]. After the oracle function, Hadamard gates are again applied to the qubits to leverage quantum parallelism and quantum interference. (If we were to measure the qubits before performing the last Hadamard gates and thus omitting the

quantum parallelism and interference step, we would essentially mimic the output of a classical processor.)

An example of this step-by-step can be seen in the following diagram, but note that the second line flips the middle two terms in the superposition state. This does not affect the result, but it might be easier to follow knowing this.

initialization:		$ 0\rangle_{d_1} 0\rangle_{d_2} 0\rangle_a$
oracle function:	$\xrightarrow{H \otimes H \otimes I}$	$\frac{1}{2}(0\rangle_{d_1} 0\rangle_{d_2} 0\rangle_a + 1\rangle_{d_1} 0\rangle_{d_2} 0\rangle_a + 0\rangle_{d_1} 1\rangle_{d_2} 0\rangle_a + 1\rangle_{d_1} 1\rangle_{d_2} 0\rangle_a)$
	$\xrightarrow{CNOT_{d_1 \rightarrow a}}$	$\frac{1}{2}(0\rangle_{d_1} 0\rangle_{d_2} 0\rangle_a + 0\rangle_{d_1} 1\rangle_{d_2} 0\rangle_a + 1\rangle_{d_1} 0\rangle_{d_2} 1\rangle_a + 1\rangle_{d_1} 1\rangle_{d_2} 1\rangle_a)$
	$\xrightarrow{CNOT_{d_2 \rightarrow a}}$	$\frac{1}{2}(0\rangle_{d_1} 0\rangle_{d_2} 0\rangle_a + 0\rangle_{d_1} 1\rangle_{d_2} 1\rangle_a + 1\rangle_{d_1} 0\rangle_{d_2} 1\rangle_a + 1\rangle_{d_1} 1\rangle_{d_2} 0\rangle_a)$
classical:	\xrightarrow{meas}	$\frac{1}{2}(0\rangle_{d_1} 0\rangle_{d_2} 0\rangle_a + 0\rangle_{d_1} 1\rangle_{d_2} 1\rangle_a + 1\rangle_{d_1} 0\rangle_{d_2} 1\rangle_a + 1\rangle_{d_1} 1\rangle_{d_2} 0\rangle_a)$ $P(0_{d_1}0_{d_2}0_a) = P(0_{d_1}1_{d_2}1_a) = P(1_{d_1}0_{d_2}1_a) = P(1_{d_1}1_{d_2}0_a) = 1/4$
quantum:	$\xrightarrow{H \otimes H \otimes H}$	$\frac{1}{2}(0\rangle_{d_1} 0\rangle_{d_2} 0\rangle_a + 0\rangle_{d_1} 1\rangle_{d_2} 1\rangle_a + 1\rangle_{d_1} 0\rangle_{d_2} 1\rangle_a + 1\rangle_{d_1} 1\rangle_{d_2} 0\rangle_a)$ $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(0\rangle_{d_1} 0\rangle_{d_2} 0\rangle_a + 1\rangle_{d_1} 1\rangle_{d_2} 1\rangle_a)$
	\xrightarrow{meas}	$P(0_{d_1}0_{d_2}0_a) = P(1_{d_1}1_{d_2}1_a) = 1/2$

Figure 10: Riste

An immediate measurement after the oracle function for $k = 11$ generates one of four distinct output states with equal probability. In fact, in a noisy environment, identification of the unknown bit string k may require even more than the ideally expected 4 queries to claim the identification of k with sufficiently high confidence.

In contrast, a quantum algorithm with classical post-processing a hybrid approach [120] benefits from quantum parallelism and interference through additional Hadamard gates applied to the qubits before the measurement [121]. The measurement projects the state onto the qubit's ground-state or a more complex state, both with probability 1/2. Post-selecting the measurement and only considering the states with an auxiliary qubit in state 1 further improves the performance of the hybrid approach [122]. Similar to the classical approach, interfering noise processes enforce multiple measurements and averaging of the results to determine k with certainty.

Even under noisy conditions, the hybrid approach outperforms the classical with respect to the number of measurements to identify k with sufficiently high certainty. The example can be generalized to other 2-bit or n-bit keys k . Note, the quantum advantage can only be achieved if the data qubits are initialized in a superposition state, reflecting all possible data bit inputs. The experiments indicate that under noisy conditions, a hybrid approach using quantum interference and parallelism outperforms its classical counterpart and determines the k faster and hence with fewer queries.

For further reading, the publication describing the experiment discussed above: Demonstration of quantum advantage in machine learning [117]

26 Quantum Support Vector Machine

So, suppose we have a classification problem we have to solve. this classification problem is given to us as n -dimensional vectors that are our data. these vectors, they belong to several classes. for simplicity, we are going to keep this discussion to only two classes. So, each vector either belongs to one class or another, and we need to classify into these two classes the data that we are given. So, in this example, we are going to have a training set that is given to us, of which we know the data and the labels. we are going to use this training set to find a cutting hyperplane that separates this data, and that we can use to classify any future data whose label we do not know and that is given to us. we assume that the data is already linearly separable. with that assumption, we can go ahead and do cutting in our training set that separates the training set we are being given. Now, we can use this cutting hyperplane to classify any future database given to us. we will do that with some degree of success. However, we want to maximize that success. So, we have a choice of cutting hyperplanes we can choose from our training data. Which one is the best one which we could choose? So, there is a method that people use to determine what is the most optimal one, which is called a support vector machine. what this method does is it places the cutting hyperplane as far as possible to any data point in the training set. Now, the closest data points to the cutting hyperplane in the training sets are going to be the data points that are more difficult to classify. once we find them, that is equivalent to finding the cutting hyperplane. These data points are called the support vectors. That is where the name comes from. once we know the support vectors, we know the cutting hyperplane, and we know it is the best we can do for this training set, now, with that cutting hyperplane, we can take new data whose label we do not know and classify it into one of the two labels. Now, this is if the data is linearly separable. If it is not, like this example, we are showing here where we have one-dimensional data. We cannot do a single cut that will separate the two labels, what we can do, the trick that people use is we can map that data into higher dimensions until we find a space in which we can linearly separate the data. This transformation is called a feature map. here, we give an example of where we transfer the one-dimensional data into two-dimensional data. here, we see that we can separate it. Now, as the problems get more complex, we can imagine that the size of our feature space, the target of the feature map, can grow significantly in a number of dimensions. However, it is not only the dimensionality that makes that problem complex. Alternatively, it is not precisely the dimensionality because what we are doing for classifying is, and we want to see how close points are to each other in the new feature space. We do not need to know where each point is, we need to know how close each point is from all the other points. So, there is a magical tool that one can use for finding how close the points are in a given space, which is called the inner product. If we can know the inner product of every pair of data in our training set, we do not need to apply, and we do not need to know the feature map explicitly. we can just try to get the inner product after applying the feature map, without applying the feature map. So, the information that gives us the inner product in the feature space between each two data points in a training set is called a kernel. once we know the kernel, we know the distance between each of the points. then, from there, we can obtain the support vectors. Now, how can quantum computing help with this problem? Well, one way is, if we have a weird data set, like the one we see here, this data set, for simplicity, has only two features, two dimensions, and two classes, which we see here as red and blue. these two classes are separated by a white gap to make them a bit easier to classify. This data set has a property that we know a feature map that will take this space, where the data is, and map it into a two-qubit state space. This is a space of two-qubit density matrices. we know that, if we have a two-qubit quantum processor, we can efficiently do operations in that space. if this data set with this same structure was much, much larger in dimensionality, we know that we could map it into a large enough quantum processor.

If we had enough low noise, then we could estimate inner products in that space because it is not only the dimensionality. we are using a data set that we know is going to be difficult to estimate inner products if the set is complex enough. With this data set, we can see here how the feature map works for a single qubit because it is simple to visualize. we can see that a one-dimensional line from 0 to 2π will map in the single-qubit Bloch sphere in the way we see. This is attained with just basic changes and phase gates. In the case of more qubits, we will add entanglements as CZ interactions, and so on. So, now we can go ahead and take a training set that we see here of 20 points per label. what we do with this training set is we map it to the two-qubit displays. We then use a quantum processor to estimate the inner product of each two points, and we obtain the kernel. here we can see the kernel. This kernel is just a matrix of 40 by 40. It is symmetric and semi-definite positive. this is real data from a quantum computer. So, this matrix is going to tell us all we need to know about this training set for classification purposes. So, from this data, we can estimate the support vectors. we can do that already outside of the quantum processor because it is easy to estimate the support vectors from a kernel if we know the kernel. It is getting the kernel that might be difficult. So, here, we see the support vectors circled in green. So, these are the data points in the training set that is closest to the hyperplane. with these support vectors, we can get new data, and we can compare it or see how close the new data is to each of the support vectors. we forget about any other point in the training data set. Then we can classify any new data. This is a randomly drawn new set of data points that we are going to try to classify. So, we have the black squares belonging to class red, and the white squares belonging to class blue. if we take each of these points and do the inner product in the quantum processor, and then see at what side of the cutting hyperplane they fall, we see that we can classify them with 100% success, that the black squares will fall on the right-hand side of the hyperplane and the white squares will fall on the left-hand side. we can say we can classify them perfectly well. Well, this was just a toy example, without any connection with real-life data problems, or data sets. However, we think that, given the spectacular progress in quantum hardware over the last decade or so, we are starting to get to a point where these processors are powerful enough to try new ideas. we know that the classical machine learning methods have been around for about half a century, and only reasonably recently, they have been starting to attract attention. that was because of the development of computer hardware, and the computing ability of our processor became much, much larger. these ideas that existed for artificial intelligence could be tested, and then the field advanced that way. It is an exciting time, really, for quantum computing because we are at a time where we can get inspiration from the classical methods in artificial intelligence and try to produce new ideas that will be applicable to the field. Support Vector Machines (SVM); The Quantum Support Vector Machine is an implementation of a machine-learning algorithm on a quantum computer [29], and it is used to classify data. The following statements describe the steps of the SVM algorithm. A quantum computer is used to efficiently calculate the inner product among points in a data set. In the case of the quantum support vector machine algorithm, the quantum computer is used for two purposes: to obtain the kernel of a known data set, and to efficiently classify any new data sets.

27 Practical Quantum Simulation: Introduction

Quantum mechanics is a remarkable theory in that its principles apply not only to atomic-scale particles but also to macroscopic objects such as electrical circuits. As we have already covered in this section, in the race towards building a quantum computer, resonant circuits constructed from superconducting metals have progressed tremendously over the past 10 years with coherent lifetimes increasing from a few nanoseconds to almost a millisecond in state of the art devices,

making nascent quantum processors a reality. These solid-state objects enjoy all the rights and privileges of qubits. They can be placed in a coherent superposition that is collapsed by the act of measurement, just like an atomic spin interacting with photons. So, why cannot we just print thousands of superconducting qubits if we know the basic recipe for each one? Well, a major challenge even at the level of 100 qubits arises from the fact that though there may be plenty of space at the bottom as Feynman said, at the nanoscale, say, to have a high density of quantum bits, there is not much space at the top where wires and electronics have to be carefully arranged to handle and process quantum information efficiently [123, 124]. Thus, the road to a universal quantum computer [125] robust to errors is still several orders of magnitude away in qubit density and lifetime. That being said, there are still different types of quantum algorithms that can be executed with technologies at hand and can solve specific problems of great scientific interest. A major focus of research today is to produce those algorithms compatible with noisy intermediate-scale quantum devices, or NISQ technology. One class of problems that can be tackled on NISQ hardware are associated with ideas put forward by Richard Feynman and are called quantum simulations [126–128], where quantum bits are coupled in a specific geometry, allowed to interact with each other, and finally probed after they have reached a final configuration. Such a hardware simulator eliminates the need to describe and track all the possible arrangements that this array of qubits can access [28]. Doing so would require an exponentially large set of classical numbers and is the fundamental reason problems of this type cannot be performed on a classical computer. In the quantum simulation paradigm, only a few select properties of the system have to be probed at the end of an algorithmic sequence. With progress in next-generation quantum algorithms, there are now many types of scientific calculations that can be efficiently mapped onto a quantum simulator [129] ranging from problems involving the energy spectra of molecules and complex solid-state materials such as high-temperature superconductors and quantum magnets to the dynamics present in natural and artificial light-harvesting complexes to models of the cosmos were ideas and quantum field theory and gravity can be tested [130]. Let us focus for a moment on an example from quantum chemistry. If we start with a modest patch of electronic matter which we can approximate for the moment as distinguishable particles, given an m by m grid of electrons which we describe each with a 100 orbitals, for an 80 electron system, this tiny patch of matter would require 100 to the power 80 numbers to describe. To put this in context, this is much larger than a mole or the number of particles in a tangible piece of matter. In fact, and it is larger than the number of particles in the entire universe. Thus, directly calculating the structure of even a small number of quantum particles is very computationally intensive. The number of atoms that can be treated by various computational chemistry methods is shown in the plot on the left. A direct computation of Schrodinger’s equation limits one to less than 10 atoms. Other methods like density functional theory give access to a much larger sample size but are approximate and not accurate for all types of materials [95]. For calculating energy levels, classical computers simply do not have enough memory to describe the large combinatorial space quantum systems live in [131]. even the most powerful classical supercomputers with petabytes of memory can only tackle of order 50 qubits. Certain clever methods using tensor networks [132, 133] and renormalization group theory can boost this number to say, 70 elements, but nonetheless do not approach the realm of complex materials. Quantum simulators provide access to classically intractable problems in chemistry [134–136]. A grand challenge, for example, in the field, is to study catalysis in particular with respect to the production of ammonia. Ammonia is a key agent used in fertilizer production and other industrial products. the industrial scale Haber process, which combines nitrogen and hydrogen at 400 degrees centigrade and 200 times atmospheric pressure, consumes of water a few percent of all the energy on Earth. Remarkably, bacteria execute nitrogen fixation at ambient conditions, making use of a catalyst, which in principle can be studied with a quantum computer. Solving problems of this type, though still some

distance away from the capabilities of current quantum machines, nevertheless promises to have a tremendous impact on human civilization.

28 Practical Quantum Simulation: Contemporary VQE

Let us work with a simpler molecule, hydrogen. we want to describe how one can develop a quantum algorithm to treat electronic structure problems in chemistry [137–142]. we first note from quantum mechanics that an electron is a fermion and obeys symmetry rules associated with such particles, and moreover, is indistinguishable from other electrons. Qubits, on the other hand, are certainly indistinguishable, since they can be labeled and addressed individually. In fact, one addresses them by the use of poly operators, and the first step in mapping a chemistry problem onto a quantum computer is to rewrite the Hamiltonian, which describes the total energy of the system from electronic creation and annihilation operators, labeled a and a^\dagger , into polypin operators, σ . this can be accomplished, for example, by the famous Jordan-Wigner transformation. This mapping preserves the number of terms in the Hamiltonian. However, the locality is lost in that spin operators from different sites are convolved, and the coefficients, g , shown here have to be computed classically. It turns out that this can be done without too much trouble. The next step is then to evaluate the terms in the Hamiltonian, which involve products of spin operators and are analogous to calculating correlation functions. This is where the quantum simulation magic comes in., we going to describe a clever algorithm, known as the Variational Quantum Eigen solver, or VQE. In this approach, we rewrite the electronic structure Hamiltonian in a power series expansion of poly operators. we are interested in computing the energy of the molecule, expressed as the expectation value of the Hamiltonian, which by linearity, can be expressed as a sum of the energies associated with each poly correlator in the sum. To calculate each term, we can arrange our quantum simulator in the corresponding configuration by way of single and two-qubit logical gate operations. One of the powerful features of this technique is that each term can be evaluated independently of the other, thereby reducing the number of quantum logic operations that have to be run in succession to only a few. This process allows current quantum hardware to execute the routine. Finally, the task of combining these terms is performed using a classical computer. Since we do not make a priori, know the electronic configuration that will yield the lowest energy, a set of parameters is scanned, and the energy landscape is produced. So, in summary, executing the algorithm consists of parameterizing the quantum state in terms of the classical parameter. Setting the knobs, we can turn in the experiment to a particular value, computing the terms in the Hamiltonian using our quantum hardware, and then finally turning our control knobs until a minimum is found. Let us see this in action for hydrogen. we are going to ignore the motion of the heavy nuclei in this calculation and treat only the electronic structure problem. In the first step, we choose a common basis of orbitals to describe the electrons in the system and then transform the Hamiltonian into the poly operator basis that we described earlier. This is called the pre-compilation step [143]. Since it is a classical computation step, we can show it as blue in the figure. In this problem, we have six degrees of freedom corresponding to two electrons, and we prepare the system in a target configuration by adjusting six experimental parameters that we have access to in our qubit system. In this case, these parameters correspond to the amplitude and phase of the excitations we can apply to each individual qubit and the length and phase of a pulse used to create quantum entanglement between the two qubits. This set of six parameters is simply expressed as a single vector, θ . This step prepares the quantum hardware in the calculation and, as shown in tan. Then, to extract the individual terms that go into the energy calculation, we measure the specific correlators that appear in the Hamiltonian and use them to calculate the ground state energy.

we can then repeat the process for a variety of different values of θ until the minimum is reached. Finally, there is a neat trick to calculate the excited states as well. Once we obtain our best guess for the ground state, we can perform an operation analogous to a Taylor expansion, where operators that cost excitations in the system can be approximated in the vicinity of the energy minimum. This can be done with only a modest number of additional measurements. Putting it all together, voila. we have the full energy spectrum of the hydrogen molecule computed using a specialized quantum computer, running a hybrid algorithm that makes efficient use of both classical and quantum computing resources. The data points in the figure represent the values obtained from the quantum machine, and the solid lines are the predicted exact values obtained from a conventional computer. The accuracy of the result is shown in the upper right inset, which shows that the quantum computations are hovering around a milli-Hartree discrepancy in energy. This level of error is near what is called chemical accuracy and indicates that the results are good enough to predict chemical processes. Though we can compute the classical energy spectrum for a simple molecule like hydrogen, the complexity of the calculation grows exponentially with system size. we would rapidly exceed the computational power of a supercomputer with say 100 qubit system. The key science questions that must now be tackled gravitate around how VQE will perform for larger numbers of qubits. Will sources of error scale in a way that does not require large resources for error correction? Will the quantum processor be stable over the time needed to make all the correlator measurements? These questions all point to the fact that this is an exciting time in quantum information science as we explore the advantage of emerging quantum hardware [1, 144, 145]. In summary, specialized quantum computers are already here and have an important role to play in many optimization problems in basic science from chemistry to cosmology. we need to study sources of error in hybrid algorithms like VQE and develop efficient routines to mitigate them [122, 146–148]. Relatedly, can the classical information processing needed to execute such routines be efficiently handled using machine learning methods? All of these points put together will help us determine the true power of these types of quantum machines.

State-of-the-art quantum computers today have 10-100 qubits, and in the not-too-distant future, we can foresee a demonstration of “quantum supremacy” [149–151]. Loosely defined, quantum supremacy is the demonstration of a task that can be successfully performed on a quantum computer, and yet cannot be performed on existing classical computers in any reasonable amount of time. For the purposes of demonstrating quantum supremacy, the actual problem implemented need not be useful, commercialize able algorithm that addresses an important problem to humankind [152]; rather, its sole purpose could simply be to demonstrate that quantum supremacy is possible.

Thus, while the demonstration of quantum supremacy will stand as an important milestone in the to-be-told history of quantum computing [153], it might not represent the turning point when quantum computers suddenly become useful machines. This is because all of the known quantum algorithms that do address important problems in cybersecurity, simulation, and optimization, require very large numbers of essentially error-free logical qubits, and the required technology to build such universal and fault-tolerant quantum processors is likely to be at least a decade or two away [152].

Between the first demonstration of quantum supremacy and the advent of fault-tolerant quantum processors, the question is, what can we do in the meantime? Are there practical, useful algorithms that we can do with the noisy, intermediate-scale quantum (NISQ) computers we have now and will have for the foreseeable future? This is an important question to answer because we know that technology development requires significant investment. Investment by governments worldwide have helped to start the field of quantum computing, and this investment

will continue to play an important role. However, government investment alone might not be sufficient to realize the potential of quantum computation.

It is imperative that the community identify quantum algorithms that run on NISQ computers and address important, meaningful problems that can be commercialized. This will kickstart a virtuous cycle of technology development. The revenue from the current generation of NISQ computers will support the development of a next-generation, higher-performance NISQ computer. There is currently significant research efforts aimed at developing such NISQ-era algorithms, starting with the types of prototype algorithms. Already there are blue-chip and start-up companies working to commercialize cloud-based access to quantum computers [154]. With more access to such quantum computers, in conjunction with the development of a software stack needed to facilitate quantum-computer programming [155], more and more researchers will be able to develop and test prototype algorithms that target commercialize applications.

29 Solving Linear Systems of Equations

One not so, the obvious application of the Hamiltonian simulation algorithms [156]. we have seen is a quantum algorithm to solve the linear system of equations, which becomes particularly interesting when these are very large systems of equations. So, we are going to tell us about that algorithm now. First, we are going to tell us about what we mean by solving a linear system of equations, and we will tell us about classical algorithms for the problem [105]. Then, we will discuss a quantum approach to this and discuss its performance, and then we will discuss some issues that arise with the quantum algorithm that is not present for the classical algorithm [157]. So, by a system of linear equations, what we mean is that we have a vector of unknowns that we would like to find. we will call them x_1, x_2 through x_n , which for our purposes will be complex numbers, although reals would also work. then, we are given the coefficients of those equations. So, we would be given an equation of the form $3x_1$ plus x_3 equals 5, x_2 minus ix_3 equals 0, and so on. we want to find a bunch of x 's that satisfy all of those equations simultaneously. It is more convenient to put these equations into the form of a matrix. So, we would have a matrix equation Ax equals b , where A is an N by N matrix that we are given, x is our vector of unknowns, and b is another vector of coefficients that we are given as part of the input. We are going to tell us about the complexity of this problem and how hard it is to solve classically in quantumly. To discuss complexity, this needs to be parameterized by several things. One may be an obvious thing to parameterize it by is the size of these vectors and matrices. we say that the dimension N is the length of the vector x , and the size of the matrix A is N by N . But, there are other parameters as well, which depend on features of the input. So, one of them is called the sparsity of the matrix A . In general, we want to work with matrices where most of the entries are 0, and only a few are non-zero. So, we say that the sparsity is S if there are at most S non-zero entries in A per row or column. S could be as large as n , in which case we would have a dense matrix. However, often, we are interested in matrices where S happens to be small and or our algorithms can make use of this to run more efficiently. Another important parameter is the condition number, κ , which we will discuss more later. κ is defined as the ratio of the largest singular value of A to the smallest singular value of A . When A is a unitary matrix, it is one. This is the smallest that κ can be. As an approach to a non-invertible matrix, κ approaches infinity. Thus, we can see that κ represents, in some sense, the difficulty of inverting the matrix A . One nice feature of it is it is invariant under rescaling in matrix A by a scalar. In some sense, it measures the numerical instability of the matrix inversion process. What we mean by that is if we perturb the input b a little bit, that will cause some change in the vector x . how large that change depends on the condition number. If the condition number is small, a small

change in the input will produce a small change in the output. If the condition number is large, then there exist small changes in the input b that will cause very large changes in the output x . So, that is what we mean by numerical instability. We will describe two classical algorithms for this problem or rather families of classical algorithms before we get to the quantum algorithm. One family of classical algorithms is called iterative solvers because they start with a partial solution which they iteratively improve. These are best described in terms of a closely related problem, which is not solving $Ax = b$ but minimizing the norm of $Ax - b$. Because this norm is a convex function, if we use gradient descent, that will work well. We should note that this generalizes the linear systems problem because it is also interesting even when there is no x that exactly solves $Ax = b$, we still might want to minimize the norm of $Ax - b$. In other words, this minimum might not reach 0, but still, we want to find the minimum. This is useful, for example, in the problem of linear regression [158], where we want to find the best linear model to fit a set of data points. So, if we apply gradient descent to this problem, the norm is a very simple function. It just looks like a giant paraboloid if we plot it. What we have shown on the screen are the level sets, which are these nested ellipses. If we follow the path of gradient descent, we will follow these blue arrows. It will sort of move towards the minimum in this zigzag path. We can see that the more distorted the ellipses are, the farther from spherical they are, the more this path will zigzag. This is precisely what the condition number measures. The condition number is the ratio of the longest axis to the smallest axis. Thus, the larger the condition number is, the more stretched this ellipsoid is, and the longer it will take gradient descent to find the minimum. We can see that this will converge to error ϵ in time that scales like that condition number κ times $\log(1/\epsilon)$. This $\log(1/\epsilon)$ dependence is not too bad. However, the linear scaling with condition number is why we say that the condition number reflects the difficulty of solving the new system of equations in this method. So, the number of iterations is $\kappa \log(1/\epsilon)$. Each iteration requires multiplying a matrix, in fact, matrix A by a vector. Doing this involves iterating over all the entries of the matrix A . The time for that is just the number of non-zero entries, which is order N , the dimension, times s , the number of non-zero entries per row. If we put this all together, we see the time is on the order of $Ns\kappa \log(1/\epsilon)$. Another class of solvers has better dependence on κ but much worse dependence on dimension. The dimension dependency goes like order N^3 , which makes them non-competitive for very large matrices. These are called direct solvers. Examples of these are Gaussian elimination and the LU decomposition. If we remember back in high school, learning to solve a linear system of equations, this was probably the method that we learned to use. They work well for small systems but are generally not used for large N because the iterative methods will be performed much better as N becomes large.

30 Quantum Algorithm for Linear Systems

Now that we have seen a classical algorithm to solve a linear system of equations, we will describe to us a quantum algorithm. The appeal of this algorithm we can see in the run time, which is similar to the classical one in its dependence on the sparsity, the condition number, and the error, but improves that linear dependence in N to an order $\log N$ dependence. So, when N is large, this can mean dramatic savings in run time. Just a reminder that parameters N , S , and κ refer to dimension, sparsity, and condition number. The way the algorithm is able to achieve this is by not writing down the entire inputs and outputs just as states in memory because by the time we would have written it down, we already would have had to expend effort on the order of N . Instead, the input and output will be represented as quantum states of N dimensions, which means they can be encoded into $\log N$ qubits. So, in this way, we never have to work with N

actual pieces of memory or expend effort linear in N . The matrix A also cannot afford to fully write down because that would involve N times S pieces of memory. Instead, we will assume that A is computable on the fly. We will need to be able to, given the index of a row of A , some procedure that will output the non-zero entries of that row along with their locations. So, this input-output model is what makes possible the run time scaling with $\log N$. As a result, it means that the quantum algorithm achieves something which is not directly the same as in the classical case. we cannot just take place where we would have used the classical linear system solver and plug in the quantum one. we have to make sure that we can meet the input and output requirements in order to run the algorithm. This is analogous to what we discuss with the quantum Fourier transform. The quantum Fourier transform took something that classically ran in time $N \log N$. It turned it into a quantum run time that was polynomial in $\log N$ [159,160]. The only way for this to be possible is to transform the amplitudes of the state rather than just a list of numbers. Similarly, the quantum algorithm will solve a linear system of equations where the input and the output are amplitudes of a quantum state rather than lists of numbers stored in memory. So, lets now tell us how the algorithm works. There are three building blocks that we will put together in order to create the quantum linear system solving algorithm. for the purpose of this example, we are going to assume that A is a Hermitian matrix. The algorithm applies more generally as well, but the extension to non-Hermitian matrices is something that we will not mention right now, how that works. So, the three building blocks are Hamiltonian simulation, which we discussed earlier. Here, what this means is we want to apply e to the iAt , and the time required to do this should scale like the norm of A as well as the time, the evolution time, t . We discuss this in the context of Hamiltonian's, but the same ideas would apply to any matrix A presented in the form that we described where we have an efficient way, given a row index, to find the non-zero entries of that row. So, in other words, it applies to matrices that are not necessarily Hamiltonian's of physical systems, but may, for example, be the matrix of coefficients for the linear system of equations that we want to solve. The second building block is phase estimation. Here, we assume that we can apply something of form e to the $i \lambda t$ for some, perhaps, scalar λ , and we want to estimate λ . Phase estimation is a way of doing this where the accuracy goes like 1 over t , where t is the amount of time that we have evolved. Essentially, this can be viewed as frequency-time uncertainty. If we look at some sample for up to time t , then we have frequency resolution, which goes like 1 over t . The third ingredient we could call filtering. In this case, we will make a measurement and condition on the measurement coming out a particular way. This is something that only succeeds with some probability, not necessarily probability one. the result of doing it is that the state will evolve in a way that is still linear but can be non-unitary. Thus, this is called filtering because it is analogous to the way when the light goes through the filter; it can be transformed. For example, we can remove some colors or attenuate the amount of some frequencies. So, how do we put these together into the algorithm? First is a mathematical step. Nothing happens but will express the input b in terms of the eigenbasis of A . So, we can expand b out into a sum of eigenstates of A , call them A sub i , and coefficients which we will call b sub i . We will then apply the phase estimation to estimate the phase that we get from doing the Hamiltonian simulation to apply e to the iAt . When we do e to the iAt , each eigenstate of A will pick up phase at some rate, depending on what the corresponding eigenvalue is of A . Call those eigenvalues, λ sub i . If we combine the two, then what we get is we get an estimate for each eigenstate of A of the corresponding eigenvalue. we have put an approximate equal sign because these procedures are not perfect, but we can bound their error. we can rigorously say how accurate they are. So, what this does is it attaches to each A sub i an estimate, λ i , of the corresponding eigenvalue. Once we have this estimate, we can perform essentially any function of λ that we would like. For our purposes, we are interested in matrix inversion, but other work has extended this to other functions of λ as well, which in

other cases can be interesting. To do matrix inversion, what we want to do is we want to add a factor of $1/\lambda_i$ here. Essentially, we want to apply A^{-1} to the state, which means dividing the corresponding eigenvector, $A_{sub\ i}$, by the eigenvalue, $\lambda_{sub\ i}$. To do this, we will do a filtering operation where we, in some cases, accept and, in some cases, reject. our probability of acceptance should scale like $1/\lambda_{sub\ i}$. If we do this and condition on acceptance, then what we will have done is essentially added a $1/\lambda_i$ term to the appropriate point in the sum. we then want to un-compute $\lambda_{sub\ i}$. This means reversing step 2, which will erase that register. we will still be left with this coefficient of $1/\lambda_{sub\ i}$, but we will not have that extra quantum state, λ_i , which had we kept could have caused decoherence. we are left in the last line with this term that essentially looks like A^{-1} applied to b , which is the state that we wanted to solve, $cat\ x$, the solution to the linear system of equations.

31 Discussion of Quantum Linear Systems Algorithm

Now that we have seen this algorithm, how should we think about its performance? Since we have had such a dramatic improvement in the dependence on n , now it makes sense to look at the other parameters since those dependencies have not been reduced. If the condition number, κ , is still large, then we will not see such a big speedup. Whereas conversely, the places where we should find a big quantum speedup are where the condition number is very small. we can show, in fact, that this dependence and condition number cannot be reduced. So, this linear and κ dependence, that we see in both classical and quantum, we are essentially stuck with. One way to think about the role of condition number, here, is that what we have discussed about quantum circuits, that they always produce unitary evolutions, is more of a guideline than the hard and fast rule. If κ is one, then we are inverting a unitary matrix. we have no overhead from κ . Everything runs very efficiently, but we can also take κ to be a little bit larger, and then our runtime will only be a little bit larger as well. So, we can afford to do something that is slightly non-unitary and just pay a little bit of a price for it in terms of runtime. This idea has been used in places that go far beyond the linear system of equations algorithms we have just described. One example is an improved algorithm for Hamiltonian simulation, which is based on taking the Taylor series, for e to the minus iHt , spanning it out to a ton of terms, many of which might be either non-unitary or proportional to unitaries, and taking linear combinations of those. The intermediate steps of that algorithm involve things that are non-unitary, but only mildly non-unitary. so, the cost of doing this is not too bad. They are able to put together the whole package for a very efficient overall algorithm to do Hamiltonian simulation. Another example is due to Dominic Berry, who describes an algorithm to simulate ODEs, where the cost scales with how non-unitary that time evolution is. The Schrodinger equation can be thought of as an example of an ODE, where the time evolution is exactly unitary. However, Berry extends this to things where the time evolution can be a little bit non-unitary. the cost only goes up with the amount of non-unitary that we experience. Another important issue with the algorithm that distinguishes it from the classical version is the format of the input. As we have seen, the input should be a vector $cat\ b$, where the entries of the vector are encoded as the amplitudes of the input state. Similarly, the output we receive in the form of amplitudes of a quantum state. The matrix a also is not something that is just written down as a list of numbers. However, it should be something that we can compute on the fly, meaning that we are given a row index w and it can efficiently describe all the non-zero entries on that row of a . Similar issues here also apply to recent work on quantum algorithms for machine learning, for which there has been much recent research. What we need to do is find a way to put the algorithm, such as the linear systems algorithm, into a complete package. This is a little bit analogous to what Shor's

algorithm does with the quantum Fourier transform. If we remember, the quantum Fourier transform is a purely quantum procedure. It takes inputs that are amplitudes of quantum states and transforms into an output, which is also an amplitude of a quantum state. To make that useful, we need an entire package that begins and ends with classical data. So, how do we do this for linear systems? we need to take a classical input string, let us say n parameters, y_1 through y_n , and transforms it into a high dimensional state, which can be the input to the quantum linear systems algorithm [34]. we also need to do something about the output, but this turns out to be much easier. If we have an output state, then we can measure it and estimate observables. This is often closer to what we already need. However, dealing with input is an important algorithmic problem. This is an ongoing research question. So, we will not be able to present a full answer, but we will mention two solutions that people have considered. One of them is to build a new type of quantum hardware, called a quantum RAM [161], that would allow quantum queries to a large classical data set. In this case, the dimension capital n would be on the same order as the number of input parameters n . One model of what this might look like is something like a CD-ROM, where we have a large amount of classical data that could, in principle, be queried by a photon that is in a superposition of different modes that picks up phase information corresponding both to its quantum data about which cell is querying and to the classical information in that cell. This would be a powerful thing to be able to build, but we do not have large examples of this yet. Just like we do not have large quantum computers. The second approach is what we call algorithmic generation. In this case, we have a small classical input. Let us say n degrees of freedom. we use this with some algorithm to create a high dimensional quantum state based on this. This might be like a nonlinear embedding of the classical input into a larger space. Another example of where this might come up is if our classical input describes the shape and our state that we are applying the linear systems algorithm to comes from a finite element model, where we have discretized space very finely. Our shape just tells us where there is material or where there is not. This would come up if we were to try to solve things like the wave equation. So, in this case, we could algorithmically generate a high dimensional state from a small input. These are two ways of trying to address the issue of how to construct an input in order to put the linear systems algorithm into an overall package that would start and end with classical data and solve a problem more efficiently than we could solve on a classical computer. These are still stepping that would need to be worked out in order to solve practical problems with this linear systems solver.

11. Linear System of Equations: Characterization; One application of Hamiltonian simulation is solving a linear system of coupled equations. Let us consider the example from the section : Solving a Linear System of Equations,

$$3x_1 + x_3 = 5, x_2 - ix_3 = 0, -2x_1 + x_2 = -1. \quad (74)$$

In this system, the variables are x_1, x_2 and x_3 . All the equations have linear combinations of these variables. The system is considered to be solved when one finds the values of x_1, x_2 and x_3 that satisfy the three equations simultaneously.

To solve linear systems of equations, it is convenient to write the system as one equation of the form $Ax = b$, where x and b are vectors of length N , with N equal to the number of variables, and where A is an $N \times N$ matrix. The length of the vector x is also called the dimension of the system.

Following the example above, the system of equations can be written as

$$\begin{pmatrix} 3 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & -i \\ -2 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 5 \\ 0 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (75)$$

In this example, the length of the vectors x and b is $N = 3$, and the matrix A is a 3×3 matrix. The difficulty in finding a solution of a linear system of equations can be parametrized by several parameters. The trace of a matrix representing a system of linear equations does not indicate the difficulty in finding a solution. The matrix trace is equivalent to the sum of the eigenvalues of the matrix.

12. Quantum Algorithm for Linear Systems I; Given a hermitian N -by- N matrix A , and a unit vector \vec{b} , the quantum algorithm for linear systems finds a sample vector \vec{x} , such that approximately $A\vec{x} = \vec{b}$. According to the section “Quantum Algorithm for Linear Systems,” following is building block of the quantum linear system solving algorithm. There are three building blocks of the quantum algorithm for solving systems of linear equations: Hamiltonian simulation, phase estimation, and filtering. To solve the eigenvalue equation $e^{iAt}|b\rangle = e^{i\lambda t}|b\rangle$, it is necessary to find the eigenvalues λ of matrix A . The phase estimation algorithm estimates the eigenvalues λ with accuracy that scales as $1/T$, where T is the amount of time that the system has evolved. To learn more about the HHL algorithm, we encourage to read “Quantum algorithm for linear systems of equations” [34]

13. Quantum Linear Systems Algorithm; Given a hermitian $N \times N$ matrix A , and a unit vector \vec{b} , the quantum algorithm for linear systems finds a sample vector \vec{x} , such that $A\vec{x} = \vec{b}$. The condition number κ is one of the parameters used to characterize the efficiency of the quantum linear system algorithm, and it is given by

$$\kappa = \|A\| \cdot \|A^{-1}\|, \quad (76)$$

where A^{-1} is the inverse of the matrix A . the condition number measure how far A is from an invertible matrix. The performance of the quantum linear system algorithm depends on the dimension N of \vec{x} , and the condition number κ . If the condition number is one, then the matrix is invertible. As κ becomes larger, the runtime of the algorithm increases, but the algorithm can still provide a quantum enhancement.

The quantum LPN algorithm is robust against noise, but it cannot identify where an error has occurred. It requires fewer queries than its classical counterpart for the same level of noise.

14. Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ) Computing; John Preskill introduced the concept of noisy intermediate-scale quantum (NISQ) computing. “Intermediate-scale” refers to computers sized between today’s 50-100 qubit machines and the large-scale, fault-tolerant machines of the future. “Noisy” refers to the fact that these machines will not be error-corrected [162]. NISQ hardware can be used to do tasks such as quantum simulations, in which qubits are coupled in some geometry, allowed to interact with each other, and measured. Regarding NISQ hardware, Even the most powerful classical supercomputers with petabytes of memory can only exactly simulate quantum systems comprising on the order of 50-70 qubits. There are many types of scientific calculations that can be efficiently mapped onto a quantum simulator. For calculating energy levels, classical computers do not have enough memory to describe the large combinatorial space quantum systems live in. More about NISQ read “Quantum Computing in the NISQ era and beyond” [27].

15. Variational Quantum Eigensolver (VQE); A variational quantum eigensolver was used in the sections to compute the energy of an atom or molecule, where the energy is given as the expectation value of the Hamiltonian. When using the VQE approach, the Hamiltonian is rewritten as a power series expansion of Pauli operators, σ_x , σ_y , and σ_z (or, X, Y, and Z gates). The expectation value of the total Hamiltonian can be written as a sum of energies associated with each Pauli operator term. VQE is a quantum/classical hybrid algorithm, which uses a

classical computer to generate trial wavefunctions, and a quantum computer to find their energy for a given Hamiltonian. The VQE is used for atomic and molecular systems [163], but it can, in principle, be used to find the ground state energy of any quantum system.

16. Quantum Algorithm for Linear Systems II; According to the section “Quantum Algorithm for Linear Systems,” Three building blocks of the quantum algorithm for solving systems of linear equations: Hamiltonian simulation, phase estimation, and filtering. Techniques of hamiltonian simulation are used to apply e^{iAt} to the state $|b\rangle$. This is done on time $O(\|A\|t)$, where $\|A\|$ is the norm of the matrix A .

Figure 11: Support Vectors

Figure 12: Quantum Simulator

32 Introduction to the Benchmarking Quantum States and Quantum Gates

In the last section, we introduced noisy intermediate-scale quantum computers and discussed examples of the types of algorithms that one might foresee running on them. NISQ computers are smaller scale quantum computers, say, 50 to 100, or 1,000 or a few thousand qubits that we either currently have, or will become available within the next several years. one of their main features is that They are not yet error corrected. This means that their utility is predominantly limited by their intrinsic gate fidelity, the types of gates enabled by the hardware, and, ultimately, the circuit depth they can support. As discussed in the last section, the quantum volume [115] is one metric that has been developed to compare different modalities and architectures. Essentially, it is a metric that attempts to capture the aggregate effect of the many characteristics that influence how well a particular quantum computer can implement a given algorithm. NISQ computers will likely implement small application-specific algorithms. For example, implementing an algorithm as a quantum coprocessor to a classical computer. we discuss an example of this last section with the variational quantum eigensolver and its application to determining the ground state energy of atoms and molecules. There is significant research currently in trying to develop useful algorithms where a small-scale quantum computer can implement a meaningful task within the circuit depth afforded by the processor. Finding such a commercialized application would be an important milestone in the development of quantum computing. The promise of universal quantum computation will require error protected qubits to perform computation with large circuit depth. whether for universal error protected computers, or for NISQ computers, it is imperative to understand how well our data operations perform at the physical level in the presence of noise. Thus, this section will take a deeper look at how we benchmark quantum

states in quantum gates to understand how well we can prepare, operate, and even measure a quantum system. The types of state and process tomography that we will discuss this section will be referenced throughout section four as we introduce fault-tolerant error correction and the threshold theorem. we will start with how to benchmark quantum states, and then we will use this state tomography to benchmark quantum gates, called process tomography [37]. we will then look at experimental, practical aspects of benchmarking, the overhead required for tomographic methods, and the use of randomized benchmarking protocols [164] to reduce that overhead. Finally, at the end of the section, we will have the opportunity to implement state tomography for ourselves on a real quantum computer.

33 Quantum State Tomography

Quantum state tomography is a vital experimental technique at the heart of debugging the operation of quantum computers, which essentially reads out a quantum state [40]. Recall that the quantum state of a single qubit is convenient to represent using the Bloch sphere picture. In this three-dimensional sphere, the north pole represents the 0 states of a qubit, while the south pole represents the 1 state. The positive x-axis point is the equal superposition of 0 and 1. the positive y-axis point is an equal superposition with a complex i phase factor. An arbitrary state, shown here as this green point, can be parameterized with two variables θ and ϕ . The Bloch sphere is also useful for representing density matrix states, as we have seen. The 0 and 1 states are the same. the surface of the sphere is the location of all density matrices made of a single quantum state that is a pure state. An equal statistical mixture of 0 and 1 is the density matrix represented by a point at the center of the sphere. This is the identity matrix. all other points in the unit ball represent other statistical mixtures. This background allows us a concrete visualization for the question answered by state tomography. Given many copies of a single qubit in-state ρ , how do we experimentally determine ρ ? For example, ρ could be at this point or is this one, and so, forth even possibly a point on the surface of the ball that is a pure state. The idea behind state tomography is that the point representing ρ can be represented as a vector r , which, for a qubit, is known as the Bloch vector. Mathematically, this is because any valid density matrix can be written as the linear combination of the identity matrix and the three Pauli matrices [165]. Recall that the Pauli matrices are denoted as σ_x , σ_y , and σ_z . It is convenient to write ρ in this way, as $1/2$ plus r dotted with the σ vector which is a vector of matrices all divided by 2. The key idea behind state tomography of a single qubit is to measure the three vector components R_x , R_y , and R_z . we claim that this can be done by recognizing that each component is the statistical expectation of a Pauli matrix. For example, R_z is the expectation value of σ_z . This can be seen by recalling the expectation is defined as a trace of the density matrix times the observable here, σ_z . And σ_z is $0,0$ minus $1,1$ matrices. So, the expectation value is just the $0,0$ entry of ρ minus the $1,1$ entry of ρ that is the projection along the z-axis, as we might expect. Mathematically, we can formally prove the claim by substituting the Bloch vector expression for ρ into the expectation value, expanding to see that the products of Pauli matrices then appear, and recognizing that all these matrices are traceless except σ_z times σ_z , meaning only the last term with r 's of z remains. the trace of the identity matrix gives 2, completing the proof. So, the procedure for state tomography of a single qubit reduces to measuring the Bloch vector components. For σ_z , this is done by obtaining the probability of a qubit being 1 in the computational basis. For σ_x , this is done by rotating minus 90 degrees around the y-axis to move plus x to plus z, then measuring. Moreover, for σ_y , we first rotate by 90 degrees about x to move plus y to plus z before measuring. The Bloch vector components are, thus, these three expectation values. The single-qubit picture of state tomography was worked

out in the 1950s for nuclear magnetic resonance, but its utility emerges for tomography of multi-qubit states. For two qubits, the density matrix may similarly be represented as a weighted sum of now tensor products of Pauli matrices. the measurement method is, as before, accomplished by rotating each qubit by 90 degrees before measurement, which, for two qubits, requires nine different measurements. State tomography has been experimentally realized in a wide number of physical systems. Shown here is one example from the 2003 experiment by Rainer Blatt's group at the University of Innsbruck, depicting the density matrix for two ions in the entangled state SS plus DD. we see that the real part of the density matrix has the expected for non-zero equal values with the off-diagonals being the signature of the entanglement of the state. we also see that the imaginary part of the density matrix is 0 to within experimental errors. This state tomography measurement was one of the first to be accomplished in a well-controlled multi-qubit system. many telegraphic measurements of even much larger quantum systems have been experimentally accomplished since these early results. State tomography remains an important foundational experimental tool today for diagnosing quantum states in quantum computers.

Quantum state tomography (QST) is a method used to characterize the quantum state of a physical system through a sequence of projective measurements on different bases. Due to the probabilistic nature of quantum states, a single projective measurement does not reveal complete information about an unknown state. Further, the act of measurement generally changes the system itself, limiting the utility of making additional measurements on the same system.

For these reasons, QST can only be successfully performed on a large ensemble of identically prepared quantum states. The availability of multiple identically prepared states enables the expectation values of measurements in different measurement bases to be estimated through repeated projective measurements. These estimated expectation values can then be used to infer the state of the system.

We will now illustrate the QST procedure where the unknown system is a single qubit. Regardless of the encoding, the density matrix of a single qubit, whether pure or mixed, can be represented as a sum of the identity matrix and the three Pauli matrices in the following form

$$\rho = \frac{1}{2}(I + r_x\sigma_x + r_y\sigma_y + r_z\sigma_z) = \frac{I + \vec{r} \cdot \vec{\sigma}}{2} \quad (77)$$

where I is the identity matrix in two dimensions and the three Pauli matrices being the previously introduced X, Y, and Z gates given by

$$X = \sigma_x = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad Y = \sigma_y = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad Z = \sigma_z = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (78)$$

The Pauli matrices are combined into a vector $\hat{\sigma} = (\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z)$, and this vector is acted on by $\vec{r} = (r_x, r_y, r_z)$, which is known as the Bloch vector. The Bloch vector determines the state of a single qubit, and it has magnitude $||\vec{r}|| \leq 1$, with $||\vec{r}|| = 1$ representing pure states.

The aim of single-qubit tomography is to determine \vec{r} for a given quantum state. This can be accomplished by relating the expectation value of a projective measurement on ρ along a direction \hat{m} to the components of \vec{r} using $\langle \sigma_m \rangle = \hat{m} \cdot \vec{r}$. Experimentally, this means projecting N identically prepared states represented by ρ along \hat{m} and calculating $\langle \sigma_m \rangle_E = (N_\uparrow - N_\downarrow)/N$ where $N_\uparrow(N_\downarrow)$ represents the number of times ρ was measured to be in the “up” state with eigenvalue 1 (“down” state with eigenvalue -1) along the \hat{m} direction. The subscript E indicates it is an estimate.

In the simplest scenario, called direct inversion, these expectation values are obtained along the Cartesian coordinates, such that \vec{r} can be reconstructed from them using $\vec{r}_E \approx (\langle \sigma_x \rangle_E, \langle \sigma_y \rangle_E, \langle \sigma_z \rangle_E)$.

While this approach works well, there are numerous sources of error that may impact the estimate of the Bloch vector. For example, state preparation errors, errors in measurement, and stochastic sampling errors may change the length of the Bloch vector, making it smaller or larger than the ideal value. Numerous techniques have been developed to account for these errors from independently measuring the state-preparation and measurement (SPAM) errors and then effectively “subtracting them off” to Bloch vector renormalization, more sophisticated forms of maximum likelihood estimation, and Bayesian estimation methods.

Extensions of the single-qubit QST procedure to multi-qubit states are straight forward, with the primary difference being that expectation values are over joint projective measurements. The density matrix for two-qubit states with qubit A and qubit B results as

$$\rho = \frac{1}{4}(I_A I_B + r_{xx}\sigma_x^A \sigma_x^B + r_{xy}\sigma_x^A \sigma_y^B + r_{xz}\sigma_x^A \sigma_z^B + r_{yx}\sigma_y^A \sigma_x^B + r_{yy}\sigma_y^A \sigma_y^B + r_{yz}\sigma_y^A \sigma_z^B + r_{zx}\sigma_z^A \sigma_x^B + r_{zy}\sigma_z^A \sigma_y^B + r_{zz}\sigma_z^A \sigma_z^B)$$

The examples for single-qubit and two-qubit QST indicate that there are three and nine measurement settings required, respectively, each estimating a Cartesian component of \vec{r} or a combination of them.

For n-qubits, a minimum of 3^n measurement settings are required. However, due to experimental constraints, in practice, the number of measurement settings required to perform QST scales closer to 4^n . This scaling is a consequence of individual evaluations of all entries of the density matrix representing an n-qubit state and hence 4^n entries.

Density Matrices on The Bloch Sphere I; The Bloch Sphere can also be used for representing single-qubit density matrices. The north pole corresponds to the projector $|0\rangle\langle 0|$, and south pole to the projector $|1\rangle\langle 1|$. The surface of the unit sphere (i.e., a sphere with unit radius) represents single-qubit density matrices that correspond. In the Bloch Sphere representation for density matrices, the matrices located in the surface of the unit sphere are given by the density matrix for $\rho = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$ of a pure quantum state $|\psi\rangle$. All of the density matrices inside the unit sphere are mixed states that can be written as a probabilistic combination of pure states, such as $\rho_M = \frac{1}{4}|0\rangle\langle 0| + \frac{3}{4}|1\rangle\langle 1|$. Since we are representing single-qubit density matrices, these cannot correspond to two-qubit states or entangled states.

34 Quantum State Fidelity

This is a brief note about quantum state fidelity, a measure of practical importance in experimental quantum computation. Recall that for pure quantum states, and the fidelity answers the question, how well does one state, say ψ , represent another state, say ϕ . The fidelity, F, is given by the absolute value of the overlap between the two states. Geometrically, the two states can be represented as unit vectors, so F is also interpretable as the projection of ϕ onto ψ or vice versa. F is thus a number between 0 and 1. Low fidelity means close to 0, while high fidelity means close to 1. Note that in the literature, sometimes an alternate definition is used, which is the square of the expression we have given to the left. Call this the square fidelity. It has the advantage that it is interpretable as a probability, though the original one reduces directly to the longstanding classical definition of fidelities between probability distributions. So, how fidelity measures extend to noisy quantum states? That is density matrices. Specifically, how well does

some density matrix ρ represent some state ϕ ? This is given by the square root of the overlap of ϕ and ρ , as shown here. It also turns out this is equal to the largest possible overlap between a purification of ρ and the state ϕ . If ψ is a purification of ρ , then it lives in a higher-dimensional space, such that forgetting the extra part produces ρ . See standard textbooks for more. Note that the fidelity between a density matrix and a pure state is commonly desired in evaluating experiments. ϕ is the ideal, theoretical state, while ρ is the actual noisy experimental result. These are just a few of the most useful expressions and properties of quantum state fidelities.

17. Noisy Quantum-State Fidelity; For noisy quantum states or density matrices, the quantum state fidelity characterizes how well an experimental density matrix ρ represents an ideal pure state $|\phi\rangle$. In this context, the fidelity is given by

$$F(|\phi\rangle, \rho) = \sqrt{\langle\phi|\rho|\phi\rangle}. \quad (79)$$

the quantum state fidelity is valid for.

- Fidelity represents the maximum projection probability of the state represented by ρ onto state $|\phi\rangle$.
- Fidelity equals the maximum overlap between a purification of ρ , across all states $|\psi\rangle$, and a pure state

$$F(|\phi\rangle, \rho) = \max_{|\psi\rangle} |\langle\psi|\phi\rangle| \quad (80)$$

- While $|\phi\rangle$ is a theoretically ideal pure state, ρ represents an actual state that is experimentally realized in the presence of noise.

35 System-Environment Model

For quantum error correction. We need to describe what an error is in a quantum mechanical context. More generally, let us try to describe all possible ways in which an input density matrix may evolve to an output density matrix. We will describe this via a map called E . E should be able to capture any physical process happening to this input state, not just unitary evolution, but non-unitary as well. The model which we all employ will be one which has two parts. We will suppose that we have a system, which may start at a pure state, say ψ for now. The system evolves in a unitary manner, but not just by itself. Rather, it is coupled to another state, which we will call the environment. Let us say the initial state of the environment is at e , a pure state. However, that need not be a pure state in general. The environment, let us say, is measured after this unitary transform. We will consider the measurement as happening on an orthonormal basis, e_0, e_1 , up through the dimension of the environment. The question is, what is the output state ρ ? We may write the output stage before the measurement by understanding that the unitary transform gives us U times e times ψ . It is convenient to invent some notation to describe this output state. We will use the circle-plus symbol to represent \circ . Using this, then we may write the output state ρ as a stochastic combination, where when the measurement result is 0, we get e_0 , U, e . this is an operator which acts on ψ . Alternatively, if the measurement result is 1, we get e_1 , U, e acting on ψ . This may be compactly written as a sum over all possible measurement outcomes where E_k, U, e . we emphasize is a matrix, an operator that acts on ψ . We call this operator an operation element. Historically, it is also called sometimes a Kraus operator. This operator E_k will play a principal role in our study of quantum error correction. We may also sometimes call them error operators. Concisely, we may write the output density matrix in this form as the sum over k $E_k \rho E_k$ dagger. This is the map E acting on ρ . The main constraint

is that the sum of the square of these operators $E_k^\dagger E_k$ must equal identity. We can check that this is true explicitly by substituting in the definition of E sub k , first using E_k^\dagger , and then E_k . Then noting that this term in the middle, the sum over $E_k E_k$, is an identity because this is a complete set of states for the basis of the environment. Thus, this sum overall gives the identity operator as desired. This setup with the system environment model giving us an equation that maps the input density matrix to the output density matrix is an important idea for quantum error correction. We will return to this model several times.

36 Quantum Operations

Let us now turn to a formal definition of what a quantum operation is. Recall that our goal is to describe in general what a legal map is for ρ going to E of ρ . Not just including unitary operations, we find that a map E is a valid quantum operation if and only if three criteria are met. First, the output density matrix must have a trace of 1. Second, E must be a linear and convex operation that is acting on a statistical mixture of density matrix inputs. It must also produce a statistical mixture and do so linearly. These two constraints are very natural from the standpoint of quantum mechanics being a linear matrix theory and also that the output must be a density matrix. So, therefore the map must be trace-preserving. A third criterion has two parts. That is that the output density matrix must also be positive. It is natural to require that the output of the map be positive. However, there is more. It turns out that one must also allow for the output to be positive, even when the map is only operating on the part of the system. Suppose we have a reference and a quantum system, R and Q , and then if E only acts on Q , then the output still must be positive, even though nothing was done to the reference part of the system. This concept is known as complete positivity, and it is much more general than just positivity. The complete positivity requirement can be understood and appreciated by looking at the quantum circuit representation of this criterion. The initial density matrix has E acting on one part, namely the quantum part, whereas the referenced part has nothing acting on it. Despite E only acting on this subsystem of the density matrix, it must still produce a valid output density matrix. Thus, this output state must be positive. We can further understand this criterion by looking at a specific example. Consider this particular map which acts on a single qubit, say a, b, c, d . it transforms that qubit by transposing the off-diagonal elements. It is straightforward to see that a positive density matrix is transformed into a positive density matrix by this transpose map. However, if we look at the operation of this map on a two-qubit system, where the first qubit has nothing happening to it, we may then, by looking at the four by four matrix, which corresponds to this transform we tensored with E , see that the operation of the trace acting on the second qubit flips these off-diagonal elements in each local quadrant of the four by four matrix. This is known as a partial transpose operation. Now let us apply this partial transpose operation to a specific density matrix, which is this $1, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 1$ state. That is, the density matrix for the two-qubit states $0,0$ plus $1,1$ normalized. The partial transpose produces this output density matrix state. The density matrix just has ones and zeros and looks tantalizingly legal and has a trace of one. However, it is not positive. It is an illegal state, not a density matrix. That is because the inner block matrix has an eigenvalue of minus 1. The transpose is thus a nonphysical operation, but it is still mathematically useful as a negative partial transpose test for entanglement.

Entanglement is a unique feature of quantum mechanics and can cause peculiar correlated quantum phenomena between distant quantum systems [24]. The information on the “strength” of the entanglement between two quantum systems is contained in the density matrix. As discussed in the section, a density matrix is trace-preserving and completely positive. Therefore,

a completely positive density matrix must possess exclusively non-negative eigenvalues and hence map all positive elements to positive elements.

To evaluate if two quantum systems A and B composing a quantum state are entangled, it is sufficient to test if the resultant quantum state is not separable. The separability of a quantum state can be evaluated with the following criterion, referred to as the Peres-Horodecki criterion. Transposing one quantum system but not the other, referred to as a partial transpose, can only result in a valid density matrix if the two quantum systems are indeed separable and hence not entangled. Suppose a density matrix ρ_{AB} representing quantum systems A and B is acted on by a partial transpose operation on quantum system B. We can write the resulting density matrix as $\rho_{AB}^{T_B}$.

Suppose there are two normalized quantum states $|\psi_A\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle$ and $|\psi_B\rangle = \gamma|0\rangle + \delta|1\rangle$ with complex amplitudes.

$$\rho_{AB} = \begin{pmatrix} |\alpha|^2 & \alpha\beta^* \\ \alpha^*\beta & |\beta|^2 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} |\gamma|^2 & \gamma\delta^* \\ \gamma^*\delta & |\delta|^2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} |\alpha|^2|\gamma|^2 & |\alpha|^2\gamma\delta^* & \alpha\beta^*|\gamma|^2 & \alpha\beta^*\gamma\delta^* \\ |\alpha|^2\gamma^*\delta & |\alpha|^2|\delta|^2 & \alpha\beta^*\gamma^*\delta & \alpha\beta^*|\delta|^2 \\ \alpha^*\beta|\gamma|^2 & \alpha^*\beta\gamma\delta^* & |\beta|^2|\gamma|^2 & |\beta|^2\gamma\delta^* \\ \alpha^*\beta\gamma^*\delta & \alpha^*\beta|\delta|^2 & |\beta|^2\gamma^*\delta & |\beta|^2|\delta|^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\rho_{AB}^{T_B} = \begin{pmatrix} |\alpha|^2 & \alpha\beta^* \\ \alpha^*\beta & |\beta|^2 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} |\gamma|^2 & \gamma^*\delta \\ \gamma\delta^* & |\delta|^2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} |\alpha|^2|\gamma|^2 & |\alpha|^2\gamma^*\delta & \alpha\beta^*|\gamma|^2 & \alpha\beta^*\gamma^*\delta \\ |\alpha|^2\gamma\delta^* & |\alpha|^2|\delta|^2 & \alpha\beta^*\gamma\delta^* & \alpha\beta^*|\delta|^2 \\ \alpha^*\beta|\gamma|^2 & \alpha^*\beta\gamma^*\delta & |\beta|^2|\gamma|^2 & |\beta|^2\gamma^*\delta \\ \alpha^*\beta\gamma\delta^* & \alpha^*\beta|\delta|^2 & |\beta|^2\gamma\delta^* & |\beta|^2|\delta|^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

The resulting density matrix $\rho_{AB}^{T_B}$ after transposing the B-qubit density matrix (compare the construction of ρ_{AB} and $\rho_{AB}^{T_B}$ above) represents the situation where quantum system A is unchanged, and quantum system B is flipped with respect to the xz-plane of the Bloch sphere. The trace of the density matrix $\rho_{AB}^{T_B}$ remains unchanged and is completely positive.

Now, suppose instead that the quantum systems are entangled, such as one of the four Bell states: $|\Psi^+\rangle = (|01\rangle + |10\rangle)/\sqrt{2}$. We then define the density matrix ρ_{AB} and the partially transposed version $\rho_{AB}^{T_B}$ (as before, the transpose of the B-qubit density matrix only).

$$\rho_{AB} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \rho_{AB}^{T_B} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Again, the trace the sum of the eigenvalues of the resulting matrix $\rho_{AB}^{T_B}$ remains unaffected. However, something has changed: we now find that one of the eigenvalues is negative.

To see this, we diagonalize $\rho_{AB}^{T_B}$:

$$\rho_{AB}^{T_B} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \xrightarrow{\text{diagonalization}} \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (81)$$

The diagonal elements of a diagonal matrix are its eigenvalues. As we can see, one eigenvalue is negative. Therefore, the partially-transposed matrix $\rho_{AB}^{T_B}$ is not a positive matrix. This ‘‘test’’

finding negative eigenvalues in $\rho_{AB}^{T_B}$ indicates that the original density matrix ρ_{AB} represents an entangled state.

Since we only require the sign of each eigenvalue, we can employ an alternative to diagonalization by using Sylvester's criterion. The criterion states that if all leading principal minors are positive, all eigenvalues are positive as well. However, first, what are leading principal minors? The leading principal minors are the determinants of the product of the eigenvalues of the upper-left 1-by-1 corner, the upper-left 2-by-2 corner. The protocol is shown below for the discussed matrix without the prefactor 1/2.

$$\begin{pmatrix} \boxed{0} & \boxed{0} & \boxed{0} & \boxed{1} \\ \boxed{0} & \boxed{1} & \boxed{0} & \boxed{0} \\ \boxed{0} & \boxed{0} & \boxed{1} & \boxed{0} \\ \boxed{1} & \boxed{0} & \boxed{0} & \boxed{0} \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{vmatrix} 0 \end{vmatrix} = 0, \quad \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 0, \quad \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 0, \quad \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{vmatrix} = -1$$

Figure 13: Formula

Since the last determinant is negative, we know that the eigenvalues of $\rho_{AB}^{T_B}$ are not all positive, and therefore ρ_{AB} represents an entangled state. This is useful because sometimes computing the principal minors is easier than diagonalizing the matrix.

With the ability to confirm if two quantum systems are entangled, one can further ask the question, "to what degree are they entangled?" The answer can be determined by probing the density matrix once more. If the partial trace of a density matrix results in a diagonal matrix with equal probabilities as entries, the quantum systems are referred to as maximally entangled.

For example, the partial trace on the entangled Bell state $|\Psi^+\rangle = (|01\rangle + |10\rangle)/\sqrt{2}$ yields:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_A &= Tr_B \left(\frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right) \\ &= Tr_B \left(\frac{|01\rangle\langle 01| + |10\rangle\langle 01| + |01\rangle\langle 10| + |10\rangle\langle 10|}{2} \right) \\ &= \frac{|0\rangle\langle 0|\langle 1|1\rangle + |1\rangle\langle 0|\langle 1|0\rangle + |0\rangle\langle 1|\langle 0|1\rangle + |1\rangle\langle 1|\langle 0|0\rangle}{2} \\ &= \frac{|0\rangle\langle 0| + |1\rangle\langle 1|}{2} = \frac{1}{2}I. \end{aligned}$$

The reduced density matrix indicates that $|\Psi^+\rangle$ is maximally entangled. This observation is true for all Bell states. The reduced density matrix describes a mixed state. As we have shown in a previous section, Bell states are pure states. Partial traces of pure entangled states represent mixed states.

In conclusion, a partial transpose can be used to evaluate if two quantum systems are entangled. If the resultant matrix is a density matrix, the quantum systems can be described

separately. The two quantum systems are maximally entangled if the partial trace of their density matrix results in a diagonal matrix and entries with equal probability. A quantum operation is linear, meaning that if the operation is performed over a statistical mixture of states with a given probability, it acts on every state and preserves the probability distribution of the mixture intact.

37 Quantum Gate Fidelity

Given the formalism for quantum noise, we may now see how the fidelity of gates versus states can be defined and measured in practice. The question is, how well does an experimental quantum operation E represent a theoretically desired unitary gate or circuit U . One simple answer to this is given by the minimum gate fidelity, also known just as gate fidelity and defined as the minimum fidelity between E acting on some input ψ , and U acting on the same input. This measure varies between 0 and 1. For example, consider a noisy X gate, which with probability p performs as Z instead of the desired X . Plugging E and U into the definition, we find the minimization is over an expectation of the Y operator. So, the final result is just the square root of $1 - p$. This agrees with our intuition that the failure probability is p . The minimum gate fidelity, unfortunately, can be hard to compute and may not reflect experimental impact in practice where the minimum is not dominant. Another measure is the entanglement fidelity of a gate, defined here by the fidelity between ϕ and the combination of E and the inverse of U acting on just half of ϕ . Here, ϕ is a maximally entangled state. We can understand the intuition behind this expression by looking at the quantum circuit realization, where it is evident that ideally, U^\dagger should cancel E and leave the entanglement between the two halves of the state intact. The entanglement fidelity thus measures how much entanglement is left intact by the quantum operation E modulo the ideal gate U . This measure is in many ways the gold standard of quantum gate fidelity because entanglement is the precious resource utilized by quantum computation. Unfortunately, it is largely impractical to measure directly today. The third measure of quantum gate fidelity is the average gate fidelity, given by computing the fidelity between U acting on a state ψ and E acting on the same state and averaging evenly over all states. This is evidently much easier to measure. However, how meaningful is it? It turns out there is a practical way to get the desired entanglement fidelity for experimental realizations. This is via a deep relationship between the entanglement fidelity of a gate and its average gate fidelity. The average fidelity is d times the entanglement fidelity plus 1 all divided by $d + 1$, where d is the dimension of the system. This means for a large dimension, they are the same. However, for qubits, they may be quite different. The neat thing is that this relationship gives a practical way to measure entanglement fidelity explicitly for a qubit. One can compare the outputs of the experimental and expected inputs σ_j , which are just the three Pauli matrices. Combining these three state tomography measurements gives the qubit gate fidelity. Generalizations of this to multi-qubit systems exist, and today, quantum gate fidelity is routinely measured as a natural part of practical quantum computation.

38 Quantum Process Tomography

Quantum state tomography is a method that allows noisy quantum states to be experimentally quantified. Quantum process tomography does the same for gates. This problem of knowing what actual quantum operation is being performed by a quantum apparatus is vital, for example, in evaluating the performance of quantum computing hardware [166–168]. Mathematically, the

problem is framed by recalling the operator sum representation of a quantum operation, shown here in terms of which the goal is to determine the operation elements e_{jk} . The e_{jk} are matrices. It is convenient to expand them in terms of a linear combination where σ_j are generalized Pauli matrices, and the C_{KJ} is an ordinary real number of coefficients. With this, we may then re-write the quantum operation e in this form, where the numerical coefficients form the so-called chi matrix. It becomes our goal to find this matrix. How many degrees of freedom are in the chi matrix? If the system ρ has dimension d , then the chi matrix has d to the fourth minus d squared degrees of freedom. Specifically, for example, for a single qubit, d equals 2, and thus, Chi has 12 parameters. Of these, three parametrize the possible single keyword unitary gates, and nine capture decoherence and damping. There are many more ways to decohere and damp than to be a perfect gate. For two qubits, the number of parameters grows quickly to become 240. Twenty years ago, when it was first computed this number, researchers are so surprised and shared with Peter Shor. For n qubits, the number is 2 to the 4 times n minus 2 to the 2 times n . Unsurprisingly, this is an exponential increase in the number of parameters. These parameters may be measured using the following four steps. First, prepare a basis set of linearly independent inputs, $\rho_{\text{sub } a}$. These may be the generalized Pauli matrices, for example. Second, send each $\rho_{\text{sub } a}$ into the apparatus. Formally, we expect this to depend on the chi matrix. We may expand its matrix coefficients in terms of other basis states. Third, measure each output using the quantum state tomography procedure and express each resulting density matrix again in terms of the basis states giving coefficients $c_{\text{sub } ab}$. Fourth, invert the linear equation relating $c_{\text{sub } ab}$ to the chi matrix to obtain the chi matrix. We are done in principle. This baseline method is known as standard quantum process tomography. There are some challenges, however. First, the exponential growth in the number of parameters makes this impractical for large numbers of qubits. The inversion of $c_{\text{sub } ab}$ is also difficult in practice when measurement results are noisy, as they inevitably are due to the statistical sampling needed for state tomography. This noise may also lead to chi matrices, which are invalid quantum operations because of violations of strict properties necessary. These operations must be completely positive and trace-preserving. Options are known for meeting these challenges. For example, one may employ statistical methods such as maximum likelihood optimization to find the closest legitimate inverse. One may also constrain the inversion always to produce a valid answer. Adding assumptions given by prior information about the operation may also dramatically reduce the number of parameters needed. As experimentalists build and test small quantum machines, quantum process tomography and its variants have become one of the most important and widely employed diagnostic tools in quantum computing laboratories.

As we have seen, quantum state fidelity quantifies the degree of similarity between an experimentally generated quantum state and its ideal counterpart. In this unit, we will study quantum process tomography, which uses quantum state tomography to characterize the fidelity of a quantum operation, such as a single gate operation or multiple gate operations. These types of operations are referred to as a “quantum process,” thus the nomenclature. For quantum computing, we are most often interested in the fidelity of the gates that comprise a universal gate set. However, more generally, quantum process tomography characterizes the quality of any quantum process.

Suppose a quantum state is manipulated with a known set of quantum gates. The ideal output quantum state can be calculated for a particular input state. We can further perform quantum state tomography to see how close our experimental output state matches our theoretical one. In practice, due to noise, we will often see a reduced quantum state fidelity. A method to investigate the underlying reasons for this reduced fidelity for any input state is called quantum process tomography (QPT), also referred to as quantum gate tomography.

QPT essentially implements quantum state tomography for a set of input states that spans the space of all input states for a given system. We will focus on systems of qubits. Note that quantum state tomography (QST), as we have seen, performs repeated measurements of an identically prepared input state across a basis that spans all output states. As we have seen, spanning this space requires approximately $2^{2n} = 4^n$ matrix elements to be estimated, where n is the number of qubits. With QPT, this state tomography is now performed for a set of input states that generally spans the same space, that is, another 4^n elements. Since all output elements must be estimated for each input element, the number of total elements that must be estimated is $4^n \times 4^n = 4^{2n}$. As we discuss, there are a few constraints that may reduce this number by a small amount, because the quantum process must take quantum states to other valid quantum states. In the language of density matrices, there are two constraints on a quantum process: it must be (1) completely positive, which means that the density matrix after the process still has positive eigenvalues, and (2) trace-preserving because density matrices must have a trace of 1. In total, this constrains 4^n of the elements we are trying to find, so there are $4^{2n} - 4^n$ elements to determine in total. Since the number of measurements scales exponentially in the number of qubits, QPT becomes intractable on larger systems of qubits.

The result of QPT is reported as a fidelity of the realized gate with respect to the desired quantum gate. Obtaining this fidelity is related to the construction of a “superoperator” and its matrix form. A superoperator is a map of density matrices to density matrices; for example, the density matrices of the input basis states to the density matrices for the output basis states. From this experimentally determined mapping, one can define a gate fidelity that describes how well the experimentally implemented gate matches the desired, ideal operation.

39 Tomography and Characterization

At a high level, running quantum algorithms involves applying a series of gate operations to a set of quantum bits in order to generate quantum states. In other sections, we have seen details on those algorithms, how they work, and what problems they are designed to solve. However, before we start applying algorithms, we need to verify that our gates are operating in the way we expect them to and that we are creating the states we intend to create. Sounds simple, but is it? To understand how to characterize a quantum state, we first need to understand how to represent a quantum state, and what happens when we perform a measurement. A pure quantum state can be expressed as a sum of basis states where the coefficients of the sum are complex, and the magnitude of the coefficients squared must sum to one. For a qubit, this means that there are two parameters that characterize a quantum state. These parameters correspond well to a point on the surface of a sphere. This is known as the Bloch sphere representation of a qubit state. However, any measurement of this quantum state projects the qubit into either the state up, the point at the top of the sphere, or the state down, the point at the bottom of the sphere. The probability of measuring up or down is given by how much of the qubit state was in the top or bottom half of the Bloch sphere. In the state representation, this means that the magnitude of the coefficient squared is the probability of measuring that particular state. In a single quantum measurement, we only obtain a single bit of information, and the original state is lost. So, how do we measure a quantum state given these constraints? The answer is tomography. Tomography means reconstructing something from many pieces of incomplete data. It is a word that we often hear from the medical field, such as X-ray tomography. True to the word, X-ray tomography is the process of building a 3D image of a person’s body from 2D X-rays taken from a number of different directions. To measure a quantum state, we perform quantum state tomography, reconstructing a quantum state from multiple incomplete measurements. To see

how tomography works, we use as an example, the maximal superposition state, which is a state on the equator of the Bloch sphere. If we measure the qubit, it will find it up or down with equal probability. If we prepare the state, again, and measure, we will, again, measure up or down with equal probability. Repeating this many times, we will get a histogram of measurements that should converge to 50/50. This is the start of a state tomography experiment because we then know that the qubit lies on the equator of the Bloch sphere, but we do not know the angle of the state ϕ . Therefore, we apply a $\pi/2$ rotation to the state around the x-axis in the Bloch sphere. This mixes ϕ along the measurement axis. If we repeat this procedure many times, we can construct a new histogram and determine ϕ . For example, if the state originally lied along the x-axis in the equator, the histogram after applying the pulse will, again, be 50/50. If the state originally lied on the y-axis in the Bloch sphere, the histogram after the pulse will be 100% in the upstate. This is the essence of quantum state tomography, but note the fuzziness of the process. we needed to take enough data so that we could get a representative histogram, but how much data does that require? What if the measurement itself has a bias? Also, we need to be able to apply a perfect $\pi/2$ pulse and prepare the exact same state many times. These are some of the challenges with quantum tomography. The above example is oversimplified because a general quantum state can also include classical probabilities. This is represented by a density matrix, which is a sum of the classical probabilities of being in a particular quantum state. These probabilities must sum to one. For a qubit, the density matrix is a two by two matrix, which is given as an example for our superposition state. If the state was instead a classical probabilistic state, that is a coin flip between up and down, the off-diagonal elements of the density matrix go to zero. In the Bloch sphere representation, this means that the qubit state can also lie inside the sphere. Because there are more terms in a density matrix, we need to do more measurements than in the example that was given before. The general procedure for quantum state tomography given a completely unknown state that can be prepared many times is shown. we perform measurements on the state after applying no pulse, a $\pi/2$ pulse along the x-axis, and a $\pi/2$ pulse along the y-axis. From these measurements, we get three numbers. These are fed into a classical optimization routine that obtains the most likely density matrix that corresponds to a physical quantum state. For end cubic quantum state tomography, we need to do three to the power of N measurements, and the density matrix has four to the power of N elements. Clearly, tomography is not a scalable procedure as the number of qubits grows. What about measuring a process, a gate versus a state? If we have a Blackbox classical gate with two inputs and one output, we construct a truth table. we input all possible states and measure the outputs. This is straightforward for the classical gate because, one, we can exactly measure the output state, and two, there are only four input states. The quantum case is similar, except we need to input quantum states and measure the output quantum states. As we know from the previous part of the discussion, measuring quantum states requires quantum state tomography. Therefore, quantum process tomography is just the repeated application of quantum state tomography, three to the power of N times. How do we represent a quantum process? Pure quantum processes or unitary matrices that take an input state to an output state. A general quantum process maps an input density matrix to an output density matrix. There is a matrix form for these general quantum processes, but this matrix has 16 to the power of N elements. therefore, it is very difficult to represent a process involving more than a handful of qubits, but what if we just want to verify the gate is doing what we expected to be doing? Moreover, we do not want to characterize the gateway fully. we just need to know how close it is to the gate that we want. This is analogous to getting in a grade on a test. A grade is a single number that tells us how we performed. However, it does not indicate what we did wrong or how we would need to fix it. What kind of grade can we give a gate? One metric is known as gate fidelity. This fidelity is related to a similar thing called state fidelity. The

state fidelity is the overlap between two quantum states. Gate fidelity is the overlap between the output states of our gate versus the output states of the expected gate averaged over all possible input states. Now, this might not sound easier than tomography. However, it can be shown that there is a simple experimental procedure to perform this type of measurement by repeated application of gates to a set of qubits starting in the ground state. This is known as randomized benchmarking, and we will go over the details of this in the next section. Single-Qubit State Tomography; Single-qubit state tomography is a procedure that enables one to reconstruct the density matrix of a given system. When implementing single-qubit state tomography all of the steps one makes in performing single-qubit state tomography.

- The state of the system is measured in the bases of the three Pauli matrices.
- The probabilities of projection onto the eigenstates of the three Pauli matrices are calculated based on the measurement results.
- The elements of the reconstructed density matrix are given by combinations of the expectation values of the three Pauli matrices.

40 Randomized Benchmarking

In the section on tomography, we discuss that to characterize a quantum process fully requires an exponential number of measurements. Additionally, tomographic methods have many built-in assumptions since we are trying to reconstruct a process from slices of data. Instead, we would like a scalable method to verify that our gates are operating as we expect without needing to do full characterization. One such method is known as randomized benchmarking [28, 164, 169, 170]. Randomized benchmarking starts by constructing a circuit from gates randomly selected from a particular set of gates known as the Clifford group. The Clifford group is, as the name suggests, a mathematical group, and so, a gate formed from composite Clifford gates is itself a Clifford gate. The Clifford group includes commonly used gates, such as the π pulse, the $\pi/2$ pulses, and the 2 qubits CNOT gate. The Clifford group is not an esoteric set of gates. It can, for example, be used to create a maximally entangled Bell state. The Clifford group has two important properties for the purposes of randomized benchmarking. First, it is classically easy to compute the gate formed from a sequence of Clifford gates. This is known as the Gottesman-Knill theorem. This theorem means that the Clifford group is not a universal set of gates for quantum computing. However, it is still considered a representative set of gates, as is evident from the list of gates we mentioned. All that is needed to extend the Clifford group to a universal set of gates is a T gate, a $\pi/4$ z rotation. The second relevant property of the Clifford group is that randomly sampling from the group ensures that we are doing a fair random sampling of the states around the Bloch sphere. we will elaborate on this point later. The first point is important because the second step of a randomized benchmarking experiment is to compute the inverse gate for the entire random sequence that we have just selected. In other words, we are constructing a large sequence of gates that is the main purpose is to do nothing, and this is precisely the point of randomized benchmarking. If we apply the sequence to a set of qubits starting in the ground state, we measure the population of each qubit in the excited state after applying the sequence of gates. For a single qubit in the Bloch sphere representation, we start in the downstate, and we apply the sequence of gates that takes the state around the Bloch sphere, then ideally, we return back to the downstate. This highlights the importance of the second property of the Clifford group on average, and the random Clifford sequences will fairly sample the entire space of the Bloch sphere. we perform this procedure for different sequence lengths and very clearly observe that as the number of gates increases, the less likely the qubit is to return to the ground state. For

extremely long sequences, the qubit state is completely depolarized. The state is equally likely to be up or down. This process is repeated again for a new random sequence, and the results are averaged. Because the Clifford group fairly samples the Bloch sphere, the average curve will fit an exponential decay. Unlike tomography, errors in the measurement or errors in the preparation of the initial state of the qubits do not affect our ability to fit this decay coefficient. How does this decay coefficient allow us to verify the gate? Well, the decay coefficient is simply related to a quantity known as the average gate fidelity. The average gate fidelity is a metric that tells us how close our gate is to the ideal gate we were attempting to implement. Because we sample from the Clifford group, we actually measure the average fidelity of the average Clifford gate. Specifically, gate fidelity is defined as the state fidelity of the output state from the gate with respect to the output state of the ideal gate, averaged over all input states, and state fidelity is defined as the overlap between states. For pure states, this is the square of the inner product of the state vectors. Randomized benchmarking is a versatile procedure that can be used to characterize single or multi-qubit circuits, but it also has variants that can be used for more specialized measurements. If we want to measure the fidelity of an individual Clifford gate, we can perform randomized benchmarking and then repeat the experiment again with the specific gate in between each Clifford of the sequence. This is known as interleaved randomized benchmarking. We can also perform independent benchmarking in parallel on different subsystems, which is known as simultaneous randomized benchmarking. This is a method for a qualitative understanding of crosstalk. Randomized benchmarking does not tell us what the errors are or how to fix them. It only gives us a single number to characterize the average performance of our multi-qubit circuit. Therefore, to improve the performance of quantum circuits, randomized benchmarking must be part of a larger toolbox of error amplification and detection routines. Fidelity from Randomized Benchmarking; There is more than one way to characterize the fidelity of a quantum gate. However, for practical reasons, not all of them are equivalently easy to measure. The gate fidelity can be more experimentally feasible to characterize by the average fidelity is easy to calculate using only state tomography. For example, for $d = 2$, it can be done using state tomography to determine the expected values of the three Pauli matrices. For d greater than two, these are generalizations.

41 Single-Qubit State Tomography: Theory

In this IBM Q experience, we will implement quantum state tomography for a single-qubit system. In the first section, we will discuss the basic concepts necessary to understand the single-qubit quantum state tomography.

In Single-Qubit State Tomography: Example, we will follow a step-by-step demonstration of how to implement single-qubit state tomography using QASM [171, 172] and IBM Q for a particular density matrix.

In Single-Qubit State Tomography: Experience, we will implement quantum state tomography for a given single-qubit quantum state. To do this, we will

1. Write the QASM codes to measure the system in each one of the bases of the Pauli matrices X, Y, and Z.
2. Use the simulation results to compute the probabilities of projecting the state to each one of the eigenstates of the Pauli matrices.
3. Calculate the expectation values of the Pauli matrices using the projection probabilities.
4. Reconstruct the density matrix from the expectation values.

Arbitrary single-qubit density matrices

An arbitrary single-qubit density matrix ρ can be written in terms of the parameters, $S_0, S_1, S_2,$ and $S_3,$ as

$$\rho = \frac{1}{2}S_0\sigma_0 + \frac{1}{2}S_1\sigma_1 + \frac{1}{2}S_2\sigma_2 + \frac{1}{2}S_3\sigma_3, \quad (82)$$

where σ_0 is the 2-by-2 identity matrix, and $\sigma_1, \sigma_2,$ and σ_3 are the Pauli matrices X, Y, and Z,

$$\sigma_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \sigma_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \sigma_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \sigma_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (83)$$

The S_i parameters are given by the expectation values of the Pauli matrices, $S_i = Tr(\sigma_i\rho)$.

Let us recall that the probability of projecting ρ onto a pure state $|\psi\rangle$ is $P_{|\psi\rangle} = \langle\psi|\rho|\psi\rangle$. The expectation values $Tr(\sigma_i\rho)$ can be written in terms of the probabilities of projecting ρ to the eigenstates of the Pauli matrices,

$$\begin{aligned} S_0 &= P_{|0\rangle} + P_{|1\rangle} = 1 \\ S_1 &= P_{\frac{|0\rangle+|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}} - P_{\frac{|0\rangle-|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}} \\ S_2 &= P_{\frac{|0\rangle+i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}} - P_{\frac{|0\rangle-i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}} \\ S_3 &= P_{|0\rangle} - P_{|1\rangle} \end{aligned} \quad (84)$$

Measurement Basis:

To reconstruct an implemented density matrix ρ , we need to compute the expectation values of the three Pauli matrices X, Y, and Z. To do this, we need to measure the system on the basis of each Pauli matrix. The IBM Q online composer comes with one pre-defined measurement. This measurement projects the state of the system to one of the eigenstates of Z (or σ_3) $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$. The IBM Q composer symbol for this measurement is

Figure 14: Measurement-Sigma Z

Once the system is measured, the IBM Q platform outputs the measurement probabilities $P_{|0\rangle}$ and $P_{|1\rangle}$. For more information on how to interpret the IBM Q measurement results, read IBM Q Tutorial.

For measuring in the X (or σ_1) basis, and thereby projecting the system to $\frac{|0\rangle+|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ or $\frac{|0\rangle-|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$, a Hadamard gate H has to be placed just before the pre-defined measurement,

Figure 15: Measurement-Sigma X

In this way, the IBM Q outputs are now equivalent to $P_{\frac{|0\rangle+|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}}$ and $P_{\frac{|0\rangle-|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}}$.

To measure in the Y (or σ_2) basis, and thereby projecting the system to $\frac{|0\rangle+i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ or $\frac{|0\rangle-i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$, a Hadamard gate H and phase gate S have to be placed just before the measurement,

Figure 16: Measurement-Sigma Y

By adding these two gates, the IBM Q outputs are now equivalent to $P_{\frac{|0\rangle+i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}}$ and $P_{\frac{|0\rangle-i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}}$.

Density Matrix Reconstruction:

The density matrix ρ can be reconstructed from the expectation values of the Pauli matrices as

$$\rho^E = \frac{1}{2}S_0\sigma_0 + \frac{1}{2}S_1\sigma_1 + \frac{1}{2}S_2\sigma_2 + \frac{1}{2}S_3\sigma_3, = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2}S_0 + \frac{1}{2}S_3 & \frac{1}{2}S_1 - \frac{1}{2}iS_2 \\ \frac{1}{2}S_1 + \frac{1}{2}iS_2 & \frac{1}{2}S_0 - \frac{1}{2}S_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (85)$$

or

$$\rho^E = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}S_3 & \frac{1}{2}S_1 - \frac{1}{2}iS_2 \\ \frac{1}{2}S_1 + \frac{1}{2}iS_2 & \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}S_3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (86)$$

Where we have used that $S_0 = 1$.

42 Single-Qubit State Tomography: Example

State preparation:

Consider the single-qubit quantum state

$$|\psi_1\rangle = TH|0\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ \frac{1+i}{2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (87)$$

The figure below shows the generation of state $|\psi_1\rangle$ using the IBM Q composer.

Figure 17: Generation of state

```

1 The QASM code that generates this quantum circuit is
2 include ‘‘qelib1.inc’’;
3 qreg q[5];
4 creg c[5];
5 // State Preparation
6 h q[0];
7 t q[0];

```

Quantum state tomography allows us to verify that the quantum state was prepared correctly. To do quantum state tomography, we start by writing the density matrix representation of the quantum state,

$$\rho_1 = |\psi_1\rangle\langle\psi_1|, \quad (88)$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ \frac{1+i}{2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1-i}{2} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (89)$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{4}\sqrt{2} - \frac{1}{4}i\sqrt{2} \\ \frac{1}{4}\sqrt{2} + \frac{1}{4}i\sqrt{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (90)$$

We write ρ_1 using numerical values to make it easier to compare with the reconstructed density matrix from the simulation results,

$$\rho_1 \approx \begin{pmatrix} 0.5 & 0.35355 - 0.35355i \\ 0.35355 + 0.35355i & 0.5 \end{pmatrix} \quad (91)$$

Measurement Basis:

The state $|\psi_1\rangle$ was simulated in the IBM Q composer 1024 times using the IBM Q 5 Tenerife backend. In order to reconstruct the density matrix $\rho_1 = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi_1|$, and verify the state preparation, we measured qubit q[0] in each of the Pauli-matrix bases.

The figure below shows the quantum circuit implemented to measure ρ_1 in the σ_3 or Z basis:

Figure 18: Sigma Z

```
1 The QASM code that generates this circuit is:  
2 include "qelib1.inc";  
3 qreg q[5];  
4 creg c[5];  
5 // State Preparation  
6 h q[0];  
7 t q[0];  
8 // Z or sigma\_3 basis  
9 measure q[0] $->$ c[0];
```

The figure below shows the quantum circuit implemented to measure ρ_1 in the σ_1 or X basis:

Figure 19: Sigma X

```

1 The QASM code that generates this circuit is:
2 include "qelib1.inc";
3 qreg q[5];
4 creg c[5];
5 // State Preparation
6 h q[0];
7 t q[0];
8 // X or sigma\1 basis
9 h q[0];
10 measure q[0] $->$ c[0];

```

The figure below shows the quantum circuit implemented to measure ρ_1 in the σ_2 or Y basis:

Figure 20: Sigma Y

```

1 The QASM code that generates this circuit is:
2 include "qelib1.inc";
3 qreg q[5];
4 creg c[5];
5 // State Preparation
6 h q[0];
7 t q[0];
8 // Y or sigma\_2 basis
9 sdg q[0];
10 h q[0];
11 measure q[0] $->$ c[0];

```

IBM Q Results:

The figure below shows the simulation results obtained when qubit $q[0]$ was measured in the σ_3 basis. The system was projected to state $|0\rangle$ 489 times, and to state $|1\rangle$ 535 times.

Figure 21: BAR-Measurement Sigma Z

The figure below shows the simulation results obtained when qubit q[0] was measured in the σ_1 basis. The system was projected to state $\frac{|0\rangle+|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ 835 times, and to state $\frac{|0\rangle-|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ 189 times.

Figure 22: BAR-Measurement Sigma X

The figure below shows the simulation results obtained when qubit q[0] was measured in the σ_2 basis. The system was projected to state $\frac{|0\rangle+i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ 845 times, and to state $\frac{|0\rangle-i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ 179 times.

Figure 23: BAR-Measurement Sigma Y

We can compute the projection probabilities by normalizing the number of projections to a particular state by the total number of simulations 1024.

Table 3: Projection probabilities

Projection probability	IBM Q results
$P_{ 0\rangle}$	0.478
$P_{ 1\rangle}$	0.522
$P_{\frac{ 0\rangle+ 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}}$	0.815
$P_{\frac{ 0\rangle- 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}}$	0.185
$P_{\frac{ 0\rangle+i 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}}$	0.825
$P_{\frac{ 0\rangle-i 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}}$	0.175

Matrix Reconstruction:

We use our results of the projection probabilities to compute the expectation values of the Pauli matrices,

$$\begin{aligned} S_1 &= 0.815 - 0.185 = 0.630, \\ S_2 &= 0.825 - 0.175 = 0.650, \\ S_3 &= 0.478 - 0.522 = -0.044. \end{aligned}$$

Once we have the experimental values of the S_i parameters, we reconstruct the density matrix

$$\rho_1^E = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}S_3 & \frac{1}{2}S_1 - \frac{1}{2}iS_2 \\ \frac{1}{2}S_1 + \frac{1}{2}iS_2 & \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}S_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0.478 & 0.315 - 0.325i \\ 0.315 + 0.325i & 0.522 \end{pmatrix}$$

We copy Equation (91) here for convenience,

$$\rho_1 \approx \begin{pmatrix} 0.5 & 0.35355 - 0.35355i \\ 0.35355 + 0.35355i & 0.5 \end{pmatrix}$$

Comparing Equation (91) with Equation (92), we can see that ρ_1 is in good agreement with the reconstructed density matrix ρ_1^E . The results are not identical due to the presence of noise and statistical sampling error. We can conclude that state preparation was successful.

43 Single-Qubit State Tomography: Experience I

State Preparation:

Consider the single-qubit quantum state

$$|\psi_1\rangle = S^\dagger H |0\rangle, = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -i \end{pmatrix}. \quad (92)$$

The figure below shows the generation of state $|\psi_2\rangle$ using the IBM Q composer.

Figure 24: Generation of state

```

1 The QASM code that generates this circuit is
2 include ‘‘qelib1.inc’’;
3 qreg q[5];
4 creg c[5];
5 // State Preparation
6 h q[0];
7 sdg q[0];

```

The density matrix representation of the quantum state $|\psi_2\rangle$ is given by

$$\rho_2 = |\psi_2\rangle\langle\psi_2| = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -i \end{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -i \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0.5 & 0.5i \\ -0.5i & 0.5 \end{pmatrix} \quad (93)$$

In the following three IBM Q assessments, we will measure qubit q[0] in each of the Pauli-matrix bases: the σ_1 basis, σ_2 basis, and σ_3 basis (equivalently, the X basis, Y basis, and Z basis, respectively). In each case, we will simulate and run the circuit 1024 times using the IBM Q 5 Tenerife backend.

18. Measuring in the Z Basis; The quantum circuit below shows the state preparation of $|\psi_2\rangle$ and its measurement in the σ_3 or Z basis.

Figure 25: Sigma Z

Write the QASM code that implements this quantum circuit.

```

1 include "qelib1.inc";
2 qreg q[5];
3 creg c[5];
4 // State preparation
5 h q[0];
6 sdg q[0];
7 // Measurement in Z
8 measure q[0] -> c[0];

```

Solution:

In the bar diagram, the bar for the measurement result labeled 00000 corresponds to the number of times that $q[0]$ was projected to state $|0\rangle$, and the bar for the measurement result labeled 00001 corresponds to the number of times that $q[0]$ was projected to state $|1\rangle$. With these results, we can now compute the projection probabilities $P_{|0\rangle}$ and $P_{|1\rangle}$.

19. Measuring in the X Basis; The quantum circuit below shows the state preparation of $|\psi_2\rangle$ and its measurement in the σ_1 or X basis.

Figure 26: Sigma X

Write the QASM code that implements this quantum circuit.

```

1 include "qelib1.inc";
2 qreg q[5];
3 creg c[5];
4 // State preparation
5 h q[0];
6 sdg q[0];
7 // Measurement in X
8 h q[0];
9 measure q[0] -> c[0];

```

Solution:

In the bar diagram, the bar for the measurement result labeled 00000 corresponds to the number of times that $q[0]$ was projected to state $\frac{|0\rangle+|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$, and the bar for the measurement result labeled 00001 corresponds to the number of times that $q[0]$ was projected to state $\frac{|0\rangle-|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$. With these results, we can now compute the projection probabilities $P_{\frac{|0\rangle\pm|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}}$.

20. Measuring in the Y Basis; The quantum circuit below shows the state preparation of $|\psi_2\rangle$ and its measurement in the σ_2 or Y basis.

Figure 27: Sigma Y

Write the QASM code that implements this quantum circuit.

```

1 include "qelib1.inc";
2 qreg q[5];
3 creg c[5];
4 // State preparation
5 h q[0];
6 sdg q[0];
7 // Measurement in Y
8 sdg q[0];
9 h q[0];
10 measure q[0] -> c[0];

```

Solution:

In the bar diagram, the bar for the measurement result labeled 00000 corresponds to the number of times that $q[0]$ was projected to state $\frac{|0\rangle+i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$, and the bar for the measurement result labeled 00001 corresponds to the number of times that $q[0]$ was projected to state $\frac{|0\rangle-i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$. With these results, we can now compute the projection probabilities $P_{\frac{|0\rangle\pm i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}}$.

44 Single-Qubit State Tomography: Experience II

Expectation Values of the Pauli Matrices:

In order to obtain the expectation values of the Pauli matrices, we need to compute the probabilities of projecting the system onto each one of the eigenstates of the Pauli matrices. Each probability will be given by the quotient of the number of times the system was projected onto one of the eigenstates and the total number of times the state was projected. In this example, we will always simulate and run the experiments 1024 times.

As an example, if the system is projected onto state $|0\rangle$ #0 times and to state $|1\rangle$ #1 times, then the corresponding projection probabilities are

$$\begin{aligned} P_{|0\rangle} &= \frac{\#0}{1024} \\ P_{|1\rangle} &= \frac{\#1}{1024} \end{aligned} \tag{94}$$

21. Z Basis Projection Probabilities; Using the simulation results that we obtained measuring $|\psi_2\rangle$ in the Z basis, compute the values of the following projection probabilities $P_{|0\rangle}$ and $P_{|1\rangle}$. Approximate our values using three significant figures.

$$\begin{aligned} P_{|0\rangle} &= 0.5 \\ P_{|1\rangle} &= 0.5 \end{aligned} \tag{95}$$

Solution:

The projection probabilities to states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ can be analytically computed as

$$\begin{aligned} P_{|0\rangle} &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0.5 & 0.5i \\ -0.5i & 0.5 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = 0.5 \\ P_{|1\rangle} &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0.5 & 0.5i \\ -0.5i & 0.5 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = 0.5 \end{aligned}$$

If in the IBM Q simulation the state was projected to $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ #0 and #1 times respectively, the projection probabilities are given by

$$\begin{aligned} P_{|0\rangle} &= \frac{\#0}{1024} \\ P_{|1\rangle} &= \frac{\#1}{1024} \end{aligned} \tag{96}$$

Note that since we are using our IBM Q simulation results for calculating projection probabilities, the accepted answers have a 0.05 tolerance.

22. X Basis Projection Probabilities; Using the simulation results that we obtained measuring $|\psi_2\rangle$ in the X basis, compute the values of the following projection probabilities $P_{\frac{|0\rangle+|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}}$. Approximate our values using three significant figures.

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\frac{|0\rangle+|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}} &= 0.5 \\ P_{\frac{|0\rangle-|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}} &= 0.5 \end{aligned} \tag{97}$$

Solution:

The projection probabilities to states $\frac{|0\rangle+|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ and $\frac{|0\rangle-|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ can be analytically computed as

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\frac{|0\rangle+|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0.5 & 0.5i \\ -0.5i & 0.5 \end{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = 0.5 \\ P_{\frac{|0\rangle-|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0.5 & 0.5i \\ -0.5i & 0.5 \end{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix} = 0.5 \end{aligned}$$

Because of the Hadamard gate before the pre-defined measurement, the result of the number of times that the state was projected to $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$, #0 and #1, now correspond to the number of times the state was projected to $\frac{|0\rangle+|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ and $\frac{|0\rangle-|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ respectively.

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\frac{|0\rangle+|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}} &= \frac{\#0}{1024} \\ P_{\frac{|0\rangle-|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}} &= \frac{\#1}{1024} \end{aligned} \quad (98)$$

Note that since we are using our IBM Q simulation results for calculating projection probabilities, the accepted answers have a 0.05 tolerance.

23. Y Basis Projection Probabilities; Using the simulation results that we obtained measuring $|\psi_2\rangle$ in the Y basis, compute the values of the following projection probabilities $P_{\frac{|0\rangle\pm i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}}$. Approximate our values using three significant figures.

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\frac{|0\rangle+i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}} &= 0 \\ P_{\frac{|0\rangle-i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}} &= 1 \end{aligned} \quad (99)$$

Solution:

The projection probabilities to states $\frac{|0\rangle+i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ and $\frac{|0\rangle-i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ can be analytically computed as

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\frac{|0\rangle+i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -i \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0.5 & 0.5i \\ -0.5i & 0.5 \end{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ i \end{pmatrix} = 0 \\ P_{\frac{|0\rangle-i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & i \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0.5 & 0.5i \\ -0.5i & 0.5 \end{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -i \end{pmatrix} = 1 \end{aligned}$$

Because of the Hadamard gate and S^\dagger gates before the pre-defined measurement, the result of the number of times that the state was projected to $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$, #0 and #1, now correspond to the number of times the state was projected to $\frac{|0\rangle+i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ and $\frac{|0\rangle-i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ respectively.

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\frac{|0\rangle+i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}} &= \frac{\#0}{1024}, \\ P_{\frac{|0\rangle-i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}} &= \frac{\#1}{1024}, \end{aligned} \quad (100)$$

Note that since we are using our IBM Q simulation results for calculating projection probabilities, the accepted answers have a 0.05 tolerance.

Expectation Values:

Compute the expectation values of the Pauli matrices σ_1 , σ_2 , and σ_3 using the following equations,

$$S_1 = P_{\frac{|0\rangle+|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}} - P_{\frac{|0\rangle-|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}}, \quad (101)$$

$$S_2 = P_{\frac{|0\rangle+i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}} - P_{\frac{|0\rangle-i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}}, \quad (102)$$

$$S_3 = P_{|0\rangle} - P_{|1\rangle}. \quad (103)$$

24. Expectation Values for Pauli Matrices: X; Enter our numerical result for the expectation value of the Pauli matrix X or $\sigma_1 = 0$.

Solution:

The analytical result of the expectation value of X or σ_1 is given by

$$S_1 = P_{\frac{|0\rangle+|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}} - P_{\frac{|0\rangle-|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}}, = 0.5 - 0.5, = 0.$$

Since we are using our IBM Q simulation results for calculating the expectation value, the accepted correct answers have a 0.07 tolerance,

25. Expectation Values for Pauli Matrices: Y; Enter our numerical result for the expectation value of the Pauli matrix Y or $\sigma_2 = -1$.

Solution:

The analytical result of the expectation value of Y or σ_2 is given by

$$S_2 = P_{\frac{|0\rangle+i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}} - P_{\frac{|0\rangle-i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}}, = 0 - 1.0, = -1.0.$$

26. Expectation Values for Pauli Matrices: Z; Enter our numerical result for the expectation value of the Pauli matrix Z or $\sigma_3 = -0$.

Solution:

The analytical result of the expectation value of Z or σ_3 is given by

$$S_3 = P_{|0\rangle} - P_{|1\rangle}, = 0.5 - 0.5, = 0.$$

Since we are using our IBM Q simulation results for calculating the expectation value, the accepted correct answers have a 0.07 tolerance.

45 Single-Qubit State Tomography: Experience III

Let us recall that the original density matrix implemented on the IBM Q Experience was

$$\rho_2 = |\psi_2\rangle\langle\psi_2| = \begin{pmatrix} 0.5 & 0.5i \\ -0.5i & 0.5 \end{pmatrix} \quad (104)$$

By measuring our system on three different bases, we can now reconstruct the original density matrix.

Quantum State Fidelity

Q: How well does state $|\psi\rangle$ represent state $|\phi\rangle$?

A: The Fidelity

$$F(|\psi\rangle, |\phi\rangle) = |\langle\psi|\phi\rangle|$$

$$0 \leq F \leq 1$$

$$F_{sq} = |\langle\psi|\phi\rangle|^2$$

Call this the “squared Fidelity”
→ Interpretable as a probability

Q: How well does state ρ represent state $|\phi\rangle$?

A: The Fidelity

$$F(|\phi\rangle, \rho) = \sqrt{\langle\phi|\rho|\phi\rangle}$$

$$= \max_{|\psi\rangle} |\langle\psi|\phi\rangle|$$

Where $|\psi\rangle$ is a “purification” of ρ

→ Interpretable as a maximum projection

Note: This is a common fidelity to compute in experiments

$|\phi\rangle$ = Ideal theoretical pure state

ρ = actual noisy experimental result

Figure 28: Quantum State Fidelity

Quantum Operations

In general, what legal $\rho \rightarrow E(\rho)$?

Define E is a valid quantum operations if and only if

(A1) $\text{Tr} [E(\rho)] = 1$ trace preserving

(A2) $E\left(\sum_k p_k \rho_k\right) = \sum_k p_k E(\rho_k)$ convex + linear
↑
probability distribution

(A3) a) if $\rho \geq 0 \rightarrow E(\rho) \geq 0$ positive

b) $(I_k \otimes E_0)(\rho_{k0}) \geq 0$ if $\rho_{k0} \geq 0$

Figure 29: Quantum Operations

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